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Author/s	Krzysztof Fuławka (CUP); Marcin Szumny (CUP); Piotr Mertuszka (CUP); Johnny van den Berg (MRP); Giorgia Stasi (GSB); Bruno Meyvis (GSB); Eberhard Falck (INTRAW); Vitor Correia (INTRAW); Marko Komac (INTRAW); George Bourmas (GM); Anton Koval (LTU); Bjorn Lindqvist (LTU); Glaciale Tiu (LTU); George Nikolakopoulos (LTU); Bob de Waard (SPE); Rene Deutsch (EPI); Panagiotis Koustoumpardis (UPAT); Athanasios Kokkinis (UPAT), Theodore Frantzis (UPAT), Konstantinos Skordis (UPAT); Fanie Terblanche (MRP -Elytica); Oskar Lindberg (EPI); Jan Gustafsson (EPI); Nicklas Fors (EPI); Laura Santas Moreu (DTU); Izabela Jaśkiewicz-Proć (CUP); Lech Stolecki (CUP); Vignsesh Kottayam Viswanathan (LTU); Sumeet Gajanan Satpute (LTU); Akash Patel (LTU); Wojciech Anacki (KGHM); Christian Burlet (GSB); Eduard van den Berg (MRP); Katarina Oquist (EPI)
Reviewer	Anton Koval (LTU); Pär-Erik Martinsson (LTU)

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Abstract	<p>The purpose of this document is to determine the requirements of end users of the technologies developed as part of the PERSEPHONE project. The requirements focus on hardware capabilities, the possibility of autonomous operation and the accuracy of the measurement devices used. All this in order to pave the way for the implementation of autonomous exploration and mining solutions in the future. In addition to describing individual technologies and specifying end-user requirements, the purpose of this document is also to define methods of evaluation and benchmarking of each solution.</p> <p>The information contained in D1.2 will be a reference point during the implementation of further parts of the PERSEPHONE project.</p>

History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
0.9 (draft)	9 May 2024	Initial draft of the document distributed between PP to review
1.0	15 May 2024	First version of document sent for revision to all PP
1.1	27 May 2024	The second, revised version of the document after taking into account the comments and remarks of the PERSEPHONE project partners
1.2	31 May 2024	Final, submitted version of document revised by all PP

Executive summary

The exploration of critical minerals in deep mines, abandoned mines, suspended mines or hard to reach deposits represents a new paradigm that exceeds the traditional approach to mineral exploration, geophysical sensing, geological mapping, and mining methods and operations. For this reason, WP1 focuses on defining a framework for PERSEPHONE technologies to be developed by:

- articulating the conceptual aspects of the project,
- acknowledging the scale of the data volumes that will be acquired for the project,
- justifying the rationale for removing people from harm, and
- augmenting all of the above by describing underground conditions for operating and abandoned mines giving general direction for the development of new technologies.

This creates a common vision, that ensures synchronised actions.

WP1 describes the technology areas to be developed by the PERSEPHONE project and assign lead partners responsible for each of these. Furthermore WP1 provide end-user requirements for exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits as well as for exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines. The PERSEPHONE project acknowledges the importance of compliance to existing regulatory codes and as exploration is an integral part of the project and by implication the reporting of Resources and Reserves, pays particular attention to the requirements of the UNFC/UNRMS/CRIRSCO codes to ensure compliance. Measurable benchmarking specifications as mechanisms that will be used to contextualise and gauge the overall impact of the PERSEPHONE project are also described.

Finally, as any mining project is only as good as the foundation it is built on, the requirements for the automation of geological models is clearly articulated with particular reference to the data requirements.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	
3D	Three dimensional
AC	Alternating Current
ADSUM	Accrual, Depletion, Shrinkage, Ullage, Movement
APF	Artificial Potential Field
ARD	Acid Rock Drainage
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CAPEX	Capital expenditures
CBRR	Comissão Brasileira de Recursos e Reservas
CCRR	Comisión Colombiana de Recursos y Reservas Minerales
CIM	Canadian Institute of Mining, Metallurgy and Petroleum
CMMI	Council of Mining and Metallurgical Institutes
CRIRSCO	Committee For Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards
CRM	Critical Raw Material
CUP	KGHM CUPRUM Ltd. R&D Centre
DARPA	Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency
DG ENV	Directorate-General for the Environment
DIANE	Discontinuous, Inhomogeneous, Anisotropic, and Non-elastic
DT	Digital Twin
DTU	Technical University of Denmark
DUV	Deep ultraviolet
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EPI	EPIROC ROCK DRILLS AB
EPRP	Emergency Preparedness and Response Planning
ERT	Electrical Resistivity Tomography
ESG	Environmental, societal and governance (aspects)
EU-OSHA	European Agency for Safety & Health at Work
EWD	Extractive Waste Directive
FA	Focus Area
FDEM	Hybrid finite-discrete element method
FEM	Finite Element Method
GCP	Ground control point
GM	Grecian Magnesite Mining Industrial Shipping and Commercial Company Societe Anonyme
GNC	Guidance, Navigation & Control
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRA	Geotechnical Risk Assessment
GSB	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
ICMM	International Council on Mining and Metals
ICOLD	International Commission on Large Dams
ID	Identity
INTRAW	International Raw Materials Observatory AISBL

IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IP	Induced polarization
IP	Ingress Protection (electrical equipment)
ISL	<i>In situ</i> -leaching
IT	Information Technology
JORC	Joint Ore Reserves Committee
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KAZRC	Kazakhstan Reporting Code
KCMI	Komite Cadangan Mineral Indonesia
KGHM	KGHM Polska Miedź S.A.
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LED	Light Emitting Diode
LIBS	Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LOM	Life of Mine
LoRa WAN	Long Range Wide Area Network
LTU	Luleå University of Technology
MI	Magnetic Induction
MIREU	Mining and Metallurgy Regions of EU
ML	Machine learning
MPC	Model Predictive Control
MPIGM	Mongolian Professional Institute of Geosciences And Mining
MRM	Mineral Resource Management
MWD	Measurement while drilling
NACRI	The quasi-real-time committee for Reporting Mineral Resources and Reserves in India
NIR	Near infrared
NORM	Naturally occurring radioactive mineral
OPEX	Operating expenses
OSH	Operational safety and health
PERC	The Pan European Reserves and Resources Reporting Committee
PFS	Project Feasibility Study
R2R	Record-to-report
RF	Radio frequency
RoM	Run-of-Mine
SAMESG	South African guideline for the reporting of environmental, social and governance
SAMREK	The South African Code for the Reporting of Exploration Results, Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves
SASB	Sustainability Accounting Standards Board
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SLAM	Simultaneous localization and mapping
SLO	Social license for operation
SME	Society for Mining, Metallurgy & Exploration (USA)

SoA	State-of-the-art
SoTA	State-of-the-art
SOM	Self-organizing maps
SP	Self-potential method
SPE	SPECTRAL INDUSTRIES BV
SWIR	Short Wavelength InfraRed
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UNFC	UNITED NATONS FRAMEWORK FOR CLASSIFICATION OF RESOURCES
UNRMS	THE UNITED NATIONS RESOURCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
UMREK	National Resources and Reserves Reporting Committee (Turkey)
UV	Ultraviolet
UV-VIS	Ultraviolet visible
VOC	Volatile organic compound
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WP	Work package
Y2K	The year 2000

1 Introduction

1.1 Conceptual aspects for developing PERSEPHONE project

PERSEPHONE project aims to revolutionize sustainable mining practices, considering factors such as ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) standards, end-user needs for exploration and extraction, geodetic mapping, navigation systems etc. The project's success relies on finding the right combination of all of them and addressing these challenges effectively. This section describes the aspects involved across various work packages (WP2- WP3-WP4-WP5) to bring the project closer to reality.

Understanding the needs and technological gaps in sustainable mining is essential for PERSEPHONE's success. Addressing these gaps and leveraging existing technologies, while also drawing inspiration from nature, ensures the development of effective solutions. This approach guarantees that the project meets the evolving demands of sustainable mining practices.

The project's development entails the consideration of various aspects of research.

- **Observing nature for inspiration:** Nature provides a rich source of inspiration for solving mining challenges. By studying how plants and animals adapt to their environments, the PERSEPHONE project uses biomimicry—imitating nature's designs and processes. For example, we're inspired by insect colonies when envisioning a swarm of modular robots. Like insects, these robots work together efficiently, with each one specialised for specific tasks. This helps them navigate tight spaces in mines and collaborate seamlessly on different missions. The physical intelligence of ant and robot collectives (Harvard.edu, 2022).
- **Locomotion:** Robots play a crucial role in mining operations, and their locomotion methods must be carefully chosen based on the environment and tasks at hand. Options include wheeled locomotion for flat surfaces, legged and screw locomotion for uneven terrain, flying locomotion for aerial tasks, and mixed locomotion for enhanced versatility.
 - **Wheeled Locomotion:** Well-suited for flat, smooth surfaces, wheeled robots offer quick and efficient movement.
 - **Legged Locomotion:** Mimicking animal motion, legged robots excel in navigating challenging terrains like uneven surfaces and stairs.
 - **Omnidirectional Screw Locomotion:** Articulated screw propulsion has been developed to operate vehicles in soft, wet terrains such as marsh, snow, and water, and adapted to robots (Lugo et al., 2017).
 - **Flying Locomotion:** Drones enable aerial tasks such as surveillance and mapping, providing valuable insights from above.
 - **Mixed Locomotion:** Combining different locomotion methods (wheeled, legged, crawling, swimming, flying, etc.) enhances a robot's adaptability and efficiency in diverse environments.
- **Navigation:** Navigation systems in mining present unique challenges, including maintaining communication between different modules.

Effective navigation is crucial for optimising operations and ensuring safety.

- **Manipulation:** Manipulation capabilities, tailored to the project's objectives, involve grasping, moving, and drilling. Understanding the specific needs of mining environments, including drilling techniques and equipment, is essential for success.

The approach, defined as the methodological strategy for tackling tasks, is exemplified in Prototyping and Simulation: The project entails developing CAD prototypes, followed by Finite Element Method (FEM) analysis and 3D rendering. Simulation aids in comprehending the environment and behaviour of the robots, thereby guiding further design iterations.

In Integration and Collaboration, mechanical engineering solutions are assimilated across various work packages, collaborating with other disciplines to effectively achieve project objectives.

1.2 Purpose and scope of the document

PERSEPHONE has as its stated objective the developing of innovative technologies for smart and integrated exploration of deep mines and abandoned mines. It is envisaged that terabytes of data will be generated in this pursuit, some possibly in formats and with attributes that have never been used before. The data so created will include sensor data used for the classification of rock types, directions of primary stresses in the forefront of mining works, and other measurable geotechnical properties vital to predicting support requirements. In constructing geomodels the digital twin would also need: GNC sensors data for spatial referencing of geological features, machine positioning and setting, pre-developed infrastructure to determine optimal tramming routes, and vehicle positioning.

The generation of such massive amounts of data from various sources and in diverse formats necessitates the integration of all this data. However, the integration is not intuitive by nature, as the data is created in disparate software packages and technical silos by subject matter experts that have very specific briefs and are governed by narrow codes of conduct. Consequently, the interaction between different datasets is severely restricted and leads to long lag times for results and decision-making.

Data integration in a digital twin solves this constraint, as it becomes intuitive through a process of interoperability that effectively translates the "technical languages" used in specialist disciplines into a common understanding.

1.3 Related information

1.3.1 The rational for removing people from harm

1.3.1.1 *Satisfying needs; a means of achieving the objective*

Maslow developed the hierarchy of human needs in 1943 and it had a profound impact on understanding human behaviour. The theory is based on the belief that humans are motivated by their needs. It also holds that if a lower-level need is not satisfied the motivation to aspire for higher-level needs will be absent.

The progression of technological advances during PERSEPHONE will follow the same patterns. Successful discoveries during the initial stages will drive the need for further discovery. Figure 1.1 (below) shows the areas of impact for the project, let's call that the basic needs. Each of these areas will have a unique set of needs which will be discussed in more detail.

Figure 1.1. Combined Hierarchy of needs for PERSEPHONE.

1.3.1.2 *The beginning of mining*

Digging and crawling in sub-terrain tunnels is not a natural human activity although there is archaeological evidence of the palaeolithic humans mining hematite more than 40,000 years ago in the Ngwenya mountains of Swaziland, in the southern regions of Africa.

Mining techniques have evolved from the early days of digging by hand to Neanderthals discovering and mining flint in Hungary and using this to make tools for mining. Mining techniques evolved and by 1627 in the Hungarian town of Banská Štiavnica explosives were introduced, a technique that rapidly spread across the world. It follows that the explosives worked better when placed in a confined void as this caused most damage to the surrounding rock. Before the advent of mechanical rock drills in its many forms and configurations of today, a worker would hold the tip of the drill steel (jumper) against the rock face whilst another worker would smash it with a hammer. A very slow, laborious and extremely dangerous activity, it was rare to find a jumper guy with all his fingers still intact.

Despite all the advances in mining methods and techniques, today humans still have to be in close proximity of the rock face to convert in situ rock to broken rock, an unavoidable step in extracting minerals from the crust of the earth.

1.3.1.3 *The role of autonomous mining equipment*

According to researchers at McKinsey & Company 2024 was a tipping point for the autonomous-vehicle industry. Although leading players were able to successfully run and scale their first commercial operations and increase their funding, others saw significant setbacks, stopped or reduced their operations, or exited the

market entirely. With this in mind, there is still much to be done before the autonomous vehicle industry is fully mature—but how much?

Of significant importance for PERSEPHONE to consider is the expected timeline and the impact of regulation on the ability to bring full autonomy to the market. When compared to the previous survey of 2021 (McKinsey & Company, 2024), respondents have indicated a two-year lag from the previous expectation making “robot miners” only available in 2030. The reasons for this shift are ongoing technical obstacles and challenges with capital availability. This is exacerbated by a growing concern amongst mining owners and leaders in the autonomous-vehicle industry that regulation for operating autonomous vehicles will ultimately be the final bottleneck to introduce autonomy to the industry.

Software development is expected to be the major consumer of capital investments estimated to be more than \$10 billion. Alongside validation costs, software development will be crucial for pushing the technology forward and demonstrating its safety. Among needed software, respondents ranked prediction algorithms and perception software as the most critical (McKinsey & Company, 2024).

The future of autonomous drill rigs in the next five years is poised to be transformative, with significant advancements expected in technology and operations. These trends indicate a shift towards more autonomous, efficient, and environmentally conscious drilling operations. We will likely see the drilling industry leveraging these advancements to meet the growing energy demands while addressing economic and environmental challenges.

The subareas listed below will play a key role of importunacy for the autonomous advancements specifically in future mining excavation.

- **Technological Advancement:** The drilling industry is anticipated to continue its trajectory towards more sophisticated technologies. This includes drilling control systems to enhance performance times.
- **Operational Efficiency:** With the adoption of advanced technologies, drilling operations are expected to become more time-efficient and cost-effective. The focus will be on selecting the best technologies and tools, optimising procedures, solving problems concretely, making accurate predictions, and rapid decision-making.
- **Environmental Considerations:** Efforts to minimise the environmental footprint of drilling activities will be a significant factor driving innovation. This involves developing technologies that can improve operational and economic performance while being environmentally responsible.
- **Digital Transformation:** The industry is likely to embrace digital technologies further, incorporating AI and automation to increase speed and efficiency. Well construction, in particular, may benefit from intelligent technologies that encode knowledge and capture learnings to improve drilling efficiency.
- **Cross-Industry Adoption:** Potential technologies from other industries could be adopted, pushing the conventional boundaries of drilling

operations. This cross-pollination of ideas and technologies can lead to breakthroughs in drilling system design and operations.

- **Automation vs. Autonomy:** While automation plays a key role in improving efficiency, the industry requires advanced autonomy capabilities to fundamentally and continuously transform performance. This means moving beyond the current limits of automation to achieve greater consistency and efficiency in well construction.
- **Technological Integration:** The integration of various technologies such as AI, machine learning, and IoT (Internet of Things) will likely lead to smarter, more efficient drilling operations that can adapt to changing underground conditions.
- **Cross-Industry Collaboration:** The drilling industry may see increased collaboration with other sectors to adopt and adapt technologies that can improve drilling operations. This could include advanced materials, robotics, and communication systems.

These advancements will accelerate the underground mining industry Technology transformation are moving towards a more automated, efficient, and environmentally friendly future, with safety as a paramount concern.

1.3.2 Mapping and localization system

One of the biggest challenges facing PERSEPHONE is to deliver a system that can accurately locate objects such as voids, solid rock faces, and other mining features and then plot their point-in-time position accurately on a co-ordinate reference grid in a CAD system. This has to be achieved without the benefit of having line-of-site to survey control points.

The dilemma of developing excavations at equipment scale and not human scale contribute directly to the complexity of establishing a proper survey control network due to the increase in “skinny” triangles brought about by the narrowing of development tunnels. The absence of humans in the working place also means that an autonomous vehicle should be equipped to physically install survey control points to a level of accuracy acceptable to legislators and the survey industry.

Current practice is to regularly perform check surveys to validate the accuracy of the survey control network. In an autonomous world this function would have to be performed by the autonomous fleet. This can only be achieved if the survey points are able to communicate with the autonomous fleet and the density of control points are drastically intensified.

1.3.2.1 *The hierarchy of needs for mapping and location systems*

Achieving the **Autonomous Extension & Maintenance of Survey Control Network** means a reality where survey control points are installed on demand by autonomous equipment – a digital surveyor, so to speak - driven and controlled by artificial intelligence. The location, intensity, and frequency of survey control points (pegs) is a highly repetitive process and can easily be defined by pre-determined parameters.

It is safe to assume that leveraging the recent advances in autonomous mining equipment, equipment building companies should have the capability to **Develop Technology to build and install Active Pegs**, i.e., the digital surveyor.

The challenge lies in the ability of the digital surveyor to locate and recognize previously installed survey pegs in order to make sufficient and relevant observations to continue the survey traverse by installing more pegs along the development tunnels. The technology of tracking & tracing of autonomous equipment and for generating digital twins of the workings rely heavily on relative positioning. Relative to other equipment, relative to geological features, relative to infrastructure and relative to the geoid earth. It is the last component that refers to absolute positioning which requires constant referencing to the survey control network. In the envisaged humanless environment survey control is required to continuously broadcast its location and for that, it needs energy giving rise to the **Adoption of Perpetual Batteries** to supply the energy required.

The science of using precise satellite positioning and trilateration to determine the position of a GPS receiver on earth is applicable to achieve this objective. However, the impact of total darkness, much shorter distances and poor-quality air will have to be tested and will require the **Adoption and Modification of Algorithms** to cater for the operating requirements.

It is possible to simulate the conditions described above in a laboratory, research in the technology mentioned is ongoing over many years are in various stages of development. It is therefore feasible to **Establish a Laboratory to test Autonomous Survey Control**. Overall hierarchy of needs is shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2. Hierarchy for Mapping & Location Systems.

1.3.3 The physical mining environment

In the early 1990's when the feasibility study of one of the world's deepest mines, the then AngloGold American's, Moab Khotsong mine in the North-West province in South Africa was conducted, the primary consideration was not mining grade as is always the case. As it was contiguous to the Great Nologwa and Kopanang shafts the confidence in geological and grade continuity was relatively high. The critical questions were about the ability and costs to create life-sustaining conditions at depths in excess of 3 km and the costs of lifting 200,000 tons per

month vertically in a single hoist from 3 km below the surface. The ingenuity of mankind prevailed, and 4 km is the new frontier that is being tested.

Although mining at these depths is not expected in Europe, underground mines are mined from the top and it can therefore be expected that mines will become deeper with it all the challenges associated with mining at depth.

Mining at increased depth will demand the consideration of the following:

1. Geotechnical complexity will increase and alternative rules for support patterns, tunnel designs, excavation dimensions, extraction rates, and mining sequences will have to be tested and adopted.
2. Creating a **life-sustaining environment** for humans during the transition to humanless mining becomes more challenging, a continuous supply of breathable air invariably requires higher volumes of air forced down the infrastructure with a concomitant increase in fan capacity. This results in an increase in energy consumption with a concomitant increase in costs as well as the impact of creating energy on the environment. In order to harvest the advances in the development of geothermal energy in Europe to combat the negative impact of geothermal gradient on the operating environment this project will seek close co-operation with the Committee of Industry, Research and Energy of the European Parliament.

This section should be read in conjunction with the 2023 publication of the Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies, authored by Matteo CIUCCI.

1.3.3.1 *The hierarchy of needs for physical conditions*

The project will **create test environments** – both virtual (refer to digital twin) and physical laboratory simulations to test the outcomes of the needs listed below.

Cognizant of the opinion that there is a growing concern amongst mining owners and leaders in the autonomous-vehicle industry that regulation for operating autonomous machines will be important obstructers to implementing autonomy in the industry, hence this project will publish recommendations for the **establishment of regulatory frameworks and authorities** to ensure an orderly and timeous transition to full autonomy in mining. *At this point, it is also envisaged that the regulations for mining equipment and street-going vehicles be separated to avoid the mining industry becoming an inconsequential heir of overly stringent regulation of street-going autonomous vehicles.*

Considering the challenges in creating physical life-sustaining conditions as described above it will be impetuous to assume that autonomous vehicles will be able to operate in the native physical conditions created in deep-level mining – even if it is humanless. The challenge for this project is to **define life-sustaining conditions for autonomous vehicles**, and then find the economic equilibrium between altering the physical conditioning and adopting the autonomous equipment to suit.

The outcomes of the suitability tests below will be used to **scale mine designs for equipment use** as opposed to the current design dimensions fit for human scale.

Mine designs have evolved to adjust to working conditions, mining methods, and technology available. Although research and publications for autonomous systems can be found, the focus is more on localization and tracking. Therefore, this project will perform tests to determine the suitability of **current mine designs for autonomous vehicles** related to manoeuvrability, effectiveness, and general fit with simulation software. The overall hierarchy of needs for physical conditions is presented in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3. Hierarchy for Physical Condition.

1.3.4 Drilling systems and peripherals

It is safe to say that remote drilling is at the forefront of automation in the hard rock mining industry. In many mines, drill rigs move autonomously to new drilling positions and have the capability to auto-navigate to the designed collar position of a new hole and drill holes at a designed dip and on a pre-designed azimuth. Machines can autonomously add drill rods and even change the drill bit when required. Recent developments translate mechanical properties generated during the drilling process to report data related to drilling speed, penetration rate, rotation speed, as well as hydraulic and physical pressure. Typically, this data is auto-attributed and used to build 3D rock hardness models which in turn can be translated into geological models.

The business process transformation journey from basic automation to Artificial Intelligence is well articulated and defined and at variable levels of transformation across a wide spectrum of industries. These transformation stages are:

- **Basic Automation** – all parts of the processes are triggered by humans, there are very simple rules governing the process, and there is no integration with other systems.
- **Robotic Process Automation** – more than one system could be involved and therefore parts of the process may be triggered by humans and the mundane parts are triggered by interoperable processes, the rules are still simple but because high volumes can be handled it is more complex, the

process can only work with structured data, and it can interact at enterprise level.

- **Enhanced Process Automation** – human thinking is augmented by basic analytics and decision support, unstructured data is introduced via intelligent document processing and optical character recognition, and integration is extended to basic web applications such as company search engines.
- **Algorithmic Automation** – complex data-based decision-making is possible with humans selecting the best option, the decision is informed by predictive and prescriptive analytics, rudimentary machine learning with basic reasoning may even suggest the best decision, unstructured & big data comes into the equation and impacts the complexity of algorithms, and advanced IoT integration is possible.
- **Artificial Intelligence** – cognitive technology emulates human decision-making capability, end-to-end autonomy including reasoning and hypothesizing, deep learning linked to neural networks, speech recognition and generation, augmented & virtual reality.

1.3.4.1 *The hierarchy of needs for drilling*

The combination of technology developed for mapping and location systems, preparing and creating life-sustaining conditions, and autonomous drilling will deliver **Fully Autonomous Humanless Drilling**.

Developing **sensor technology to determine the mineral quality** of resources in real-time is simultaneously the most ambitious and most critical for the successful outcome of this project. Standard operating procedures for validation protocols, intervention actions, and geostatistical interpretation will be developed and published as industry guidelines.

Understanding that drilling is the precursor to blasting rock – liberating it from the crust of the Earth - puts it in its rightful place in the value chain. Having an uninterrupted supply of drilling consumables is the apex in the mining value chain. Yet, due to the lack of interoperability between enterprise resource planning solutions and mineral resource management systems, this space is still largely un-serviced. The digitalization of drilling hardware and software provides the ideal opportunity for an **Autonomous Consumable Supply System**.

Currently, cameras strategically placed on drill rigs allow the operator to control, navigation and position the rig in the workplace where drilling is required. Using on-board lasers, the drill rig is navigated and positioned to a high degree of accuracy ensuring that the drilling is executed according to the drill plan. All without having to start the diesel engine. Technology development to replace the current navigation system with **Sensor-based location and Navigation** is well advanced and translates to increased rig utilization, increased productivity and fewer travels to the machine, keeping the operator away from risky areas.

By moving the joystick controlling the drill rig from the cabin to a remote-control room the drill rig operator is also moved to the control room thereby enabling **Remote Access Drilling**. All actions - drill, tram, navigate, and drill again are

enabled from a remote position with the benefit of having one controller in control of multiple rigs. The hierarchy of needs for drilling can be seen in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4. Hierarchy for Drilling.

1.3.5 Geomodelling requirements

Geomodelling is the sophisticated method of creating a geomodel, which is a numerical representation of physical geological features based on geological observations made on and below the earth's surface. It involves the natural sciences branches of Geology, Geotechnics, and Geophysics. It is dependent on other disciplines in the mine technical domain such as Survey, Volumetric Sciences, and even Finances to provide a complete picture. Recent changes in environmental and sustainable expectations of mining companies resulted in the development of geometallurgical models. Traditionally geology would be part of the mineral resources management domain and have little regard for the requirements for the metallurgical domain.

There is growing support for the hypothesis that the production process can do much more to support the environmental and sustainable efforts of the metallurgical works, which normally take the full brunt of unhappy communities in regard to undesired outcomes of mining.

Although this project finds its conclusion at geomodels development of systems and solutions will be mindful of the needs of and impact on geometallurgical models. Intuitive hook-in points will thus be left open, allowing seamless integration with metallurgical attribution requirements in future developments.

1.3.5.1 Components of geomodels

- **Structural Framework** – The mining industry is one of the many beneficiaries of the rise in fully three 3-dimensional visualizations brought about by the introduction in 2006 of 64-bit Technology. This allowed mining software companies to respond to the increasing demand to create spatial data and to provide interoperability of mining data from disparate data create sources. The visualization of the geomodel is not only restricted to data related directly to geology such as structure of mineral quality anymore, but also include the mining infrastructure – both planned

and actual achieved, access to utilities and drilling platforms when planning exploration and infill drilling, and off course sighting of target areas on the micro and macro level.

A practical example is the size of pixels; in order to produce high-resolution images of the ore body and all the related images that complete the visual, it is beneficial to have the finest level of granularity. Another benefit, although not directly attributed to 64-bit bit development due to it, is the speed at which computers run. Working with big data sets becomes frustrating if you spend most of your time looking at a spinning hourglass.

- **Rock type classification** – The purpose of the geomodel is to allow users to identify mineralization zones – the parts where ore minerals have been deposited, ore – the part of the mineralised zone that has potential for eventual economics extraction, waste rock – the rock that will be removed during extraction but have no economic value, country rock – the part that is left behind, and geological structures – the effect of younger geological incidents on the orebody. The classification takes place during the original creation of the geomodel and is updated as and when new relevant and material data obtained from the sampling regime, exploration program, production drilling, and geological observations are available.

Rock-type classification can also include attributes such as rock hardness, lithology, colour, tensile strength, and many more. Data attributes are used to group, combine, filter, sort, compare, screen, and organize data. It is therefore critical that the right attributes are selected at the outset. The range of attributes will normally be determined by the end-user requirements. In an integrated environment, the geomodel will not only be used by geologists but also by mining engineers to create mine design geometries and schedules, competent persons for the classification of resources and reserves, ventilation and environmental engineers to create life-sustaining environments, geotechnical engineers to design and validate extraction sequencing models, drill & blast engineers, load & haul engineers, and surveyors.

- **Estimation** – once the geomodel is completed and the location of the mineralization zones and the geological structures such as faults, dykes, and intrusions have been delineated, the question of “where is it” has been answered. The second question to answer is how “much of it” is there? The objective of this determinant (grade) is to understand what the potential for eventual economic extraction is.
 - Is there a demand for this mineral, metal, or stones?
 - Is the quality/quantity enough to pay for the cost of development, exploitation, beneficiation, and rehabilitation?
 - Is the confidence in grade and geological continuity enough to convince investors to part with their hard-earned money to fund the venture?

The number of techniques to determine the grade are many and variable and range from basic rudimentary mathematics to mathematics that require sophisticated algorithms to find resolution. Until now human interpretation is the final determinant, and despite all the research done in the field of human behaviour, human conduct remains unpredictable and becomes corruptible under the right conditions. Many reporting codes have been developed to ensure consistency in the human factor by creating qualifications and specifications for professionals that make resource estimates.

The Australian industry established a committee known as the Joint Ore Reserves Committee (JORC). This committee published the first version of the JORC Code in 1989. That code was to become the foundation on which all recently developed national codes are built. In 1997 the need for international standards and stronger control on the reporting of mineral information was made painfully obvious by the Bre-X scandal concerning the fictitious Busang gold deposit in Indonesia. Even though it was recognized that regulations alone could not have stopped Bre-X from happening, the lack of standards, and the lack of procedure to ensure that these standards are followed, was perceived as a significant contributing factor (Camisani-Calzolari, 2024). CRIRSCO (2024) has been set up as a coordinating body for the national and regional reporting standards. The relevant reporting standard for Europe is PERC-Standard (2024). For further discussions on mineral resource and reserve reporting and classification see also Section 6.3.

1.3.5.2 The hierarchy of needs for automated geomodelling

Validation of new software and ensuring quality compliance remains a challenge for software development companies. It is not expected that it will be different in the case of PERSEPHONE. The software will not only be tested on the two operations below but will include the **Creation and Testing of Geomodels** on datasets available from an extensive client base.

To ensure that the geomodel **incorporates reporting codes and rules and** supports the uptake of the EU Critical Raw Materials Act, the PERSEPHONE project will ensure alignment with the UNITED NATIONS FRAMEWORK FOR CLASSIFICATION OF RESOURCES (UNFC) requirements. Reporting codes and the UNFC classification system are extensively covered in Section 6 of this document.

Drilling is not only the precursor to blasting rock – in many cases, but also the first instance of “touching” the ore body. This interaction with the ore body in the form of a drilled core, drilling chips, or pictures enables the geologist to create a representation of the geological structure of the mineral deposit. This is the “where it is” part of the model-building process. The next part is where the rock is sampled, and the quality of the mineral content is determined through assaying or scanning. This is the “how much are there” part of the model-building process. The PERSEPHONE project will use two types of data to **develop algorithms to automate the process of “where it is” and “how much of it is there”**. High-

intensity lasers combined with high-density spectral photogrammetry will be used to determine the mineral quality while physical properties recorded with Measure While Drilling techniques will be used to determine the physical properties of the rock.

Mining is not a one-size-fits-all operation, and developers of software will agree that a lot of work performed in mining is repetitive and can therefore be parameterized through the appropriate application of mathematical algorithms. However, there is always the exception to the rule in all operations that calls for a certain portion of the solution to be fit-for-purpose. The PERSEPHONE project has **identified two operating mines as sources from where to procure data** to build the automated geomodels.

Determining the data requirements for a Geomodel is described in detail in Section 8 of this document. It is critical to understand the end-state requirements of the geomodel as articulated by the end-users in order to develop the software to achieve these objectives. The hierarchy for developing a geomodel is shown in Figure 1.5.

Figure 1.5. Hierarchy for Geological Model.

1.3.6 Expected mineral ore

A properly compiled Resource and Reserve statement/report is the only artefact investors and analysts have at their disposal to determine the real economic value of a mining operation. Artefact in this context means something observed in a scientific investigation or experiment that is not natively present but occurs as a result of the preparative or investigative procedure. It holds therefore that if the R&R statement is flawed, the valuation of the operation will also be flawed. The history, objectives and justification for developing reporting codes and enforce adherence to these codes is widely described in Section 6 of this document, suffice to say for now that it is in the interest of owners, investors, communities, legislators, and all other interested and affected parties that R&R statements is as close to reality as possible.

The expression of the **expected mineral ore**, which is the product that is delivered to the metallurgical works and from which the final economic commodity is liberated is entirely dependent on the R&R Statement.

1.3.6.1 Components of the expected mineral ore

- **Mineral Resources** – it is a concentration or occurrence of material of economic interest in or on the earth's crust in such form, quality and quantity that there are reasonable and realistic prospects for eventual economic extraction. The path of the classification process of mineral resources is presented in Figure 1.6.

Figure 1.6. Path to Classification of Mineral Resource.

- **Mineral Reserve** – it is the economically mineable material derived from Measured and Indicated Resource, includes dilution and contaminating materials and allows for losses expected during mining, it is assessed to pre-feasibility level (for projects) and Life of Mine level (for operations), and modification by mining, metallurgical, economic, marketing legal, social, environmental and governmental factors have been considered and those applicable must be disclosed. The path of the classification process of mineral reserves can be seen in Figure 1.7.

Figure 1.7. Path to Classification of Mineral Reserve.

The role of **Information Technology** and the pressure facing software and hardware companies to develop appropriate technology to satisfy the demand of mining companies to remain lucrative to investors was realised very early. *The use of Information Technology in the Mineral Resource Management environment* (Van Zyl Visser, 2003) published as early as 2003 illustrates this point. The paper describes how the then technology could be deployed to remove the latency in determining Expected Mineral Ore and recognizes the importance in inter-

discipline integration and intra-domain interoperability. The graphic below (Figure 1.8), taken from the paper is significant in that it shows the relationship between Business, MRM, and IT which at the time of the publication of this paper in 2003, was hardly articulated or recognized.

Figure 1.8. Showing the interdependency between business, MRM and IT (Van Zyl Visser, 2003).

Analysts and Industry Advisors became more sophisticated which pressurized mine operators and owners to improve their responses to the market – both in the fields of descriptive and predictive analytics. At the same time technology companies, have survived the Y2K scare and have obliterated the lull in income created by the turn-of-the-millennium threat. Software companies, in particular, were developing software packages based on a narrow spectrum and were driven by commercial value. MRM practitioners were in the proverbial vice grip having to answer changing questions from operators with software that was not well suited to the challenge. In 2010 at the 38th International Society of Mine Surveying Presidium the MRM fraternity issued a very strong ultimatum to software developers – “provide us with the solutions we require or face the consequences”. What followed was a vast improvement in collaboration between mining companies in the form of user groups and consortiums and between mining companies and suppliers. Although the industry has matured a lot since 2003 and the technology made major strides, the eternal truth in the diagram above remains valid more than 20 years later.

1.3.6.2 The hierarchy of needs for expected mineral ore

The culmination of all the technologies investigated, tested, and hypothesized in the PERSEPHONE Project will apex in the production of a **UNFC-compliant report**.

- Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes.
- Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems and Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics.
- Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator.
- Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions.
- Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination.
- High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations.
- On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment.
- Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization.

The technology developed in PERSEPHONE will allow users to maintain an accurate **R&R inventory** as all transactions impacting on the inventory status is maintained in near real-time by applying the ADSUM - **A**ccrual, **D**epletion, **S**hrinkage, **U**llage, **M**ovement – principle, a method applied in the supply chain industry and Enterprise Resource Planning solutions for many years.

The UNFC reporting code calls for the classification of Resources and Reserves in a 3-dimensional matrix representing three distinct categories. Rules for the categorization into the prescribed classes for the E-Axis and F-axis will be developed.

- The **E-Axis** designates the degree of favourability of environmental-socio-economic and governance (ESG) conditions in establishing the viability of the project, including consideration of market prices and relevant legal, regulatory, social, environmental, and contractual conditions.
- The **F-Axis** designates the maturity of technology, studies, and commitments necessary to implement the project. These projects range from early conceptual studies through to fully developed projects that produce and reflect standard value-chain management principles.

Algorithms based on temporal, spatial, and sample density rules will be incorporated into the automated Geomodel software to represent the confidence in the geological and grade continuation of the deposit.

- The **G-Axis** designates the degree of confidence in the estimate of the quantities of products from the project. This will ensure that only Resources and Reserves that qualify according to the definitions stated in 1.2.6.1 are included in the scope of work to be conducted for the classification of the E-, and F-Axis.

Even though the rules for reporting are clearly defined in the code it also allows for the interpretation of the competent person to ensure that the nuances of local geology, the restrictions or allowances of local legislation, and compliance with

the local social licence to mine is reflected in the reporting. The code will therefore be **adapted by the competent person and adopted by the R&R committee**. The hierarchy of needs for expected mineral ore is shown in Figure 1.9.

Figure 1.9. Hierarchy of needs for Expected Mineral Ore.

1.3.7 Digital Twin creation

Imagine a world where the impact of decisions that have the potential to destroy value in a company are tested and various alternative outcomes are simulated before the most appropriate one is selected. The application of Digital Twins is proving to be the capability needed to deliver this heightened degree of certainty. A Digital Twin is a digitally enabled virtual representation of a physical object or environment. All aspects of the Digital Twin are identical to the real-world instance that it represents, which requires it to be linked to real data sources that update the twin in real-time or near real-time as defined by the user. With proper integration, the twin's data sources are unrestricted and source-code agnostic.

Typical Construction of a Digital Twin

A Digital Twin is made-up of layers of data. Just as geology is the basis of any mining venture in the physical world, so is the global geological structural model in the virtual world always a good place to start. The structure model typically shows the mineralised areas plus all associated structures that had an influence on the formation of geological zones or facies if they are the oldest, or that impacted on the shape and relative position if they are younger. An example of a geological structural model is presented in Figure 1.10.

Figure 1.10. The DT starts with the geological structural model.

The geological structural model can hide many features that have an impact on the mining method, the mine design, and the mining sequence. As these can't be separated in the physical world, it is imperative to have the capability to do so in the virtual world. Figure 1.11 shows such an expanded view with the structures such as faults and dykes separated from the ore blocks demarcated according to the various facies' classification. The distinction of facies is based on the various attributes determined by the exploration program and continuously augmented by further infill drilling and even MWD data from production (blast-hole) drilling.

Figure 1.11. Exploded view of structures and facies.

In the case of an operational mine, the next step will be to integrate the infrastructure data (Figure 1.12).

Figure 1.12. The structure with added infrastructure.

The infrastructure data consisting of 3D scans of the development network, is integrated from the volumetric sciences solution. On older mines or for older and abandoned areas of the mine, electronic scans from hand drafted plans representing the infrastructure and previously mined areas may be the source of the data. In this case, 3D resolution will be provided by vertical extrusion of the geometries.

Data such as the co-ordinates of survey control points, attributes related to the provenance of the working places such as workplace name, date of mining, equipment identifiers, mining crew data, support installed, geological and ventilation observations, drilling data, rock type or facies, and many more will be integrated. If the planned extraction plan is available this will be added. The extraction plan, consisting of the mine design, sequence and schedule is normally integrated from the planning solution in use. An example of an integrated plan is shown in Figure 1.13.

Figure 1.13. Tunnel design and drill rings as designed in relation to the infrastructure.

The next step is to add the mine design elements (Figure 1.14). It is possible to add multiple versions of the plan based on the level of planning – Life of Mine Plan, Business Plan, Tactical Plan, or Short-Term Plan; or on the planning horizon Life of Mine, 5-year, 24-months, or 7-day plan.

Figure 1.14. Future Development Schedule added.

The basic building blocks of the Digital Twin are in place and the twin can be visualised (Figure 1.15).

Figure 1.15. The Digital Twin with the geology added.

Now that the geological structure is visible, the current and historic infrastructure is orientated and the future mine design, sequence and schedule added, it is a good time to add the quality parameters, in this case in the form of the grade block model (Figure 1.16). These are the basic building blocks of the Digital Twin.

Figure 1.16. With the Block Grade Model added.

The power of the Digital Twin is in the capacity to provide behavioural insights and visualization derived from the data providing the ability to:

- Track execution as it happens (Figure 1.17) – identifying flaws and reacting appropriately to rectify this behaviour will result in significant improvement in the quality of mining.

Figure 1.17. A 2D view of one mining level showing various spatial PKI's related to production activities, tunnel statuses, volumes, and inventories.

- Track compliance to plan – accepting that the plan is optimal, any deviation to the plan reduces the optimality of the expected planned outcomes (Figure 1.18).

Figure 1.18. A 2d spatial dashboard showing equipment movement, fuel levels, and various infrastructure related KPI's.

- Monitoring operational conditions (Figure 1.19) – the physical conditions and operating environment in an underground mine can become a threat to human life. This can't go undetected if stringent safety standards are to be adhered to.

Figure 1.19. A heatmap showing the ingress of waste.

- Monitoring asset health – deviation from predetermined parameters for machine, human, and mineral performance act as early warning indicators.
- Removing the lid from the mine – providing visibility at planning meetings, shift line-out sessions, and even investor interactions.

- Create a single source for all data – translates to a single version of the truth.
- Improve sustainability – helps to reduce waste mining by improved mining mix and control of waste movement.

1.3.7.1 *The hierarchy of needs for the Digital Twin*

With the capability of a Digital Twin for the Mine Technical Services demonstrated and in place, it will be prudent to move to the next level of Digital Twin which is the **Enterprise Metaverse**. As it grows in maturity the first Digital Twin should evolve based on learnings from behavioural data to, ultimately providing increasingly powerful predictive capabilities. Although not strictly within the realms and framework of the PERSEPHONE project, this is the perfect springboard to launch the hypothesis into the world of multiple interconnected Digital Twins – the Enterprise Metaverse. Generating richer behaviour insights for even more sophisticated use cases unlocking greater value – imagine a world where the execution consumption pattern directly triggers workflows to the supply chain for spares, parts, and consumables, and where the supply chain combined with the production engine provides the metallurgical works with predictions regarding volume and value of the product heading its way. The hierarchy of needs for the Digital Twin can be seen in Figure 1.20.

In order to achieve the project aspiration of reporting Resources and Reserves, testing the financial viability of the mining plans, and the feasibility of autonomous drilling and mining, interoperability with the Financial & Administration domain, Human Resources domain, and Environmental & Sustainability domain will be required. **Inter-domain interoperability** differs from intra-discipline integration in that the technical terminology is different, i.e., the languages are not the same and therefore a translator is required. Interoperability in the context means that the source code of the external domain software is understood and can therefore be translated to fit within the MRM domain.

MineRP's Spatial Analyzer® and MineRP's Spatial Dash® is the software packages that will be used to develop visualizations and **build, update, and maintain** the initial use cases applicable to the Mineral Resources Management Discipline. The transformed information is orchestrated to satisfy the consumption pattern of the users. The users cover the whole spectrum of users and decision-makers along the mining value chain, from discovery to closure and rehabilitation. The frequency of updates is determined by the availability of new data as well as the consumption patterns.

It is important to understand that not all the data required to build a digital twin emanates from the same source, or the same discipline, or even the same software package. Identifying the **integration requirements** early helps with identifying the core data product – in this case, data science professionals will use the MineRP4.0 platform to integrate data through mediation to populate a data lake where all the data is stored. In order to get the data to interact seamlessly data stewardship is required to ensure that all the data required for the twin to reflect the physical world is available in the correct format, context, and appropriate

attributes. At this point, the data is transformed into information. The information is then curated by identification, cleansing, and transformation.

The first step in creating a Digital Twin is to understand the digital maturity inside the organization followed by a determination of the level of digitalization inside the organization. Digitizing assets could not be the scary grey fog of unknown things that users are scared of; it can start with replacing a hand-written tram slip on a piece of paper which is collected at the end of the shift and captured into a spreadsheet with a pre-formatted form on a mobile device. For the sake of digitalisation projects, the ultimate objective is to build automated Geomodels that are made visible in the DT. The sensible start will be to begin with the **geological data available**, the new data-driven by the technologies developed for the project, and the reporting needs. With this knowledge it will be possible to develop a blueprint for the twin model defining the type of twin, the order for building it, the way the capability will evolve, and importantly the owners, affected parties and the governance structures.

Figure 1.20. Hierarchy of needs for the Digital Twin.

1.3.8 Waste Management and Recycling

The waste-management, closure, decommissioning, and remediation steps are not within the scope of PERSEPHONE as such, but the techniques being developed in the project will help to alleviate some of the issues often associated with these steps. For instance, more targeted extraction means less waste to manage on the surface and, hence, smaller and thus easier to manage facilities with less impact and eventually less effort during closure and a possible remediation phase.

2 Conditions in underground operating and abandoned mines with general directions for the further development of new technologies

Underground workings located both in deep active mines as well as abandoned and suspended mining areas are characterized by unique environmental conditions that determine specific requirements for the technologies used. Lack of light, lack of natural ventilation, high dust, water levels and many other factors mean that solutions that are commonly used in industry are not necessarily applicable in their current form in the exploration and mining of deep-located deposits. This chapter approximates the general conditions prevailing in underground workings. Technologies will also be discussed which, after appropriate adaptation, could be successfully implemented for regular use in exploration and mining.

In general, the challenges that have to be tackled in underground mines, whether deep or abandoned, are the following:

- Constant high humidity levels typically range between 95% and 100%. Since all underground openings have gauge pressure and the groundwater in the vicinity of them is always at higher pressure, water ingress is typical as all sub-terrain spaces act like “water magnets” (Figure 2.1). Although the presence of water can be economically tackled by many methods, the high humidity levels pose a challenge to the operability of modern machines, since high humidity levels always affect electronics and the like.

Figure 2.1. Drilling in mining face with high water content in rocks.

- All underground mines ideally operate under the assumption that the minimum required flow of fresh air is provided in all openings. In reality, this is seldom the case, since the rate of advance is generally higher than the rate of ventilation network installations. In view of the unfavourable ventilation conditions that always exist in some parts of underground mines, the operation of both machines and mine personnel is challenging, at least. It is also underlined that poor ventilation conditions hinder visibility and corresponding safety issues are raised. The example of mining works in poor visibility conditions are presented in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2. Mining operation in high dust and low visibility conditions.

- Rockmass stability is the number one concern in all underground mines since uncontrolled rockfalls are always a direct threat to the life of personnel and the operation of machines (Figure 2.3). Under this frame, underground operations, either those involving personnel and machines or autonomous systems, should be executed under the safest possible conditions, which in turn entail the recognition of geotechnically adverse areas.

Figure 2.3. Mining machine buried by dynamic rockfall in one of EU underground mines.

- Only in the case of deep underground mines, high temperatures may be encountered, owing to the geothermal gradient. For example, at an overburden depth of approx. 600m, the virgin rock temperature in Mount Isa (AUS, sulphides) is approx. 35°C while in Moranbah (AUS, coal) exceeds 60°C. These potentially high temperatures may create technical issues to the operability of autonomous machines.

2.1 Geodetic survey of underground mines

Mapping the environment is pivotal in every navigation and survey task. This, however, is not always an easy endeavour due to various environmental

constraints. It is important to include sensors able to map the environment and equip the robots with additional elements to compensate for poor working conditions.

There are multiple ways a robot can scan the environment, ranging from acoustic to optical sensory data processing. The most used and reliable ways of acquiring spatial information about the mine is by either using a LiDAR or a camera (Ebadi et al., 2023).

LIDAR sensors have the advantage of not being limited by poor lighting conditions and by not having prevalent geometries (landmarks) that can be discerned easily. Furthermore, LIDAR data requires little processing compared to using a camera (or multiple). However, it is important to note that LiDAR sensors do not fare well with water bodies and wall formations with multiple refraction indices. Furthermore, standard LiDAR systems require IMU sensors and a dead-reckoning approach to map a place. Lastly, LiDARs can be obstructed by dense dust in the air.

If cameras are used, then it is important to ensure that light sources are mounted on the robot's chassis, so that the cameras can actually perceive the environment. The matter of whether one or multiple cameras should be used depends on the constraints that the robot's design will impose. By using multiple cameras, it is possible to directly extract 3d point clouds (stereovision) without the need to examine multiple frames. In the case of one camera, it is necessary to store previous frames to construct the point cloud. By using any number of cameras, it is possible to extract information from the "optical-flow" using multiple frames and then extrapolate the robot's pose from them. This eliminates the need for an IMU or another localization scheme, but results show that a fusion of both approaches works best for SLAM applications.

After exploring the environment for a while, it would be advised to place coils in specific and denoted locations throughout the mapped portion of the mine that will act as beacons to the robots who will be able to tell their directions using magnetometers. This could further enhance the localization process of the robots.

In the end, it is proposed that the system carries multiple cameras and a lighting system to support them. Additionally, it is preferable to include an IMU to have an additional estimation of the robot's pose to apply corrections. If the magnetic field's values are used, then the robots should also have magnetometers included, in the case of mines that have ores that allow the use of magnetic induction sensing.

As far as the survey errors are concerned using AC magnetic field-based positioning (Abrudan et al., 2016) can provide a decent accuracy of less than 0.7 m in positioning error, however, this has been tested on a relatively short range of 15 m in a man-made cave. Also, most of the applied methods for localization seem to be in the range of meters.

Although underground mine development is not mandatory to follow specific alignments, taking into consideration that underground works target mineralised zones and not points in the underground space, geodetic survey works must be always executed with good to fairly good accuracy for the following reasons:

- Excavation of drives with specific curvature and grade to meet operating requirements.
- Localization of deposit characteristics to develop the domain of the ore body.

Underground geodetic survey works are in general executed by standard electronic distance and angle measurement instruments that use the impulse method (total stations) (Figure 2.4). The transmitter sends an impulse which propagates to the other endpoint and returns. The receiver receives a small fraction of the emitted impulse immediately and also the impulse which has travelled along the line and back. The propagation timer, which is controlled by an extremely accurate clock, determines the difference in propagation time for the two impulses. This difference corresponds to the time needed by the external impulse to twice travel the requested distance. Therefore, a total station and a reflector are in general utilised for open traversing underground drives. The abovementioned method is quite common in many underground mines and it has the following pros and cons:

- It is a survey work of high accuracy.
- Mining operations must be halted during the surveying works, which incorporate the creation of control targets per traverse edge.
- Mine layout is only an approximation of the as-built works since a limited number of points are measured.
- The calculation of volumes extracted is only a rough approximation due to the previous limitations.
- Underground mine parts with unfavourable geotechnical conditions are hard to survey for safety reasons.

Figure 2.4. The underground geodetic survey in progress.

Nowadays, SoA underground surveying techniques entail the generation of point clouds, which in turn are generated by laser scanners. Moreover, portable laser scanners that use SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping) technology are very useful instruments for underground mapping, since the surveyor is not required to level and centralise the instrument per control target point. However, SLAM methods suffer from unaccepted errors, especially in the case of open traverses, which are quite common in underground mine surveying works. For

example, at Koutzi underground magnesite mine operated by GM in Euboea Greece, an open traverse of approx. 200m in total length, executed with SLAM-type portable laser scanners, may return an error greater than 1.5 m, meaning that drive points at the end of the traverse are displaced 1.5 m away from their true position in space. The solution to this discrepancy is the establishment of high-accuracy control point targets by conducting standard geodetic techniques and the calibration of the point-cloud through those high-accuracy control point targets. The field measurement with SLAM technology is presented in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5. SLAM scanning survey in progress.

By reference to the above-mentioned, it is an operational demand for the autonomous rig concept to include a SLAM-type system for mapping uncharted underground mine areas in abandoned/suspended mines, where human access is strictly forbidden. This mapping process will be utilised for the navigation of the autonomous rig itself, as well as for the localization of areas of interest, e.g. for the chainage of drive-orebody intersection, for identifying the stretch of similar geological conditions etc. However, the GPS-denied underground environment, as well as the shortage of control point targets in uncharted underground mine areas, are currently a challenge for incorporating SLAM-type technologies, since the expected geodetic errors will be unacceptable. In order to implement new innovative procedures in the field of excavation mapping, it is necessary to answer the questions:

- *What kind of procedures, devices and sensors are needed to survey uncharted underground openings with the autonomous rig, in order to produce a survey of reasonable accuracy?*
- *What measurement accuracy is acceptable to the end user and what level of accuracy can be considered reasonable for further analysis?*

2.2 Navigation of autonomous machine in uncharted areas

Navigation in underground environments can be challenging for a multitude of reasons. Firstly, it is difficult for technology such as GPS to work, due to the propagation difficulty of RF signals of such high frequency. Furthermore, the fact

that it is not always feasible to include ground control points (GCPs) in the mine means that it will not be possible to apply correction methods through optical methods.

In order to achieve the localization of the robot, there needs to be a scheme that doesn't rely, at least constantly, on RF communication. To that effect, it is advisable to use the classic dead reckoning approach with an IMU and Magnetic Induction (MI) to help the robot localise. Magnetic induction is the reading of the magnetic field value, using a magnetometer, which is then used to construct, with the readings of an accelerometer, a map with known magnetic field intensity values. External limit-switching pads can be used to determine the boundaries of the mine's tunnel while protecting the robot from environmental collisions. The accuracy of the localization largely depends on the variation of the field's value, which should be high enough considering the abstract geometry of the mine tunnels. But the MI method only works on pre-mapped environments and requires that the sensors are not affected by the nature of the ores (paramagnetic materials).

Another viable approach is to use a camera or a LIDAR sensor and an accelerometer (or the "structure from motion with optical flow" method) to construct a 3D representation of the mine using photogrammetry / direct mapping. By utilising SLAM algorithms, it should be possible to use a camera to navigate the mine autonomously. By combining these two approaches it should be possible to construct a 3D map with known magnetometer values that will allow the robot to utilize the SLAM approach for unexplored areas and the readings from the magnetometer for already mapped areas.

Both approaches use non-RF reliant principles, but it will not be possible to effectively and safely navigate an underground environment without employing a communication system. In the case of pure MI navigation in mapped areas, it is not possible for multiple robots to notice each other's presence, leading to erratic behaviour in the event of multiple robot collisions. Robots that utilise vision-based sensors (cameras) can be equipped with a marker that contains their unique ID, making it possible to implement a collision prevention algorithm, but the problem, in this case, is that this doesn't help in the event that a robot can't see the ID of a robot it approaches. In order to solve these problems, it is important to implement RF communication functionality in the robots and allow them to transfer information between them about the history of their navigation information (3D maps, cloud points, etc.). In any case, it is not possible to avoid a "dead reckoning" approach when it comes to navigation in non-mapped areas, unless a high fps camera and easily computable algorithm produces the map ("structure from motion with optical flow").

Of course, it is not expected for the robots to have the processing capabilities to handle multiple point clouds and 3D meshes in a reasonable time. There needs to be a server that will handle the processing for them. To that end, it is necessary for the point clouds to be transmitted back to the server and the server's commands to be transmitted to the robots. This can't be done without the help of repeaters in large mines. By utilizing signal repeaters, it should be possible to

cover large networks of tunnels (Li & Zhan, 2018). The aforementioned research describes the use of WLAN networks, but WLAN operates at a high frequency, meaning that it will not be feasible for the signal to penetrate the soil, forcing the repeaters to be at line-of-sight positions. Furthermore, the range of a WLAN repeater is not typically great enough, leading to an increase in the number of repeaters and the introduction of considerable overhead in communication packets. Using LoRa WAN instead of WLAN is more efficient in underground environments, due to the fact that LoRa WAN operates at a lower frequency than WLAN, and therefore is able to penetrate a reasonable amount of soil (Seguel et al., 2022). Another advantage of LoRa WAN devices is that they can make an ad-hoc network, increasing the network's range easily.

- *From the aforementioned information, it can be derived that a combination of a magnetometer (when possible), a camera and an IMU will be able to accurately navigate a robotic rig in a mine. The optical system could be the main navigation tool, while the MI sensors should help reduce future errors in mapped areas. Furthermore, it is imperative that additional robots may place LoRa WAN repeaters after the signal's strength diminishes to ensure that the server will be accessible to the robots.*

2.3 Geochemical mapping of underground openings

Exploration programs in underground mines are a critical part of the operations since new mineralised domains are discovered and existing ones are mined with greater confidence regarding the grades and quantities of ore. Moreover, data acquired by exploration boreholes are utilised for understanding the general geological regime of the area under study, for the development of the geological model and finally for delineating the areas of interest. In all cases, the exploration program greenlights mining operations or ceases them, i.e. its outcomes are critical for mine life.

In underground mines the exploration program is conducted by the following methods, which are executed either simultaneously or independently:

- Boreholes from the surface.
- Boreholes from underground.
- Exploration drives.
- Utilization of geochemical data acquired from abandoned/suspended underground sections.

The first two exploration work methods are very common worldwide and are the most costly as well. Depending on the orebody geometrical characteristics, the mineralised domain may be intersected by a limited number of boreholes, to gain confidence in grades and quantities however it is always the case that a denser pattern of boreholes must be executed by all means. Borehole data in the form of cores or chips are used to calculate ore grades, map geological features and estimate rockmass geomechanical strength figures. In turn, resource models, geological models and geotechnical models can be inferred from point data, which are finally utilised for creating mine plans, production schedules and future mine developments.

Sometimes, the confidence gained from the outcome of exploration drilling works is not considered representative and exploration drives may be executed, which adds even higher costs. Through exploration drives, the following information is generally collected:

- The representative grades of materials.
- RoM dilution and losses.
- Immediate reinforcement and/or support requirements.
- Mine dewatering requirements.

In case abandoned/suspended underground mine drives exist, there is a great potential of carrying out a representative exploration program of relatively low cost since the direct access to merely infinite ore samples, geological features and structural data can provide invaluable information for the mineralised domains, the orebody genesis mechanisms in the area under study and the detailed mapping of tectonic features. The main drawback of gaining access to the abovementioned data is the high risk associated with entering self-supported openings, since in most cases the abandoned/suspended underground mine drives are of low profile and are unsupported, thus re-entry of personnel is of high risk. In Figure 2.6 in-person underground survey in unfavourable geomechanical conditions was presented.

Figure 2.6. Inspection of an underground chamber.

With reference to the above-mentioned, there is an operational demand for the autonomous rig concept to include systems of measuring geochemical data along the abandoned/suspended underground routes that should be surveyed. These data could be directly combined to point-cloud data, therefore the exact locations of geochemical features of interest may be collected. Under ideal conditions, geochemical profiles at regular intervals of abandoned/suspended underground drives can be calculated, which in turn will be incorporated into the development of the digital twin of uncharted underground areas. The introduction of improved geomechanical mapping need be based on the following question:

- *What are kinds of devices and sensors needed to measure geochemical data per profile?*
- *Is there a technology that would enable ongoing mapping of the geochemical composition of rocks?*
- *What should be done to adapt this technology to the conditions existing underground?*

2.4 Autonomous drilling

The main activity of the autonomous rig concept will be the execution of exploration boreholes from underground. Ideally, the locations from where fan drilling will be carried out will coincide with areas within mineralised domains or in the vicinity of them. These areas will be recognized from the autonomous rig after the execution of the surveying and geochemical measurement campaigns.

Taking into consideration that exploration drilling from abandoned/suspended underground mine stretches will be conducted in potentially confined spaces, the overall size of the autonomous rig has to be smaller compared to currently operating equipment.

Still to identify possibilities related to autonomous drilling technology development following questions have to be answered:

- *How will a large rig's energy autonomy be, taking into account its small size, the potentially long distances that have to be covered and the drilling work that must be executed in an area of no available infrastructures?*
- *What are the steps that the autonomous drilling rig will follow to get the job done?*
- *Will the rig start a fan drilling pattern or will there be a mechanism of providing predesigned drilling orientations?*
- *How will the drilling samples be collected by a drilling rig of small scale?*
- *What is the expected drilling accuracy?*
- *What technology may be used during drilling planning?*
- *Will the accuracy of drilling be monitored in any way?*

2.5 ON-THE-FLY data transmission

It is quite common nowadays to monitor the performance of underground machinery through on-the-fly data transmissions from the machines to control rooms on the surface. Therefore, machine hours, hydraulic temperatures, maintenance schedules, and performance characteristics are collected and stored in databases (Figure 2.7).

Figure 2.7. An example screen summarizing the machine's operation.

In turn, the decision-making team controls the operability of the equipment and schedules preventive maintenance campaigns. The overall target is to minimise downtimes and safeguard the operational reliability of the equipment. In general, on-the-fly data transmissions require underground infrastructures. For example, at Koutzi underground magnesite mine operated by GM in Euboea Greece, there are Wi-Fi infrastructures underground and through them the underground mining equipment transmits critical operational data to the surface office. It is then up to the maintenance department to schedule machine stops in order to keep the mining fleet up and running the longest possible.

With reference to the above-mentioned, it is an operational demand for the autonomous rig concept to include systems of operational data transmissions, as well as the transmissions of data regarding the geochemical characteristics of the rockmass samples that will be collected during the executing of exploration boreholes. However, since the operation of the autonomous rig will take place also in abandoned/suspended underground mine stretches, where the installation of Wi-Fi beacons or similar instruments will not be possible to be carried out by the underground mine personnel, an innovative system of on-the-fly data transmission has to be incorporated. Still, some questions must be answered before developing a new solution.

Using LoRa WAN to transmit data to and from the operator with the help of repeaters is the proposed approach to this problem, as aforementioned. In order to prevent exhausting the bandwidth of the communication system, it is important to compress the data before transmitting it. In the case of 3D meshes and point clouds, Google has already developed an open-source compression algorithm, called Draco, which has been used in DARPA's SubT challenge by the Cerberus Team. This will be helpful, considering the lower bandwidth of LoRa WAN networks. In the case of geochemical data, if it can be simply represented with a text-based format, and therefore there is no theoretical reason it can't be compressed using traditional compression algorithms.

2.6 Recovery of autonomous machine

Unlike underground civil tunnel works, underground mine works are comprised of a dense network of drives that expands at lower and upper elevations, under and above the base gallery (Figure 2.8). Depending on the geometrical characteristics of the deposit, there are underground mines where the routes to production headings are straightforward, e.g. sublevel stopping of a single mineralised vein, as well as mines that resemble a labyrinth, e.g. inclined room and pillar mines.

Figure 2.8. Map of underground workings remained after exploitation in one of EU underground mines.

In the case of abandoned/suspended underground mines, adding to the scenario of a pre-existing complicated mine layout, the following obstacles are likely to be encountered during the autonomous navigation of the rig:

- Drive stretches where debris from fallen rocks are partially blocking the roadway.
- Drive stretches where underground water ingress has been accumulated.

By reference to the above mentioned, it is an operational demand for the autonomous rig concept to include mechanisms and procedures that will safeguard the recovery of the rig in case rough conditions are encountered along the roadways and in the case that long distances must be covered. Implementation of recovery procedures should be preceded by answers to the following questions:

- *What kind of navigation systems will be installed on the rig?*

- *How could the rig bypass tunnel stretch with debris of various sizes blocking the floor?*
- *How could the rig navigate in partially flooded drive stretches?*
- *How will a large rig's energy autonomy be taking into account its small size, the potentially long distances that have to be covered and the drilling work that must be executed in an area with no available infrastructures?*
- *In case something goes wrong and the machine is not able to be navigated back to its base, what would be the backup plan for machine recovery?*

3 Technologies developed as part of the PERSEPHONE project

Due to the increasing demand for CRM, it is necessary to explore and extract deposits in increasingly difficult conditions. It is assumed that soon, it will be necessary to operate at great depths and in very difficult environmental conditions. It is also possible to reactivate areas that could once have been classified as unsustainable, but with the use of modern technical means, their extraction may become profitable again. Of course, not all technologies can currently be used for the exploration and extraction of deposits located in deep mines and abandoned/suspended mines. Sometimes this is due to technological limitations and sometimes it is economically unjustified. However, there are some areas that could already be successfully adapted, developed and implemented. Selected issues are the subject of the PERSEPHONE project.

The PERSEPHONE project is aimed at developing innovative solutions for exploration and mining in difficult conditions, without access to media, in places inaccessible to people. Due to the need to face the increasingly difficult conditions prevailing in underground mine workings and due to the need to implement better operation planning that maximises extraction and minimises waste production, the tasks of the PERSEPHONE project focus on the development of autonomous technologies and on the design and development of a digital twin adapted to the complex conditions prevailing underground. The implementation of autonomous technologies will enable unmanned exploration and extraction of deposits located in extremely difficult and dangerous conditions, while a properly developed digital twin will maximise the efficiency of work while maintaining the safety of the machinery park and the crew.

The main directions of development analysed within the PERSEPHONE project together with the partner responsible for their development and implementation are presented in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1. Technology areas developed as part of the PERSEPHONE project.

Task/technology name	Leading partner
Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes	EPI
Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems	DTU
Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator	EPI
Real-time rock characterization as input to systems for sustainable underground mining	EPI
Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions	CUP
Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination	LTU
High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations	LTU
On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment	LTU
Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization	LTU
Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics	DTU

Advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterisation of near-mine exploratory drilling using machines based on LIBS and multi-spectral sensors	SPE
Real-time Detection of Rock Mechanical and Geophysical Properties from Exploration and Extraction Machinery	SPE

A detailed description of specific technologies is provided in subsections 3.1-3.10.

3.1 Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes

One of the goals of the PERSEPHONE project is to develop a suitable method for rock mass preconditioning to reduce the energy consumption of extractive processes. This task will include, among others, an investigation of the potential pre-conditioning methods to be used with conventional drilling/excavation tools.

Within the PERSEPHONE project, the analysis will be based mainly on theoretical considerations. In the first stage, a literature review will be performed, and the most suitable pre-conditioning methods will be selected according to current SoTA and existing theoretical/experimental results. Then further laboratory testing/proof of concept will be performed accordingly.

Testing of individual technologies in in-situ conditions is not planned due to the low TRL of technologies. Analyses will be based mainly on simulations, which will allow us to initially determine the effectiveness of individual solutions, and in the future, taking into account costs, it will be the basis for testing and implementing new preconditioning technologies for the conditions in the mine.

3.2 Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems and Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics

3.2.1 Modular system for deployment of exploration drilling rigs and measurement systems, leveraging existing robotic solutions

The Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems task includes technologies that enable the operation of autonomous machines in areas of the mine that are inaccessible to people for various reasons. Modular systems consist of robotic mobile bases, manipulators, end-effectors and sensors (Figure 3.1) will allow the end user to safely and efficiently recognize conditions in explored areas.

Figure 3.1. Various concepts of operating scenarios of an autonomous modular machine for exploration and extraction of deposits.

Moreover, multiple robots will be linked/combined together to provide one or more functionalities for exploration drilling missions (e.g. providing additional power supply to the drilling tool or replacing drill extension). Early-stage development of this technology will consist of:

- Research into existing robotic drilling technologies and modular systems.
- CAD design,
- Prototyping and testing should be carried out in the lab environment,
- Hardware and software integration of prototyped parts on existing robotic solutions.

The development of a new modular solution will significantly contribute to the current SoTA. Firstly, delivering drilling rigs in hard-to-reach dangerous areas will allow them to perform continuous exploration even in harsh environments (Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2. Conceptual mining machine reaching deposit unreachable by standard mining operations.

Secondly, the implementation of new advances in modular robotic systems (Figure 3.3) will enable versatile and efficient exploration and mining operations in challenging environments.

Figure 3.3. Concept of modular prospection & excavation machine supported by another autonomous robotic machine.

Finally, a Fleet of modular ground robots carrying sensors and mechanical elements necessary to guarantee:

- 1) Traversability of the mine.
- 2) Distribution of loads and transportation of electrical and drilling mediums.
- 3) Physical collaboration for precise exploration drilling.

3.2.2 Autonomous drill planning and execution systems that utilise onboard sensing of rock face characteristics

In order to fully automate work related to the exploration and extraction of deposits, it is necessary to equip the machines with devices enabling the collection of data on the composition of a given face in real-time. Information about the geometry of the face and the arrangement of geological layers will be the basis for ongoing planning of drilling works and correcting drilling and blasting patterns.

One of the ambitions of the PERSEPHONE project is the development of autonomous drill planning and execution systems that utilise onboard sensing of rock face characteristics. This technology will involve integrating sensors into drilling equipment to gather real-time data on rock properties and surrounding drilling areas.

To achieve set goals the project team will:

- 1) Develop theoretical research to understand the principles of onboard sensing and its application in autonomous drilling.
- 2) Explore and adapt existing sensor technologies and data processing algorithms for use cases analysed within the PERSEPHONE project.
- 3) Create seamless communication and coordination between robotic systems and tools, enhancing the ability to perform complex manoeuvres with precision and efficiency.

All these means will allow us to autonomously plan and execute drilling operations by analysing real-time sensor data from drilling equipment. The novelty of the proposed solution is that it adjusts parameters based on rock characteristics to optimise drilling efficiency and effectiveness.

It is assumed that the PERSEPHONE project will achieve high accuracy of the system for autonomous drill planning and execution from onboard sensing of the rock face characteristics. It is also assumed that under simulation conditions the system will be capable of accurately reacting to various geological scenarios and drilling conditions.

Development of such technology will significantly improve current SoTA due to the ability of autonomous drilling systems to gather and utilise real-time data on rock characteristics and workings geometry for data-driven decision-making. It surely will enhance drilling efficiency, reduce reliance on manual intervention, and improve safety by providing valuable insights into geological conditions during drilling.

3.3 Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator

Ensuring high mining efficiency and high quality of deposit exploration requires ensuring appropriate drilling accuracy. Minimising the deviation of production and exploration wells is undoubtedly a significant challenge, and any progress in this area will have a positive impact on the exploration and production process. As part of the PERSEPHONE project, it is planned to develop a technology to measure hole deviation for long hole drilling. Technology will be continuously improved thanks to periodical testing and further validation. Results will be also uploaded and visualised to geomodel developed by MineRP.

As previous experience shows, correctly made blast holes determine the mining efficiency. Any deviations from the values assumed in the blasting metric determine the need to provide more energy, e.g. to crush the rock. This requires an increase in the number of explosives and increases the visible costs of the works. Additionally, in the case of contouring holes, their correct execution without deviations affects the stability of the workings in the long run by influencing the ability to maintain the integration of the roof layers. In the years 2016-2020, CUP and KGHM were part of the PROMETEST ministerial project financed by the National Center for Research and Development of Poland. As a result of theoretical analyses and subsequent empirical observations. Incorrect drilling of blast holes may require the use of up to 100% more explosives to achieve the same effect. Figure 3.4 shows the simulation results of the detonation process for V-cut, while Figure 3.5 presents the effect of burn-cut detonation.

Figure 3.4. Effective (left) and ineffective (right) detonation of V-cut in mining face consisting of hard rock.

Figure 3.5 Effective (left) and ineffective (right) detonation of burn cut in mining face consisting hard rock.

Taking the abovementioned into account, the PERSEPHONE team will develop a system that will enable continuous measurement of the deviation of the blast

holes in relation to the assumed design. Information in this regard will be the basis for taking appropriate corrective and preventive actions.

The PERSEPHONE project plans to:

- Develop a method of data collection and synchronization between drilling equipment and measurement technology data.
- Develop a mechanized solution – test platform.
- Develop continuous measurements.
- Visualization of theoretical vs real data.

3.4 Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling

Real-time rock characterization supported with on-line analytics systems is the most extensive module of the PERSEPHONE project due to the complexity of the technologies used. The approach that will be developed as part of the project is based on the assumption that the measurement system equipped with a series of sensors will be able to continuously collect and transmit information accompanying the drilling process at the stage of preparation for drilling, during drilling and after drilling (Figure 3.6). Below two LIBS scenarios are described. In the PERSEPHONE project one scenario will be selected for in-field testing.

Figure 3.6. Parameters collected during borehole drilling.

3.4.1 LIBS slurry analyser

LIBS is an analysis technique that uses a high-power laser beam to analyse the chemical composition of a target. The technique has been around for a long time and has been successfully applied in many different academic and industrial applications such as mining, recycling, and manufacturing industries.

The concept of the LIBS drilling slurry analyser is schematically elaborated in the figure below (Figure 3.7). Drilling fluids will be collected from the drill hole while it is being drilled. The collected fluids are analysed online by a LIBS system for chemical composition. The resulting data can be used to get a depth profile of the composition behind the mine face.

Figure 3.7. Scheme of LIBS slurry analyser.

In an earlier EU H2020 project (ROBOMINERS grant agreement n°820971), GSB developed an early prototype system for online LIBS analysis on slurries. This prototype can be the starting point for further development in PERSEPHONE. Lab studies can be conducted to get a better understanding of detection limits in slurries, measurement parameters, temporal resolution and other technical improvements to make the system more viable in mining environments.

The current state of the technology is only theoretical and based on fundamental lab tests. At the end of the project, we aim to have a convincing proof of concept, that the technology can work in a mining environment.

Performing LIBS on fluids has been actively done in academia for a long time already. However, due to the challenging nature of the practice, this is almost always done in very controlled lab conditions with careful sample preparation. Taking this technology and adapting it to harsh mine environments is therefore a significant challenge, but if successful could mean a revolution in drilling technology. It would be the first technology available that allows us to get early data on the composition of the rock behind the mine face before blasting.

3.4.2 LIBS mine-face scanning

A LIBS sensor could be designed to scan a mine face at a distance to create a map of the face. This map can be used to visualise the orebody and determine where the ore is located. This is especially useful in areas with difficult accessibility. There are two concepts at the moment for development within this scope. First of all, a LIBS system mounted on some type of rover/robot scans rocks from a distance. Secondly, a LIBS system is mounted on a robot arm, where the arm creates a scanning pattern (Figure 3.8).

Figure 3.8. LIBS mine-face scanning.

SPE has developed custom LIBS systems for a variety of applications, particularly in the mining industry, for over 8 years. During this time novel solutions in designing LIBS systems for conveyor belt scanners, core scanners, and drill chip analysers were proposed by SPE. This experience is vital for the development of other novel applications of LIBS such as this. In the first stage series of simulations of different sensor designs will be performed to figure out which design works optimal at a distance and meets other requirements (lightweight etc.) After confirmation of system feasibility SPE will create a prototype and test it in the lab environment.

The development of a LIBS system that can be used for mine-face scanning needs a couple of novelties investigated. First of all, the working distance will need to be increased significantly beyond the <0.5m which is the working distance of conventional LIBS systems. This will involve a study into novel optical configurations that allow accurate measurements at long distances. Secondly, the LIBS system needs to be incorporated with a scanning system that allows coverage of the entire mine face. There are several potential ways to tackle this, but it needs to be investigated what options are cost-effective and feasible in a challenging underground mine environment. Current concepts involve a pan-tilt system for a long-distance LIBS system or a robot-arm system for shorter-distance LIBS systems.

Long-distance LIBS sensors have been successfully developed by several research groups in the academic world and in space applications. The current drawback on those systems is that they are not designed for real-world applications and that the costs, bulk and robustness are completely out of scope. This project will aim to design a sensor that meets the demanding requirements of underground mining, or at least come up with a concept that is scalable to reach it.

3.4.3 MWD and in-situ hardness test

Measure While Drilling (MWD) refers to visual and numerical analysis based on accurate data acquisition of drilling process parameters for each hole as it is being drilled. The development of MWD is developed as a reaction to a desire from the market to increase knowledge of the characteristics of the rock mass in which infrastructure is created and from which minerals is liberated. The initial requirements were in the field of geotechnical engineering sciences to improve safety through support designs. Traditional methods of gaining data such as geological mapping, bore hole geophysics, sampling and, visual hole inspections proved to be limited, leading to the development of MWD. It is quickly proving to extend far beyond safety only.

The MWD technology consists of two separate processes: registration of data and evaluation/interpretation of data. The parameters recorded are based on the mechanical behaviour of the drill rig and can be all of the below or a combination of any set of the parameters:

- Penetration rate
- Percussive pressure
- Feed pressure
- Rotation pressure
- Rotation speed
- Damper pressure
- Flushing water pressure
- Flushing water flow

What follows is a use case of a mining operation using MWD data to build rock hardness models for use in drilling designs and schedules and for informing future mining parameters. In figures 3.9-3.12 a visualisation of MWD-collected parameters was presented.

Figure 3.9. Showing MWD results in 3D.

Figure 3.10. Showing Detailed MWD results in 3D.

Figure 3.11. Showing Analyses of MWD.

Figure 3.12. A block model based on MWD data.

An indentation device will be tested as a calibration tool for the MWD hardness data that today gives a relative value. The indentation device will give a calibration value to a method or software application that will result in a mechanical characterization value of the rock. The device is based on indentation test in general and the current version is spherical indentation (closer to Brinell), but we are not limited to this shape of indenter. If possible, the indentation device will be mounted on a feed during the test. The grey parts in the Figure 3.13 are the parts that will be developed, the blue exists today.

Figure 3.13. Showing areas of development during the project.

3.4.4 Multi-spectral down hole imager

The multi-spectral downhole imager is a compact self-motorized device that slides or crawls into a predrilled borehole (sub-horizontal or vertical) to capture image data at specific wavelengths across the electromagnetic spectrum (Figure 3.14). These images are processed to infer the mineralogy/composition based on a machine learning (ML) model trained on reference datasets (use case-specific wavelengths and model). The output product is a “virtual” drill core where

minerals are classified for quick texture/distribution evaluation and basic statistics can be derived (e.g. mineral proportions).

Figure 3.14. Principles of multi-spectral down hole imager operation.

The method used will be based on UV-NIR-SWIR reflectance/fluorescence imagery, build-in a compact and resilient format. The technologies used will be built upon compact spectrometers developed previously by GSB, using miniature solid-state spectrometers (Figure 3.15). The technology will rely on two physical phenomena that allow to detect of specific mineral species with their optical properties: the absorption of specific wavelengths (especially in the SWIR range between 1100 and 2500nm) and the fluorescence emission when exposed to UV light.

Figure 3.15. Example of a prototype miniature spectrometer (viewport visible) integrated in a robotic propulsion system by GSB. right: UV-induced fluorescence spectra on a carbonated shale formation, with mineral-specific fluorescence bands highlighted.

Direct usage is to provide spectral information used to identify the mineral distribution in the borehole. Potential for automated mineralogy (ex: characteristic fluorescence peak of specific minerals). Indirect: potential for grade estimation by calculating the mineral proportions and their theoretical elemental composition in regard to the imaged surface.

Within the PERSEPHONE project, it is assumed that the system after improvement will combine newly developed compact and power-efficient light sources (broadband and deep UV) with cost-efficient solid-state detectors (ex: vibration-tolerant SWIR detectors in boreholes). Moreover, it is expected that optimization

of the multispectral setup will be possible (use case specific wavelength acquisition instead of broadband hyperspectral capture) and fully automated in-situ data treatment/classification will be tested (ML model running on edge computer). One of key features of the developed approach will be a possibility for reconstruction of virtual cores even in case of destructive drilling.

In light of the current SoTA the Multi-spectral down hole imager will provide fluorescence and reflectance multispectral imaging in one compact package (what will improve down-hole acquisition capacity). It will be also characterized by ultra-compact size, which is aimed for PQ size long holes imaging (122mm EXTERNAL diameter). Finally, data processing will be fully integrated.

3.4.5 Multispectral rock face imager

The multi-spectral mine face imager is a robust, cost-efficient method to quickly and roughly evaluate the mineralogical/chemical composition of a rock face (Figure 3.16). The output of this sensor is qualitative or semi-quantitative depending on the condition and the rock types.

Figure 3.16. Principle of multispectral rock face imager operation.

The aim is to capture and process a multispectral image of the rock face in a few seconds, to produce a reference image to help decision-making for further exploration (e.g.: rock face LIBS scan area, long hole drilling). The device is based on one or more imaging cameras equipped with motorized filters to capture image data at specific wavelengths across the electromagnetic spectrum. These images are then processed to infer the mineralogy/composition based on a machine learning (ML) model trained on reference datasets (use case specific wavelengths and model). The output product is a reference classified image of the rock face.

The method use will be based on UV-NIR reflectance/fluorescence imagery, built-in a compact and resilient format with decent illumination power to be operated at a few meters of the rock face. The technologies used will be built upon a compact scientific imaging device developed previously by GSB, relying on the recent industry developments in high-power high-efficiency UV-VIS LED technologies.

The technology will rely on two physical phenomena that allow to detect of specific mineral species with their optical properties: the absorption of specific wavelengths in the visible to near-infrared range (350-900nm) and the fluorescence emission when exposed to UV light (275 and 365nm) (Figure 3.17).

Figure 3.17. Rock face (2x1m) was imaged with a standard camera and white broadband light (left) and the same rock face was imaged with a combination of UV light 275 and 365nm, the zinc ore (ZnS) appears red orange, the dolomized zone in various shades of blue (right).

Direct usage is to provide spectral information used to identify the mineral distribution on the rock face or variation in composition (e.g. Mg content in carbonates). The improvement of the technology within the PERSEPHONE project will consist of:

- 1) combining newly developed compact and power-efficient light sources (especially in the deep UV) with cost-efficient sensitive scientific cameras.
- 2) optimization of the multispectral setup (use case specific wavelength acquisition instead of broadband hyperspectral capture).
- 3) fully automated in-situ data treatment/classification (ML model running on edge computer).

The proposed approach will be significantly improved compared to the current SoTA. This is because fluorescence and reflectance multispectral imaging will be installed in one compact package. DUV fluorescence imaging with specific multiband VIS-NIR IMAGING is especially underused in mining exploration and has the potential to outperform current multispectral/hyperspectral cameras using only broadband white illumination.

3.4.6 Downhole electro (magnetic) measurement – ERT and IP

Electrical methods can be either passive, using fields within the Earth, or active, with the injection of artificial and controlled current into the ground. They rely on the contrast of the electrical properties of the rocks (conductivity and resistivity) and the subsurface. The principal of downhole electro (magnetic) measurement is shown in Figure 3.18. The electrical conductivity is affected by several parameters, such as: the presence of water, porosity, groundwater salinity, temperature, pressure and the amount of conducting minerals in the rock. This wide range of properties make electrical conductivity a perfect clue for the individuation of different mineral deposits (Kemna et al., 2012). These include the resistivity method, the induced polarization (IP) method and the self-potential method (SP) (Dentith & Mudge, 2014). While the SP method measures the natural potential of the subsurface, the resistivity (ERT) and IP methods depend on the injection of the current (direct current or low-frequency alternating currents) into the ground. The resistivity method discerns in the electrical properties of the ground the horizontal and vertical discontinuities. It is also used for the detection

of anomalous electrical conductivity measurements due to three-dimensional bodies. The IP method use the determination of the capacitive characteristic of the soil, or rather the capacity of rocks and minerals to accumulate charges by the injected current to locate the areas where the conductive minerals are disseminated (Kemna et al., 2012). In this project ERT and IP measurements will be tested. Experimental tool coupling the use of MWD. The fixed rig of electrodes will use the hole created by the MWD to perform horizontal downhole measurements.

Figure 3.18. Principle of downhole electro (magnetic) measurement – ERT an IP.

Technology will be especially useful for direct measuring of rock mechanical properties (resistivity, conductivity, induced polarization) and indirect measurement of mineralogy (for sulphide deposits).

The innovativeness of the proposed solution will be expressed through the development of a sensor that can be mounted on PERSEPHONE's machinery to perform automated mapping.

3.4.7 Face-scanning electro (magnetic) measurement ERT-IP

It is planned that the experimental tool will be mounted on a robotic arm that will be able to scan the mine face wall (Figure 3.19). Measurement is going to be coupled to LIBS and multispectral camera analysis which will provide an in-depth view.

Figure 3.19. Principle of face-scanning electro (magnetic) measurement ERT-IP.

Implementation of such an approach will be the base for measuring rock mechanical properties and mineralogy.

Also in this case, the key element ensuring progress beyond the current SoTA is the Development of a sensor that can be mounted on PERSEPHONE's machinery to perform automated (real-time) face mapping of geological features and development of a sensor applied to PERSEPHONE's machinery.

3.4.8 Acoustics

Acoustic methods measure the travel times of the reflected or refracted waves detected by a series of geophones placed on the ground surface and are able to estimate the location and depth of the targets. For this purpose, receiver and transmitter are set up at specific frequencies to detect geological features (faults, fractures, changes in lithology).

Within the PERSEPHONE project an experimental tool coupling the use of MWD and ERT will be developed. The receiver and transmitter will be placed at the bottom of the hole created by the MWD to perform acoustic measurements and reach a deeper depth (Figure 3.20).

Figure 3.20. Principle of acoustic measurements during drilling of mining face.

This technology may be very useful from the perspective of exploration and mining due to the ability of petro-physical properties and structural information determination.

3.5 Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions

Numerical modelling is one of the fastest-growing fields in geomechanics. New complex numerical codes, well-developed constitutive models of rocks and advanced boundary conditions adapted to simulate highly dynamic phenomena make the simulation results increasingly closer to the situation observed in real conditions. Nevertheless, due to the complexity of the strength parameters, and the complicated mechanism of rock failure, numerical models in geomechanical practice are most often made on a small scale. This facilitates model validation. An example of rock failure simulation during a Brazilian test compared to the real observed situation is presented in Figure 3.21.

Figure 3.21. Small-scale simulation of Brazilian test with the use of FDEM numerical code.

Unfortunately, solutions of this type cannot be used on a large scale (several cubic kilometres) due to large discrepancies between the results of numerical analyses and the results of underground measurements. The differences in the results are mainly due to the complexity of the exploitation process and disturbances in the stress zone in the vicinity of underground workings. Generally, large pillars will have a different level of rock disintegration than small pillars, and liquidation zones will have a lower load-bearing capacity than intact rock mass. Considering that in real conditions a significant geometric difference between underground structures is observed (Figure 3.22), it can be assumed that the implementation of in-situ measurements at the stage of model construction and validation will contribute to increasing the accuracy of large-scale numerical simulations.

Figure 3.22. Example of KGHM mining panel geometry.

A significant step towards the implementation of large-scale mining models for regular use in underground mining is to increase the accuracy of the model based on data collected on an ongoing basis from underground monitoring systems and rock parameters collected on an ongoing basis during the mining process. The use of real data will be the basis for validating the model, which will make it possible to use it not only for post-factum analyses but also as a prediction tool, for

example, the behaviour of the rock mass during exploitation in exceptional geological and mining conditions.

As part of the PERSEPHONE project, a 3D numerical modelling method will be developed based on the finite element approach, using data from actual geomechanical measurements and rock strength data collected in situ conditions to increase the accuracy of the model. Then, a well-validated model will be used to simulate excavation in exceptional deposit conditions, e.g. near a fault or in areas with a significantly increased content of useful minerals. An approach based on real data will mean that the modelling results can be considered quantitatively and not only qualitatively as before.

The use of a new data-driven approach will be the basis for increasing the efficiency and safety of mining at great depths.

A comprehensive approach to numerical modelling will be developed, describing the process of collecting and archiving geomechanical data in situ (with a description of the type of data, method and frequency of its collection). Then, a method for validating the model will be developed by modifying the strength parameters of the rocks building underground structures. The general research methodology in light of the standard approach is presented in Figure 3.23.

Numerical modelling will be enriched with data collected in situ in real-time. This approach will enable an increase in the level of accuracy compared to research-based strictly on laboratory analyses.

According to the current SoTA, numerical models are developed based on data from laboratory tests. This gives satisfactory results in small-scale simulations but is not applicable in large-scale simulations. The use of a data-driven approach will be the basis for increasing the accuracy of the simulations and will enable their implementation into regular mining operations. An example of the large-scale model developed with the use of lab data and data from an underground measuring system is presented in Figure 3.24.

Figure 3.23. General workflow of standard approach and data-driven approach to large scale-numerical modelling.

Figure 3.24. Safety factor distribution of rocks achieved based on rock strength parameters from lab tests (top) and utilizing data from underground measuring systems (bottom).

3.6 Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination

Autonomous path planning is an integral component for robots and vehicles to enable their safe and efficient navigation in various environments. More specifically, it determines a collision-free path for an autonomous system to navigate from its initial location to a specified goal location. Generally, one can mention two main path-planning approaches: local and global path-planning.

Local path planning focuses on navigating the immediate surroundings of the robot that are defined by onboard sensors' detection range. As an example, it can consider sensor data from LiDAR, cameras, or radars to detect nearby obstacles and plan a path that avoids them in real-time. Local path planners are essential for handling unexpected obstacles or changes in the environment that may not be considered in the path generated by a global path planner. One of the common local path-planning approaches is an Artificial Potential Field (APF). This method operates by generating attractive and repulsive "force fields" that act on robots. Such as, attractive forces push the robot towards a goal, while repulsive forces push the robot away from obstacles in this environment. As an example, in Figure 3.25 an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) is given a goal-point on the other side of the obstacle, and the path planning/avoidance algorithm continuously shifts intermediate waypoints to provide an obstacle-free motion with a safe distance from the obstacle.

Figure 3.25. APF navigation around a column obstacle. UAV's motion starts on the left. The path is highlighted with green colour (Nikolakopoulos et al., 2022).

Alike local path planners, global path planners consider the entire environment. Usually, this is achieved by using a map that represents information about the environment. Global path planner calculates a global path from start to goal location on a given map. Among the common global path planning approaches one can mention grid-based path planners. In this case, map of the environment is represented with a 2D grid or 3D voxels. The most well-known grid-based path planners are A* and D*. Figure 3.26 below illustrates D* Lite path on 2D map and D*₊ path on 3D map.

Figure 3.26. On the left is depicted global path generated by D* Lite, where green circle represents starting point and red circle goal point. On the right, is shown a global path created by D*₊, where the path is planned from blue sphere to red sphere. Red voxels represent high risk area and green voxels represent lower risk area. On both images obstacles and path are represented with black colour. (Nikolakopoulos et al., 2022).

One of the key parts of the core PERSEPHONE activities will be dedicated towards enabling mining machines' autonomous navigation inside mining areas which is both applied to deep and abandoned mine use-cases. In this task a method for safe multi-machine navigation that will generate optimal global routes for machines operating in the mine, as well as detect and resolve potential collisions that will determine replanning needs will be developed. Additionally, local path re-

planning based on the local sensor information will be used to refine the initial path considering machine's location, manoeuvrability limitations in tight areas.

It is foreseen that this planning capability will become an integral functionality for the next generation of mining.

In terms of the development of novel approach, it is assumed that it will be built on top of existing methods and our current knowledge. As an input data for us will be the following data structures:

- a) Point cloud map of the area.
- b) LiDAR scan.
- c) Radar scan.
- d) Camera image and video feed.
- e) Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) data.
- f) Other parameters.

Within the PERSEPHONE project, a methodology to collect, process and validate data for producing reliable information for safe multi-machine navigation will be developed.

The core research tasks in path planning will consist of:

- finding global optimal paths considering traversability information, available resources, power and media connectivity, feasibility, collision, dynamic and physical constraints,
- finding precise and collision-free paths that will be calculated based on the utilization of Model Predictive Control (MPC) approach.

In overall, this methodology will be part of the overall Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) framework (KET 3) developed in the project and will be base for further development of concepts of mining machines to enable their autonomous and safe navigation.

One of the project activities is focused on developing of the digital twin of a mine. Utilization of real mining data will allow to validate the developed methodology in high-fidelity simulations.

Considering the contribution to the current SoTA, it may be stated that *the* new methodological framework will improve significantly the current level of knowledge. The proposed approach will be validated on the utilization of novel designs of mining machines and real-mine data for enabling precision navigation. The aim is to extend and make existing path-planning solutions capable of addressing existing mining challenges.

3.7 High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations

While significant progress has been made, accurately determining a robot's initial pose within a pre-built map (global pose estimation) remains an active research area. Especially in the subterranean areas, where GPS signals are not available.

This task is crucial for robots to understand their location at the start of a mission or positioning themselves in the environment. Unlike local methods, global techniques can localise a robot even without any initial position information, addressing the "kidnapped robot problem." Figure 3.27 depicts a scenario in which the robot has already been relocalised and aligned its position with the environment.

Fig. 3.27. Visual representation of the estimated pose in the global point cloud map. Where white points represent the aligned point cloud, green and blue points represent the global map, the trajectory is represented with yellow colour and estimated pose with a coordinate frame. (Stathoulopoulos et al., 2024).

In the PERSEPHONE project part of the activities will be focused on the high-accuracy navigation and alignment with a face for precise autonomous drilling with further excavation operations. To address this challenge, we propose an approach for high-accuracy alignment using onboard visual surveying methods, considering the machine's size and work area. The precise alignment in this case will be performed by relying solely on onboard cameras, LiDARs, and radars. These sensors will enable safe machine navigation and alignment even in complete darkness or heavy dust, eliminating the need for external positioning systems and accelerating deployment times.

It is planned to develop a new research methodology that will be built on top of existing methods and our current knowledge. As an input data for us will be the following data structures:

- a) Point cloud map of the area.
- b) LiDAR scan.
- c) Radar scan.
- d) Camera image and video feed.
- e) Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) data.
- f) Other parameters.

Within the PERSEPHONE project will be developed a methodology to collect, process and validate data for producing reliable information for safe and precise machine alignment with the face. The core research tasks will be in solving:

- the relocalisation or “kidnapped robot” problem in challenging subterranean conditions in order to estimate the machine’s pose
- solving the task of high-accuracy alignment with a drill face in accordance with the given drilling plan.

In overall, this methodology will be part of the overall Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) framework (KET 3) developed in the project.

This methodology will be applied to the developed concepts of mining machines to enable their autonomous and safe precise positioning and navigation for face drilling. The methodology will be improved by incorporating data from multiple sensors in the framework.

A new methodological framework will be validated on the utilization of novel designs of mining machines and real-mine data for enabling precise alignment and navigation. The aim is to validate that this methodology can be deployed on novel concepts of mining machines.

3.8 On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment

In the context of mining automation, where rugged and unpredictable terrains are commonplace, the reliance on geometric features alone for navigation poses significant challenges. Traditional geometric- based navigation methods often overlook crucial environmental properties such as the type of surface or the presence of obstacles like glass or wire mesh. These oversights can lead to unsafe traversable routes for robotic platforms, especially in complex scenarios where geometric information alone is insufficient. To address these challenges, the incorporation of real-time sensor feedback to assess terrain traversability based on both geometric features and semantic understanding are currently proposed. By incorporating semantic segmentation techniques, such systems can classify terrains and identify obstacles with greater accuracy, enabling more informed decision-making for autonomous navigation. An example, of terrain traversability detection is shown in Figure 3.28.

Figure 3.28. Detection of traversability of the outdoor environment (Saucedo et al., 2024).

In order to tackle the challenge of safe autonomous navigation in subterranean mines in PERSEPHONE will be developed following two-step methodology:

- **Traversability Analysis:** The developed method will allow the machine to analyse the ground terrain to avoid obstacles and non-traversable areas like rocks, unstable ground, deep water, etc.
- **Real-Time Risk Assessment:** As the machine navigates, it will continuously scan its surroundings to detect changes in the environment. By comparing these scans to previous data, the system can identify areas with a high risk of rockfall or collapse based on changes in the scanned maps. These high-risk zones will be flagged and incorporated into the overall mine map, allowing the machine to avoid them in the future.

As input data, the following data structure will be required:

- a) Point cloud map of the area.
- b) LiDAR scan.
- c) Radar scan.

- d) Camera image and video feed.
- e) Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) data.
- f) Other parameters.

Thus, the methodological framework will consist of four key elements:

- **Understanding the Environment:** This involves two processes: semantic segmentation of images to identify different objects and surfaces (e.g., walls, floors, obstacles, rocks) and estimating surface normal from depth images to understand the orientation of these surfaces.
- **Traversability Analysis:** The information from step (a) will be used to create a map indicating how easily the machine can traverse different areas.
- **Prioritizing Safe Paths:** This step refines the traversability map by "inflating" less traversable regions (like obstacles, and rockfalls), making them appear larger and thus encouraging the machine to avoid them.
- **Real-Time Navigation:** Finally, the traversability map is integrated into a reactive navigation system, allowing the machine to navigate in real-time while avoiding obstacles and prioritizing safe paths.

In overall, this methodology will be part of the overall Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) framework (KET 3) developed in the project.

It is expected that this particular methodology will be applied to the developed concepts of mining machines in order to enable their autonomous and safe navigation.

To improve the maturity of technology real mining data will be used. Utilization of such data will allow to validate the developed methodology in high-fidelity simulations. In terms of contribution to current SoTA, it is expected that a new methodological framework will be validated on the utilization of novel designs of mining machines and real-mine data for enabling safe navigation. The aim that this methodology will enhance local machine path planning.

3.9 Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization

Multi-machine operation in GPS-denied subterranean mining environments requires precise localization and mapping. However, taking each machine as an individual unit or agent will not allow to gather holistic information about the tunnels. Especially, considering that each machine has limited resources (e.g. battery capacity). As such, there is an obvious need to establish a map-merging framework. Such a framework will allow to combine multiple local maps from individual machines into one global map. This capability is essential for the next generation of mining machines and live digital twin of a mine. An example of the merging of two maps of the same area is shown in Figure 3.29.

Figure 3.29. Merging of two maps of the same area (Stathouloupoulos et al., 2023).

LiDARs became SoTA sensors for navigation in dark subterranean environments. As output data these sensors produce a point cloud that together with IMU fusion is used in Simultaneous Localization and Mapping algorithms (SLAM) for solving localization and mapping tasks. The methodology that will be developed in PERSEPHONE will focus on the utilization of LiDAR SLAM-produced maps in collaborative multi-agent map merging. This enables collaboratively building a comprehensive map of the entire mine. The map will be continuously updated by each machine as it explores the environment. This ensures the overall mine map reflects the latest information. Machines will share sensor data and map information with each other through a local mesh network (independent of Wi-Fi or similar infrastructure). If a surface connection is available, the updated mine map, information about non-traversable areas, and machine positions will be streamed to surface control centres. This allows human operators to monitor operations in real-time.

As an input data for the newly developed methodology following data structures will be required:

- a) Point cloud map of the area.
- b) LiDAR scan.
- c) Radar scan.
- d) Inertial Measurement Unit (IMU) data.
- e) Other parameters.

Within the PERSEPHONE project a methodology to collect, process and validate data for producing reliable information for safe multi-machine navigation will be developed.

Considering the core research tasks in path planning, it is assumed that it will focus on collaborative SLAM for safe and efficient navigation for autonomous machines in infrastructure-free environments.

Wireless Infrastructureless Mesh Network. In a telecommunication infrastructure free environment, such as an abandoned mine where an autonomous exploration mission is being carried out, it is not possible to rely on an existing network infrastructure and it is not even possible to deploy a temporary wireless network. Therefore, the adoption of an on-board-based fully wireless mesh network is needed, combined also with the adoption of data buffer where store the data during connectivity outage, allowing this information to be then shared with the other elements of the swarm when the connectivity is restored.

In order to achieve these results in a critical environment, it can be possible to exploit the concept of wireless reconfigurable mesh networks to be applied on Wi-Fi equipment installed on the nodes of the swarm, as depicted in Figure 3.30, where a swarm of UAVs is connected through a Wi-Fi IEEE 802.11s mesh network, thus enabling robust infrastructure-free data-exchange with the best routing rules based on the path cost metrics.

Figure 3.30: UAVs swarm enabled infrastructure less communication enabled by on-board Wi-Fi IEEE 802.11s mesh network (Davoli et al., 2021).

In order to achieve such results in an underground environment, several wireless communication protocols can be combined and implemented on-board of the robotic platforms, with the highest throughput task delegated to the robust and short-range Wi-Fi IEEE 802.11s mesh, while for the less demanding applications, long range efficient protocols such as LoRa or XBee can be exploited, in both a point-to-point or mesh network configurations.

Furthermore, data buffering capabilities might be added to the platforms, allowing to store data during critical operations in part of the tunnels where there might not be any communication availability with other machines, thus then allowing them to exchange the gathered data when the connectivity is restored.

In overall, this methodology will be part of the overall Guidance, Navigation and Control (GNC) framework (KET 3) developed in the project.

This methodology will be applied to the developed concepts of mining machines in order to enable their autonomous and safe navigation. One of the project activities is focused on developing of the digital twin of a mine. Utilization of real mining data will allow to validate the developed methodology in high-fidelity simulations.

New methodological framework will be validated on the utilization of novel designs of mining machines and real-mine data for enabling precision navigation. The aim is to extend and make existing path planning solutions capable of addressing existing mining challenges.

3.10 Current and expected TRL with determination applicability of PERSEPHONE technologies in the exploration of analysed use cases

Two use cases are being considered as part of the PERSEPHONE project.

- The first use case concerns the use of innovative, autonomous technologies for exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits.
- The second use case is related to the exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines.

Both use cases are characterized by different environmental conditions and technical possibilities, with particular emphasis on the proximity of active mining infrastructure and utilities.

Based on the questionnaire prepared as part of WP1 of the PERSEPHONE project, the initial and target TRL for each technology was determined and their applicability in each of both use cases was defined. The collective conclusions collected on the basis of the completed questionnaires are presented in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2. Current and target TRL of the PERSEPHONE project technology with the definition of target use cases.

Technology type	Start TRL	End TRL	Use case 1	Use case 2
1. Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes	3	4	✓	✗
2. Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems	2	3	✓	✓
3. Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator	2	5	✓	✗
4. Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling	<i>Depends on sub-technology. Details below</i>			
4.1. LIBS slurry analyser	1	3	✓	✗
4.2. LIBS mine-face scanning	2	4	✓	✓
4.3. MWD and in-situ hardness test	3	4	✓	✗
4.4. Multi-spectral down hole imager	2	4	✓	✓
4.5. Multi-spectral rock face imager	3	5	✓	✓
4.6. Downhole electro (magnetic) measurement – ERT an IP	3	4	✓	✓
4.7. Face-scanning electro (magnetic) measurement ERT-IP	3	4	✓	✓
4.8. Acoustics	2	3	✓	✓
5. Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions	2	5	✓	✓
6. Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination	2	5	✓	✓
7. High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations	2	5	✓	✓
8. On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment	2	5	✓	✓
9. Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization	2	5	✓	✓
10. Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics	2	3	✓	✓
<i>Use case 1- exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits Use case 2 - exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines.</i>				

4 End-user requirements for exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits – USE CASE 1

In this section, the project requirements related to the mining of deep deposits will be defined and analysed in detail, which in turn will define the project objectives of the rest of the WPs. The outcome of this section will be to define and set the end-user requirements for technologies developed within the PERSEPHONE project.

According to the Cambridge Dictionary “End-user” is a person or organization that uses something rather than an organization that trades in it.

4.1 Identification of end users

In order to correctly determine the requirements set by end users to new technologies, it is necessary to take actions aimed at the correct identification of these users. Requirements set by units not necessarily involved in the process of exploitation of a given technology could result in an incorrect definition of the objective function, which would effectively prevent the effective development of individual technologies.

As part of the activities carried out under WP1, the process of identifying end-users was carried out in two ways (Figure 4.1). On the one hand, a literature review was carried out in the field of developed technologies in order to identify end users of technologies that are currently implemented in exploration and mining activities. On the other hand, a questionnaire was prepared aimed, among other things, at identifying the end users of the technologies developed under the PERSEPHONE project. The questionnaire was sent to all partners of the PERSEPHONE project consortium (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.1. Process of identifying end-user requirements.

The extensive experience and competences of the PERSEPHONE project consortium (Figure 4.2) determined the reliability of the information collected as part of the questionnaire. The end-user identification list is shown in Table 4.1.

Figure 4.2. Partners are involved in defining the requirements for technologies developed within PERSEPHONE along with their core background.

Table 4.1. Identification of end users for technologies developed for USE CASE 1.

Technology type	End-user			
	Mining operator	R&D Academia	Exploration company	Technology developer Machine producer
1. Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes	✓	✗	✗	✗
2. Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems	✓	✓	✓	✓
3. Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator	✓	✓	✗	✗
4. Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling	Depends on sub-technology. Details below			
4.1. LIBS slurry analyser	✓	✓	✗	✗
4.2. LIBS mine-face scanning	✓	✓	✓	✓
4.3. MWD and in-situ hardness test	✓	✗	✓	✓
4.4. Multi-spectral down hole imager	✓	✓	✓	✗
4.5. Multi-spectral rock face imager	✓	✓	✓	✗
4.6. Downhole electro (magnetic) measurement – ERT an IP	✓	✓	✓	✗
4.7. Face-scanning electro (magnetic) measurement ERT-IP	✓	✓	✓	✗

4.8. Acoustics	✓	✓	✓	✗
5. Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions	✓	✓	✗	✗
6. Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination	✓	✓	✓	✗
7. High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations	✓	✓	✗	✗
8. On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment	✓	✓	✓	✓
9. Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure free mapping and localization	✓	✓	✓	✓
10. Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics	✓	✓	✓	✓
✓ - Primary user ✓ - Indirect user ✗ - The entity is not the intended user				

4.2 Defining the requirements

Table 4.2. End-user requirements for technologies developed for USE CASE 1.

<p>Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes</p> <p>Infrastructural requirements: Depending on the type of preconditioning.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the case of preconditioning using hydrofracturing, access to machinery enabling drilling holes and injecting liquid under high pressure into the rock mass must be necessary. • In the case of destress blasting, access to machines and tools enabling the placement of explosives in the rock mass is necessary. <p>End-user requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The developed preconditioning method must be adapted to the operating system used. • It is important that the solutions used do not negatively affect the roof conditions and the stability of the workings near the preconditioning site (such situations occurred in the past, among others, during destress blasting). • The cost of the machinery and tools used for rock mass preconditioning must be justified in terms of the economics of conducting the work. This means that reducing mining costs by softening the rock mass should compensate for any costs incurred for pre-conditioning.
<p>Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems</p> <p>Infrastructural requirements: Ultimately, technology will be designed such that extra additional infrastructure will not be needed. However, the development of the implementation phase in the project will require special infrastructures such as external tracking systems and mechanical, electronic and 3d printing workshops. Also, specialised sensors and communication systems may be needed for monitoring and control.</p>

<p>End-user requirements: From the end-user perspective the developed technology has to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work in hard environments (high humidity, no light, no external power infrastructure). • Has an accurate self-positioning. • Be able to drill at least one hole to know some parameters of possible excavation. • Be able to drill according to a drill plan and adjust based on drill data. • Be able to operate withing 2 m x 2 m pathways.
<p>Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator</p>
<p>Infrastructural requirements: Need for additional hardware for drilling equipment. An additional module for data handling for drilling data and measured hole deviation technology data will be required. From the perspective of technology implementation drilling machines need to be upgraded with software to visualise the results.</p> <p>End-user requirements: From the end user's perspective, it would be recommended if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was possible to install the module on drilling rigs already available in the mine. • The system should be adapted to the difficult environment in underground conditions. • The hole deviation measurement module must enable ongoing visualization of data while drilling holes and subsequent archiving of this data for further use, among others, for mining efficiency analyses. • The system should not affect the continuity of the machine's operation (the machine must be able to work even in the event of a system failure). • The system should be easy to use so that machine operators can use it effectively after a short training. • The measurement process cannot be time consumed. • Collected deviation data must be compatible with other drilling data.
<p>Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - LIBS slurry analyser</p>
<p>Infrastructural requirements: Additional infrastructure would be limited to a system that collects the drilling fluid from the hole as it is being drilled, as this is currently not common practice.</p> <p>End-user requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should survive test environment: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ IP rating 67. ○ Temperature operating range (0-40 deg). ○ Vibration/shock resistance. • Ease-of-use.

- Can be integrated onto the drilling rig (power supply, data accessibility, control interface).
- Limited maintenance.
- Depth resolution: 5 cm.
- Accuracy:
 - Minimum: distinguish ore/waste.
 - Required accuracy depends strongly on the case.
 - Repeatability of results.
- Works on all rock types.
- Low power consumption.
- The system should be laser-safe (Class 1 system).
- Data processing:
 - Results in < 1 min

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - LIBS mine-face scanning

Infrastructural requirements: Ideally, the technology would not need a lot of additional supporting infrastructure, as it should operate relatively autonomously using battery packs mounted on rovers/robots.

End-user requirements:

- The device should be able to operate without access to the power grid.
- Sufficient working time (proper power source).
- Low power consumption.
- The device should be able to operate in places without access to light.
- The mining face scan should enable a clear determination of the rock layers within the face, which is necessary for proper drilling planning.
- Straightforward visualization of results.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - MWD and in-situ hardness test

Infrastructural requirements: For MWD measurement nothing except the sensor system is required. In the future connectivity to the MRP database will be needed for the purpose of digital twin and geo model creation. Also edge computer will be required on the rig.

End-user requirements:

- Easy and safe to use.
- Flawless data handling process.
- Suitable for the test environment. (temp, humidity etc).
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems

for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Multi-spectral down hole imager

Infrastructural requirements: Implementation of technology in deep mines will require only the sensor system. In the future connectivity to MRP database will be needed for the purpose of digital twin and geomodel creation.

End-user requirements:

- Should survive test environment:
 - IP rating 67.
 - Temperature operating range (0-40°C).
 - Vibration/shock resistance.
- Ease-of-use.
- Can be integrated onto drilling rig (power supply, data accessibility, control interface).
- Limited maintenance (quick water cleaning).
- Sufficient working time (proper power source).
- Low power consumption.
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.
- Accuracy:
 - Minimum: distinguish one type of ore from waste.
 - Required accuracy depends strongly on specific target mineralogy case.
 - Repeatability of results.
- Data processing:
 - Results in <15 min (1 m virtual core).

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Multi-spectral rock face imager

Infrastructural requirements: Implementation of technology in deep mines will require only the sensor system. In the future connectivity to MRP database will be needed for the purpose of digital twin and geo-model creation.

End-user requirements:

- Should survive test environment:
 - IP rating 67.
 - Temperature operating range (0-40°C).
 - Vibration/shock resistance.
- Ease-of-use.
- Can be integrated onto the drilling rig (power supply, data accessibility, control interface).
- Limited maintenance (quick water cleaning).
- Sufficient working time (proper power source).
- Low power consumption.
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.
- Accuracy:
 - Minimum: distinguish one type of ore from waste.

- Required accuracy depends strongly on the specific target mineralogy case.
- Repeatability of results.
- Data processing:
 - Results in <1min (3×3 m image).

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Downhole electro(magnetic) measurement - ERT and IP

Infrastructural requirements: Nothing will be mounted on current machinery, the system will be self-standing (laptop and batteries) with potential connectivity to the drilling rig.

End-user requirements:

- Easy to use.
- Safe for the operator.
- Can be integrated onto the drilling rig/exploration machine.
- Easy and automated electrodes replacement.
- Low power consumption.
- Flawless data handling process.
- Suitable for the test environment. (temp, humidity etc).
- Resolution depth: a few cm – meters.
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.
- Must be able to distinguish ore/waste and hint at structural discontinuities.
- Scans should take no longer than 45 minutes/profile for a resolution of 5-10 cm.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Face-scanning electro(magnetic) measurement ERT-IP

Infrastructural requirements: Nothing will be mounted on current machinery, the system will be self-standing (laptop and batteries) with potential connectivity to an exploration rover.

End-user requirements:

- Easy to use.
- Safe for the operator.
- Can be integrated onto the drilling rig/exploration machine.
- Easy and automated electrodes replacement.
- Sufficient working time.
- Low power consumption.
- Flawless data handling process.
- Suitable for the test environment. (temp, humidity etc).
- Resolution depth: few cm – meters.
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.

- Must be able to distinguish ore/waste and hint at structural discontinuities.
- Scans should take no longer than 45 minutes/profile for a resolution of 5-10 cm.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Acoustics

Infrastructural requirements: There is no infrastructural requirements in relation to this technology. The system will be self-standing with potential connectivity to the drilling rig.

End-user requirements:

- Acoustic sensors must fit in holes of small diameters (coreless drilling).
- It has to have a good connection between the sensor and rockmass to properly gather acoustic data.
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.
- Sufficient working time.
- Low power consumption.
- Spatial resolution of at least 15 cm.

Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions

Infrastructural requirements: Efficient implementation of computer-aided planning requires the installation of underground geomechanical monitoring systems (at least convergence measurement). A seismic network is optional but recommended.

End-user requirements:

- Models should be prepared based on geological data already available.
- Geometry of workings and 3D models has to be generated based on maps of mining progress. Cannot be too simplified.
- The analysis results must be understandable to people not advanced in numerical modelling. The results of the calculations should be displacements and the safety factor.
- Data used for model validation should be available using currently installed monitoring systems.
- If it is necessary to install additional devices, they must be low-cost and should enable measurement without disturbing the operational process.
- In the case of strength parameters of rocks collected in situ (Schmidt's hammer, MWD), the results should be compared with laboratory tests in laboratory conditions to confirm the reliability of the new results.

Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination

Infrastructural requirements: Proposed methodology is infrastructureless and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centre above the surface.

End-user requirements: The developed methodological framework should be capable of:

- Replace manually operated machines with autonomous machines with no loss in production.
- Remove the human presence from highly increased operating depths.
- Minimise the number of traffic conflicts.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation in challenging conditions, without the need of ventilation infrastructure.
- Enable robotized drilling plans with increased accuracy.
- High level of safety (human detection nearby).

High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations

Infrastructural requirements: The proposed technology is infrastructureless and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centres above the surface.

End-user requirements: The developed methodological framework is capable:

- Replace manually operated machines with autonomous machines with no loss in production.
- Remove the human presence from highly increased operating depths.
- Minimise the number of traffic conflicts.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation in challenging conditions, without the need of ventilation infrastructure.
- Enable robotized drilling plans with increased accuracy.
- High level of safety (human detection nearby).

On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment

Infrastructural requirements: This methodology is infrastructureless and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centres above the surface.

End-user requirements: The developed methodological framework should be capable of:

- Replace manually operated machines with autonomous machines with no loss in production.
- Remove the human presence from highly increased operating depths.
- Minimise the number of traffic conflicts.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation in challenging conditions, without the need for ventilation infrastructure.
- Enable robotized drilling plans with increased accuracy.

Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure-free mapping and localization

Infrastructural requirements: This methodology is infrastructure-less and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centre above the surface.

End-user requirements: The developed methodological framework should be capable of:

- Replace manually operated machines with autonomous machines with no loss in production.
- Remove the human presence from highly increased operating depths.
- Minimise the number of traffic conflicts.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation in challenging conditions, without the need for ventilation infrastructure.
- Enable robotized drilling plans with increased accuracy.
- High level of safety (human detection nearby).

Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics

Infrastructural requirements: Environmental and scenarios parameters needed for simulation integration.

End-user requirements: An autonomous drill planning system should be able to:

- Work in hard environments (high humidity, no light, no external power infrastructure), accurate position and ability to drill at least one hole to know some parameters of possible excavation.
- To be able to drill according to a drill plan and adjusting base on drill data.
- Achieve reaching heights of >2 m for placing of the driller, with an accuracy of ≤ 30 cm in XYZ.
- Autonomously aligned and positioned in the drift for drilling operations to $\leq 5^\circ$ in dip, $\leq 5^\circ$ degrees in azimuth, and ≤ 50 cm in XYZ.
- Should be able to drill 2m through the face.

5 End-user requirements for exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines - USE CASE 2

There are many areas in Europe and worldwide where low-profile mine drives exist, which once upon a time were being used for accessing ore deposits. In the light of current mineral market and possible future, there is significant potential to use this access to research these deposits for future development. As a test site for technology development GM mining area is considered.

Only in Euboea Island, central Greece, and only in mining concessions managed by Grecian Magnesite (GM), there are currently more than 100 km of low profile (2 m × 2 m, approx.) underground mine drives that intersect magnesite mineralization zones of very good to superior quality. All these existing networks of abandoned/suspended underground mines were developed by handheld equipment between 1832 and 1965 and since then they have been abandoned or suspended due to the discovery of large-scale near-surface deposits. The decision-making teams of mining companies back then favoured the development of surface operations over underground ones for the following reasons:

- Prior to 1965, mine technology and related solutions were more reliable for surface operations than for underground works.
- The exploration technology and work were easier to execute and more productive for near-surface deposits, compared to finding and interpreting steeply dipping mineralised zones.

Taking into consideration the case of GM and its Euboean deposits, where the magnesite mineralization has the form of steeply dipping parallel vein systems of highly fluctuating true thickness, under an irregular terrain covered by dense forests, the required exploration work is generally conducted with inclined boreholes of mean length 300 m/exploration string (Figure 5.1). The respective exploration work is currently time-consuming, and tedious, it has a high cost and a medium to high environmental impact.

Figure 5.1. Cross-section of the GM site – one of PERSEPHONE use-cases.

At the same time, there exists a dense network of low profile (2 m × 2 m approx.) old underground mine drives that intersect mineralised zones of very good to superior quality. These drives are unsupported and re-entry of personnel is laborious and entails high risks. Adding to it, the execution of drive widening and supporting works under the frame of exploration tunnelling is accompanied by

high costs and risks, since specific and not all magnesite grades are in general targeted through underground works.

Under this framework, the potential utilization of an autonomous exploration system in abandoned/suspended underground mines could significantly cut down exploration costs and render known resources into reserves. Moreover, the utilization of existing underground drives for exploration purposes could skyrocket the green transition of mining companies, since intervention works on terrains of high environmental value could be kept to a minimum. Therefore, the possibility of using innovative autonomous technologies for the needs of the PERSEPHONE project was analysed and the requirements of possible end users for specific technologies and solutions were determined.

5.1 Identification of end users

Due to environmental and technological conditions, not all technologies can be successfully used in abandoned and suspended mines. These restrictions mainly concern the lack of access to mine utilities, such as access to the electricity grid and water. Additionally, it is assumed that any type of regular machine will not be able to be sent to such places due to possible oxygen deficient, presence of toxic gases and small dimensions of the mining excavations.

Additionally, taking into account the nature of abandoned and suspended mines, it can be assumed that the main, direct end user in this case will be the entity responsible for carrying out the exploration works. Based on this knowledge and information contained in the questionnaires for the PERSEPHONE project, the end users for *use case 2 - which is the exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines* were identified (Table 5.1).

Table 5.1. Identification of end users for technologies developed for USE CASE 2.

Technology type	End-user			
	Mining operator	R&D Academia	Exploration company	Technology developer Machine producer
1. Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems	✓	✓	✓	✓
2. Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling	<i>Depends on sub-technology. Details below</i>			
2.1. LIBS mine-face scanning	✓	✓	✓	✓
2.2. Multi-spectral down hole imager	✓	✓	✓	✗
2.3. Multi-spectral rock face imager	✓	✓	✓	✗
3. Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions	✓	✓	✓	✗

4. Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination	✓	✗	✓	✗
5. High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations	✓	✗	✓	✗
6. On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment	✓	✗	✓	✓
7. Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure free mapping and localization	✓	✗	✓	✓
8. Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics	✓	✗	✓	✓
✓ - Primary user ✓ - Indirect user ✗ - The entity is not the intended user				

5.2 Defining the requirements

Table 5.2. End-user requirements for technologies developed for USE CASE 2.

Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems
<p>Infrastructural requirements: Ultimately, technology will be designed such that extra additional infrastructure will not be needed. However, the development of the implementation phase in the project will require special infrastructures such as external tracking systems and mechanical, electronic and 3d printing workshops. Also, specialised sensors and communication systems may be needed for monitoring and control.</p> <p>End-user requirements: From the end-user perspective the developed technology has to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work in hard environments (high humidity, no light, no external power infrastructure). • Has an accurate self-positioning. • Be able to drill at least one hole to know some parameters of possible excavation. • Be able to drill according to a drill plan and adjust based on drill data. • Be able to operate withing 2 m x 2 m pathways.
Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - LIBS mine-face scanning
<p>Infrastructural requirements: According to current plan the technology would not need of additional supporting infrastructure, as it should operate autonomously using battery packs mounted on rovers/robots.</p> <p>End-user requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The device should be able to operate without access to the power grid. • The device should be able to operate in places without access to light. • The mining face scan should enable a clear determination of the rock layers within the face, which is necessary for proper drilling planning. • Sufficient working time.

- Low power consumption.
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Multi-spectral down hole imager

Infrastructural requirements: Implementation of technology in abandoned and suspended mines will require the installation of the sensor system on an autonomous robot/vehicle.

End-user requirements:

- Should survive test environment:
 - IP rating 67.
 - Temperature operating range (0-40°C).
 - Vibration/shock resistance.
- Ease-of-use.
- Can be integrated onto the drilling rig (power supply, data accessibility, control interface).
- Limited maintenance (quick water cleaning).
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.
- Low power consumption.
- Sufficient working time.
- Accuracy:
 - Minimum: distinguish one type of ore from waste.
 - Required accuracy depends strongly on specific target mineralogy case.
 - Repeatability of results.
- Data processing:
 - Results in <15min (1m virtual core).

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Multi-spectral rock face imager

Infrastructural requirements: Implementation of technology in abandoned and suspended mines will require installation of the sensor system on autonomous robot/machine.

End-user requirements:

- Should survive test environment:
 - IP rating 67.
 - Temperature operating range (0-40°C).
 - Vibration/shock resistance.
- Ease-of-use.
- Can be integrated onto drilling rig (power supply, data accessibility, control interface).
- Limited maintenance (quick water cleaning).
- Straightforward spatial visualization of results.

- Low power consumption.
- Sufficient working time.
- Accuracy:
 - Minimum: distinguish one type of ore from waste.
 - Required accuracy depends strongly on the specific target mineralogy case.
 - Repeatability of results.
- Data processing:
 - Results in <1min (3×3m image).

Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions

Infrastructural requirements: Computer-aided data-driven approach requires input of in-situ gathered data considering geometry of workings and strength parameters of rocks, thus preparation of the model has to be preceded by exploration drill holes, or measurements with use of autonomous technologies developed within PERSEPHONE project.

End-user requirements:

- Models should be prepared based on geological data already available.
- The geometry of workings and 3D models has to be generated based on the existing structure of workings. Cannot be too simplified.
- The analysis results must be understandable to people not advanced in numerical modelling. The results of the calculations should be displacements and the safety factor.
- Data used for model validation should be available using currently installed monitoring systems.
- If it is necessary to install additional devices, they must be low-cost and should enable measurement without disturbing the operational process.
- In the case of strength parameters of rocks collected in situ (Schmidt's hammer, MWD), the results should be compared with laboratory tests in laboratory conditions to confirm the reliability of the new results.

Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination

Infrastructural requirements: The proposed technology is infrastructureless and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centres above the surface.

End-user requirements:

- Establish autonomous machines as part of the abandoned mine survey for re-opening purposes.
- Remove the human presence from highly unknown and potentially dangerous conditions of the abandoned mine.
- Enable the data collection of the abandoned mine condition for decision-making.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation of multiple platforms for efficient exploration of the infrastructure-free abandoned mine.
- Allow the collection of various inspection data, based on the needs of the operator to take the decision of the abandoned mine re-opening.

- Sufficient working time.
- Low power consumption.

High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations

Infrastructural requirements: The proposed technology is infrastructureless and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centre above the surface.

End-user requirements:

- Establish autonomous machines as part of the abandoned mine survey for re-opening purposes.
- Remove the human presence from highly unknown and potentially dangerous conditions of the abandoned mine.
- Enable the data collection of the abandoned mine condition for decision-making.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation of multiple platforms for efficient exploration of the infrastructure-free abandoned mine.
- Allow the collection of various inspection data, based on the needs of the operator to take the decision of the abandoned mine re-opening.
- Sufficient working time.
- Low power consumption.

On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment

Infrastructural requirements: The proposed technology is infrastructureless and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centre above the surface.

End-user requirements:

- Establish autonomous machines as part of the abandoned mine survey for re-opening purposes.
- Remove the human presence from highly unknown and potentially dangerous conditions of the abandoned mine.
- Enable the data collection of the abandoned mine condition for decision-making.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation of multiple platforms for efficient exploration of the infrastructure-free abandoned mine.
- Allow the collection of various inspection data, based on the needs of the operator to take the decision of the abandoned mine re-opening.
- Sufficient working time.
- Low power consumption.

Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure free mapping and localization

Infrastructural requirements: The proposed technology is infrastructureless and is purely based on the mining machines with onboard perception and mining control centre above the surface.

End-user requirements:

- Establish autonomous machines as part of the abandoned mine survey for re-opening purposes.
- Remove the human presence from highly unknown and potentially dangerous conditions of the abandoned mine.
- Enable the data collection of the abandoned mine condition for decision-making.
- Enable continuous and long-term operation of multiple platforms for efficient exploration of the infrastructure-free abandoned mine.
- Allow the collection of various inspection data, based on the needs of the operator to take the decision of the abandoned mine re-opening.
- Sufficient working time.
- Low power consumption.
- Robust connectivity between the mining machines

Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics

Infrastructural requirements: Implementation may require specialised drilling equipment, installation of robust sensor systems capable of operating harsh environments, and advanced control systems to ensure reliable operation in deep and challenging conditions.

End-user requirements: Autonomous drill planning system should be able to:

- Work in hard environments (high humidity, no light, no external power infrastructure), accurate position and ability to drill at least one hole to know some parameters of possible excavation.
- To be able to drill according to a drill plan and adjusting base on drill data.
- Achieve reaching heights of >2 m for placing of the driller, with an accuracy of ≤ 30 cm in XYZ.
- Autonomously aligned and positioned in the drift for drilling operations to $\leq 5^\circ$ in dip, $\leq 5^\circ$ degrees in azimuth, and ≤ 50 cm in XYZ.
- Should be able to drill 2m through the face.

6 Setting the framework conditions for alignment with the UNFC and UNRMS

6.1 Introduction and objectives

Today mining projects are not only determined by what is in the ground and what can be taken out technically at economically competitive costs, but most significantly also by the socio-economic and -political context. The wide absence of mining projects across Europe has made societies become detached from this very first step in our non-biological value chains. While there are far-ranging societal discourses over the desirable socio-economic development trajectories in the future that help to mitigate climate change, it is clear that over the short to medium term we need to ensure a sufficient supply of mineral raw materials to make up for dispersive losses and lock-up in goods and infrastructure.

In most areas in Europe mining projects will only have a chance for realisation and, therefore, viability from the investors' point of view, when concerns over their environmental and societal impacts and concerns are addressed adequately and when their implementation process follows expectations of good governance. Task 1.4 of PERSEPHONE sets out to investigate these boundary conditions and provide tools for their inclusion in the technology development assessment.

The objective of PERSEPHONE, therefore, must be to develop extraction processes that result in low-impact and low-visibility mines. In the following, the measures and **requirements to meet environmental, societal, and governance (ESG) goals** are discussed. The concept of low-impact/low-visibility mines was already explored in the FP7 project I²Mine (I²Mine, 2024) and in the H2020 project ROBOMINERS (ROBOMINERS, 2024), and PERSEPHONE will take this further, by developing 'minimally invasive' extraction techniques.

Every extraction project requires vast amounts of energy to open up shafts, tunnels, and galleries and to break up and process the target ore. In the past, often only a single commodity was targeted, sometimes other commodities were and are produced as by-products. This has two consequences, namely large quantities of extractive wastes are generated and when it turns out that these wastes or parts of the mine contain other commodities that subsequently have become of commercial interest, these materials or mines may be reworked. There is, however, also the risk, that previous mine workings have effectively 'sterilised' certain mineral occurrences because of the high risk of accessing already mined areas by conventional mining techniques. For this reason, the concept of **comprehensive and integrated resource recovery** has been promoted. While this makes sense from a sustainability and safety perspective, it is not so easy to justify from an economic and business perspective. If there is no market for a certain commodity at a given time, there are no commercial incentives to process the excavated material to retrieve this commodity. Stockpiling may be a solution, but also entails costs for providing and maintaining the respective storage facilities. There will be also regulatory challenges in the case of existing mines, as mining permits are normally given for a given set of target commodities. Enlarging the scope will require an amendment to the permit. This Task will explore how

the implications of total extraction and stockpiling can be reflected in a UNFC assessment.

A topic closely related to that of total extraction is that of **valorising extraction residues**. Minimising unwanted extraction and, hence, waste has been a major goal of the industry, as the management of waste is costly and has to follow the rules set by the Extractive Waste Directive (EWD, 2006). However, a certain amount of extractive waste is unavoidable due to the need to dig shafts and tunnels to access the mineral occurrence. New mineral resources are likely to be located deeper than those exploited in the past so that inevitably larger quantities of waste will arise. PERSEPHONE on the other hand aims to develop exploration and mining techniques that reduce the amount of material excavated due to smaller diameter access facilities and more targeted extraction. Nevertheless, it will be of overall economic and environmental benefit, if these excavated materials can be turned into a useful resource and/or used underground without the need to lift them to the surface just for disposal. This Task will look into, how the valorisation of such residues will influence the classification of the target resource according to UNFC from an economic and ESG point of view. At the exploration and in the early project stages the above issue constitutes a significant project risk, as the associated costs are difficult to capture.

This task will also serve as a guide to reduce the investment risk towards, as a result, acceptance among stakeholders and mining companies.

6.1.1 Low-impact / low-visibility mining

As noted above, the concept of low-impact / low-visibility mining had already been developed for the FP7 project I²Mine (I²Mine, 2024). The conceptual challenges of a deep mine with minimal environmental impacts while reaching ever deeper have been summarised in Figure 6.1.

Figure 6.1. Conceptual challenges of low-visibility / low-impact mine (from I²Mine).

A key point is that every movement of mass will entail some form of environmental and potentially also societal impact.

It is obvious that moving rock masses requires energy and this energy has to be harvested in some form from nature through an energy conversion system. Depending on the conversion system chosen or available, there will be a certain carbon footprint associated with any Joule of energy provided to the mine operation. This carbon footprint can already be reduced by opting out of fossil fuel-operated systems as much as possible for both, stationary electricity provision and powering mobile plants and vehicles. Currently, a number of alternatives are available, namely a completely electrified mine or the use of other energy carriers, such as hydrogen.

It is important to remember that hydrogen is not a fuel, as often apostrophed in the popular press, but only an energy carrier. Hydrogen production from water is an energy-intensive process. The most commonly used process today is electrolysis, which in turn requires electricity. The major low-carbon electricity generating systems are photovoltaics, wind or nuclear. As will be discussed later in more detail, mine-safety and the safety of underground workers is a major concern in the extractive industry and, therefore, the use of hydrogen as an energy carrier in an underground mine may give rise to serious safety concerns, e.g. in the case of leakages.

In addition to avoiding emissions from fossil carbon at the source, the industry is also working on carbon recovery and capturing strategies for equipment, machinery and vehicles in the mine. Such systems certainly would improve the air-quality underground, but they are end-of-the-pipe solutions for a problem that is better addressed at the root. Avoiding 'unwanted' extraction by reducing the size of access shafts, tunnels, adits etc. to the practical minimum is another strategy to reduce mass movement.

Avoiding hoisting materials to the surface considerably reduces the energy expenditure and at the same time reduces the area required for constructing impoundments for mining residues. The idea would be to dispose of or re-utilise as much as possible excavated materials that do not contain any target minerals. There are practical limitations though, as a certain volume of open underground space is needed for operating the mine and because the disaggregated rock can never be compacted back to its original density. There will be always a considerable amount of excess rock that needs to be managed/disposed of at the surface. One also needs to strike a balance between the impacts arising from surface management of mining residues and the energy requirement for possibly bringing them back underground, for instance as backfill. There may be economic and environmental advantages from backfilling, as filling in open mine spaces with material of sufficient strength will allow to mine the area between the previous open mine-works. This technique was extensively used in coalmining, where coal seams would have considerable lateral extent and where otherwise perhaps half or more of the coal would have been lost and sterilised for further mining.

Autonomous robotic exploration and mining systems, as envisaged by PERSEPHONE, are designed to operate in smaller open spaces and perform more targeted excavation, guided by on-board analytical systems. Smaller excavated

volumes result in less energy expended in disintegrating the rock material and less energy expended on transporting these materials to other areas of the mine or to the surface.

In existing or abandoned mines key decisions about the original layout of the mine and the extractive waste management decisions will have already been taken and frequently a long time ago. There will still be significant benefits from deploying the techniques under investigation in PERSEPHONE. For instance, more targeted and possibly comprehensive extraction will result in less waste generated per amount of metal value recovered. This can have a significant impact on the life-time extension of a mine. As more can be produced without needing more disposal volume for extractive waste on the surface than planned, which often is the most serious bottleneck from the perspective of both, of land availability and of regulatory and stakeholder approval. Drone-base surveying techniques can also aid in developing concepts for backfilling wastes, as they allow to calculate available volumes and to assess the state of these mine voids that may not have been maintained for a long time. Remotely operated or autonomous machinery may also permit to access mine voids for backfilling that would be unsafe to enter for personnel, thus making more disposal volume available.

Already in I²Mine a key strategy towards a low visibility mine was move as much of the crushing, sorting, and subsequent processing below ground as possible. This avoids having unsightly and possibly noisy operations on the surface, thus reducing the associated nuisances and impacts. With the crushing and sorting taking place within the mine, lifting out of the mine of much of the gangue is avoided, limiting the associated energy expenditure and reducing the volume of material that will have to be managed as mining residues on the surface. Although cavities of sufficient size need to be opened up, it is likely that a net gain in volume reduction will be achieved.

As Figure 6.1 indicates, a number of challenges need to be considered, when aiming for such options.

6.1.2 Comprehensive extraction

When there is a viable market for a constituent mineral or metal, comprehensive extraction is a logical business decision, aligned with recent sustainable development recommendations (Hilton et al., 2018). In a world of increasing scarce natural resources and possible external constraints, such as politically motivated disruptions of supply-webs, comprehensive extraction will also become a strategic decision to safeguard natural resources and to ensure supply even when markets are not fully functioning.

Most natural occurrences of minerals and metals contain a certain spectrum of other minerals and metals beyond the one that is of immediate commercial interest. In history, many metals went unrecognised due to the lack of knowledge of the periodic system of elements and/or because no suitable analytical techniques were available. Other metals or minerals were not analysed ignored, because there was no technical or economic use for them. Today we have comprehensive chemical and mineralogical knowledge and analytical capabilities that can be deployed even down in a mine and at the working face of a mine. A

wide variety of analytical techniques give us a whole spectrum of elements at no extra OPEX. Combined with modern analytical techniques that give information on mineralogy, these allow us to analyse even small concentrations of potentially interesting metal occurrences (Butcher et al. 2023).

Comprehensive extraction serves several purposes. It prevents a potentially important source of certain mineral raw materials becoming sterilised, i.e. inaccessible, due to previous mining works. It can be technically difficult and unsafe to re-enter and re-mine an area that has already been mined, due to the unpredictable behaviour of the host rocks. On the other hand, also energy is saved, as the material is only moved once and then possibly put through several extraction steps.

There are obvious technical and economic limitations to comprehensive extraction. The presence alone of a certain metal is not sufficient, it also needs to be present at a certain minimum concentration. In principle even very small concentrations can be extracted, which is the basis for analytics at trace concentrations. However, the amount of energy embedded into processes increases exponentially with decreasing concentration, so that extraction not only may make no commercial sense, but energy expenditures may surpass energy and other impact savings from comprehensive extraction. For this reason, a careful cost vs. benefit analysis with respect to gains and impacts is needed.

Another technical issue would be degree of refractiveness of the minerals to which the accessory target metals are bound. In other words, whether a cost-and energy-effective processing method with limited environmental impact can be found. While comprehensive extraction would make sense from a strategic supply perspective, this does not necessarily mean that it is commercially viable at a given time. If the full economic operational cost (OPEX) and the preceding set-up costs for the process (CAPEX) cannot be recovered within a certain amortization timeframe, no mine or mineral processor will venture into such an undertaking. Various mines do stockpile certain products or certain extractive residues when they expect to find a market for them over a reasonable time horizon. In a market economy, however, it is unreasonable to expect mining companies to stockpile such material in the case that one day in the future an economic use for them is found. There are also constraints by the Extractive Waste Directive (EWD, 2006) under which regulators may consider stockpiles after a certain period as unmanaged extractive waste.

On the other hand, we have various metals that were of little use and value ten or 20 years ago and that now are in great demand, most notably, of course, REE and lithium for instance. A forward-looking approach, scanning the horizon for technological developments that may give rise to a respective demand may be helpful as a decision-aiding tool. It needs to be kept in mind, that comprehensive extraction may not only be an economic decision but has a strong political-strategic aspect that goes beyond straightforward business decisions.

As noted above, comprehensive extraction in addition may meet regulatory challenges. Usually permits are given for one or more target commodities. The logic behind is that each mineral may require a specific route of comminution and processing, for which then also the respective EIA need to be undertaken.

In order to make an otherwise unwise business decision economically attractive, external incentives would need to be provided. One could think of tax-credits for contributing to strategic autonomy, tradeable CO₂-credits for avoiding the energy expenditure of additional mining, direct subsidies for stockpiling strategic minerals, or the government buys up materials considered to be strategic. The recent Critical Raw Material Act (EC, 2023) already discusses such possibilities. It should be noted that such actions may in fact undermine the credo of market economy, as supply, demand, and price are not determined by a free market economy, but by the actions of governments.

6.1.3 Valorisation of extractive waste

The stated aim of PERSEPHONE is *inter alia* to help reduce the amount of extractive waste. As has been stated in the PERSEPHONE proposal, comprehensive characterisation with a view to comprehensive extraction is one strategy to overall reduce the amount of extractive waste generated. This view has been recently underlined by Parbhakar-Fox & Baumgartner (2023), who state that a comprehensive characterisation during the exploration and the actual mining phase helps to make extractive waste management more efficient.

The Extractive Waste Directive (EWD, 2006) and subsidiary national legislation determine the framework according to which such waste has to be managed. While the EWD already prefers avoidance and recycling, it has to be kept in mind that the concepts of 'waste' and of 'waste-management' originate in paradigms from the middle of 20th century, when it began to be recognised that inadequate waste-management may lead to significant environmental impacts. Waste management conceptually is an 'end-of-pipe' treatment of a problem, rather than tackling it at the root. The underlying strategy of the EWD is to ensure permanently safe disposal of the waste at the earliest possible moment during operation. 'Waste' in this sense means not only an economic decision about materials excavated during a mining operation, but the declaration of a material as being 'waste' attributes a certain legal property to it and triggers in consequence the obligation to manage/dispose of it as prescribed by the EWD and its national implementations.

This legal property has important consequences for what may be done and what may not be done with these materials. These consequences may be even more severe at the national level than what is outlined by the EWD. In various EU legislative systems, it is virtually impossible to touch again disposed materials. The motives originally were laudable, mainly to ensure that an environmentally safe and permanent solution was implemented, that would not allow operators to walk away from temporary solutions e.g., in the case of financial difficulties.

However, paradigms have changed with the arrival of the concept of 'circular economy'. In some other fields with similar regulatory constraints, for instance, in the case of electronics scrap, the problem was sought to be circumvented by promoting the concept of an 'end-of-waste'-state. This is essentially a regulatory procedure that allows waste to be re-integrated into the productive economy. In the case of 'extractive waste' no such solution is yet available, although the issue is being discussed in technical and regulatory circles.

Extractive residues are still awaiting a more comprehensive solution that drops the concept of 'waste' altogether and rather looks in a systemic way at the life cycle of materials with a view to create some sort of materials stewardship. An important impediment for the valorisation of extractive residues stems from the timeframes set by the EWD (2006) for managing materials as waste. Unless used for construction purposes within a mine, materials for which no further use is foreseen within the set timeframe of several years must be disposed of in adequate waste management facilities. This effectively prevents stockpiling materials of uncertain future value as noted earlier. Unfortunately, once this material has been officially declared 'waste', it must be disposed of permanently in an engineered extractive waste facility (with liners, covers and drainage as may be required) after having successfully undergone the required licensing procedures.

In most legislative systems, a license for (re-)mining would need to be applied for, which may take too long to follow market trends. This is in contrast to the fact that technically, it could be relatively easy and safe to dig up and process such materials.

Within the current regulatory framework of the EWD (2006) it is, therefore, important to carefully tailor the management of excavated materials to conceivable further uses. To this end the characterisation of the geomaterials at the exploration phase or as part of the production process will help to route them appropriately. Inert materials can be set aside for construction uses in a mine, for instance for constructing roads, for back-filling that is needed to ensure the mine-stability, or for back-filling to allow the excavation of adjacent areas in the mine. Back-filling for the purpose of disposal on the other hand would fall under the disposal licensing requirement of the EWD (2006) and pertinent national legislation.

The EWD (2006) would permit the stockpiling of below-grade ore or processing residues with a specified view to (further) process them when favourable market conditions arrive. Of course, this stockpiling has to take place in dedicated and engineered facilities that prevent environmental impacts from erosion, dispersal, leaching, etc. Parbhakar-Fox & Baumgartner (2023) suggested to (re)assess (e.g. using hyperspectral scanning) these materials for metal-content and mineralogy before deposition and to (3D) map their exact location in block-models to facilitate later retrieval.

Likewise, potentially acid-generating materials identified, such as sulfidic minerals, can be routed right away for specific disposal locations or utilisation of e.g. sulfuric acid production needed as part of the milling process.

It is not unusual for a mining operation to cease rather abruptly due to unfavourable economic and market conditions, so there is a risk that such stockpiled materials will lack a final disposal solution at that moment. To prevent such 'orphan' mining legacies in case the operator ceases to exist, in the EU mining operations are required to build up a reserve fund in an escrow account that only becomes accessible to the mine operator, once the regulator has concluded that the operation and associated extractive waste management facilities have been closed to acceptable standards and any environmental impacts remediated as per the requirement of the EWD (2006).

It should be noted that such stockpiled but unused materials are likely to fall into the category of 'reactive waste' due to their ore content and, therefore, require disposal in a 'Class A' extractive waste management facility. This should be considered by any mining operation from the outset in order to avoid the surprise of high back-end disposal costs. Such considerations need to be part of the financial and economic risk assessment of a mine operation.

Figure 6.2. Conceptual decision tree for the valorisation of different types of extractive wastes (INTRAW).

Avoiding unwanted extraction and, hence, the unnecessary generation of extractive waste is one of the key objectives of PERSEPHONE. However, the generation of a certain quantity of below-grade ore and of gangue is operationally unavoidable, even with the low cross-section machinery under development in the project. Once excavated, the material will be sorted and routed accordingly, to processing, stockpiling, for construction, or disposal (in or outside the mine). Figure 6.2 provides a conceptual flow-diagram for the valorisation of the different types of wastes that will arise during extraction.

Processing waste typically arises in the form of 'tailings'. Processing begins with a physical disaggregation of the excavated material by breaking and grinding (comminution), which has the objective of increasing the surface area and

accessibility of minerals for the following wet processing. The grinding may also be followed by further sorting/concentration through e.g., flotation processes. Depending on the composition of the flotation residues, these will be either destined for further processing, stockpiling, or disposal. The ore concentrate then will be subject to the actual wet extraction process. The residues, the 'tailings', again would be subject to a triage, determining whether there is any (metal) value in them that warrants further processing or stockpiling. Otherwise, the tailings will have to be disposed of either in mined-out volumes of the mine or in a dedicated 'Class A' extractive waste disposal facility, a tailings pond. Tailings initially are difficult to manage materials owing to the high water-to-solid ratio and the uniform grain-size distribution that results in unfavourable geotechnical properties. Following numerous high-consequence failures of tailings-ponds up to the recent history, today mechanical dewatering and 'dry-stacking' of tailings is the preferred management option, albeit with additional energy expenditure.

In order to reduce the risks associated with tailings ponds, an international group of experts has developed a set of recommendations for their management (GTR, 2020), which was preceded by other initiatives to make large dams safer (ICOLD, 2013; 2011). The International Council on Mining and Metals produced its own recommendations (ICMM 2021a, b).

Due to their unfavourable geotechnical properties, if used for structural backfilling, tailings will need to be mixed with other aggregates and a suitable binder. In case of in-mine disposal, the addition of a binder probably will be sufficient. Apart from providing some structural stability to prevent outflowing, the binder also serves to reduce permeabilities and thus the percolation of groundwaters that may lead to the long-term leaching of constituents that have not been removed by the chemical processing. The binder also may buffer residual acid or alkalinity from the wet processing.

As noted above, careful mineralogical and geochemical assessment, if possible close to the mine face, is important to decide early on which material to excavate and where to route the excavated materials. The constantly updated forecasts allow for rapid adjustments of the mining and processing planning to ensure that sufficient capacities at all the routes, from processing to disposal are available. It also allows near real-time cost calculations and related forecasts of profitability, taking into account income from the primary resource and any by-products. Together with 3D-mapping of the disposal location a good knowledge of the properties of the disposed materials would make it easier to recover them, should this be deemed of commercial interest at some later stage.

Another obstacle to overcome more on the waste avoidance than on the waste re-utilisation side is, that in some jurisdictions mining permits are given in the sense that only the licensed target commodity may be extracted, and other constituents of interest have to become waste, unless the permit is amended. There is a certain logic in this, as the EIA would need to cover the extraction and processing of those additional constituents, which could have a rather different impact profile from the original commodity.

An issue that is actually beyond the remit of PERSEPHONE, but that is relevant in the context of mineral raw material stewardship, is the maintenance of databases

with data gathered during exploration and production and how to keep them accessible to possibly interested parties beyond the lifetime of the mining company. The majority of the data discussed above would be proprietary to the mining company and only a small selection of them may need to be submitted to the responsible geological surveys or the mining authorities. It would be helpful for the future if data on the content of extractive waste management facilities would be maintained independent of the continued existence of the respective mining company.

6.2 Internalisation of ESG requirements

6.2.1 What are ESG requirements?

Environmental, Social and Governance requirements are borne out of the need to address issues around risks, impacts, expectations and company behaviour in the context of any extractive operation. In other words, it revolves around how companies go about addressing environmental and socio-economic risks and how these risks shape the extraction strategy and processes in all relevant dimensions. In order to define such requirements, it is necessary to define the system boundaries and to specify for what purpose these requirements are formulated. From a project perspective, the ESG requirements can be used to assess and mitigate any risks that may adversely affect project implementation. On the other hand, projects may need to be assessed with respect to their sustainability in a wider sense in order to justify, whether to ahead with it at all or in the chosen form. Of course, the two aspects are linked and are built on the same set of data and information. A difficulty arises from the fact that ‘sustainability’ is an only a loosely defined concept and may be used and interpreted differently by different stakeholders. While in PERSEPHONE we are concerned about the overall ‘sustainability’ of the novel extraction methods as such, we want to give practitioners a tool that can help them to assess the potential impacts and risks of their projects and thus to identify possible mitigation strategies. This in turn will provide project promoters with arguments in any sustainability debate that may arise from the project.

Over the past decades a large body of literature on ESG requirements and how to implement them in extraction projects has been accumulated. The importance of ESG aspects for the successful implementation of extraction projects has been acknowledged by including them into the resources and reserves reporting processes for investors (see. Ch. 5). The viability of extraction projects is assessed on the basis of reporting standards, such as CRIRSCO (2024) or UNFC (2021). In the first instance, these describe a mineral occurrence from its geological perspective and the mineability from a mining engineering perspective with a view to provide investors with decision-making information. However, a range of so-called ‘modifying factors’ are introduced that describe the context of a potential extractive operation, which may help or hinder its implementation.

For the (self)assessment of operations with respect to their sustainability and with a view to disclose such information in annual reports to the public together with financial and social responsibility reporting various standards have been

developed (e.g. those by the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board) (SASB, 2024).

The **societal dimension** is complex and is illustrated by societal discourses around new mining projects in Europe in particular. It is therefore important not only to enter into a societal dialogue with the local communities but to also enable these communities to shape the mining projects to some extent in a way that serves their needs and expectations, thus resulting in a win-win situation. This is in fact in line with the MIREU recommendations for obtaining social licensing for operation (SLO) in the mining industry (Tost et al., 2021). The recommendations for internalising societal aspects (Section 4.3) take account of this.

In the following Section 6.2.2 the environmental aspects are discussed in more detail. The need for taking ESG aspects into the (economic) equation of extractive operations has been pointed out *inter alia* by Falck (2016). The issues to consider with a view to avoid risks becoming issues for operators and investors has been nicely summed up by Steele-Schober et al. (2020):

1. *Not applying the same level of rigour to understanding ESG considerations as we do for other technical disciplines e.g., mine planning. Because Sustainability is not a clearly delineated discipline and has an inherently high level of uncertainty – much of which is qualitative, it has not always received the same focus and input as more quantitative disciplines, where we can get a number and know that it's right or wrong to fair, or at least quantifiable, level of certainty.*
2. *Historically, ESG has been seen as a separate section of a project, aimed at providing some qualitative risk input. The financial impacts of the ESG risks have not always been quantified and the information used to determine appropriate action.*
3. *Due to a lack of rigour or possible uncertainties, the tendency is to be overly optimistic regarding ESG risk impacts to balance out risk conservatism in other areas, providing a “more spread” picture. Belief in the Board Room and amongst experts from more quantitative disciplines that all ESG risks can be mitigated at the operational phase.*
4. *ESG issues are often only considered as qualitative risks for too long and therefore projects are unable to mitigate or implement change once these evolve from risks to issues.*
5. *In many cases, ESG risks become issues that are often project stoppers or significant erodes of value. Earlier and better understanding of the risk case reduces the chances of this occurring and allows for better up-front decisions to be made.*

6.2.2 Environmental and operational safety & health risks

6.2.2.1 Risk categories

Basis for following discussions of risk assessment are the *Guidelines for Risk Assessment in the Extractive Industries* recently developed on behalf of the European Commission's DG ENV (Eco-Efficiency, 2023). These guidelines include a comprehensive catalogue of environmental and OSH risks. Pertinent EU regulations and directives (cf. Section 3.3) were also taken into consideration. The

cited Guidelines cover four main Focus Areas (FAs) that reflect the life cycles of extractive operations:

- FA1 – Exploration
- FA2 – Project development
- FA3.1 – Surface extraction
- FA3.2 – Underground extraction
- FA3.3 – Processing
- FA4 – Closure, remediation and long-term management

Of these, the Focus Areas FA1, FA2, FA 3.2, and FA3.3 are of particular relevance in the context of PERSEPHONE. Only a short overview of the potential environmental and OSH risks encountered can be given below and the reader is referred to the comprehensive treatment of the subject in Eco-Efficiency (2023).

The exploration phase often is also the first moment, when a potential future project comes into contact with the local population. The exploration crew, therefore, needs to be prepared to enter into meaningful interaction with stakeholders in order to prepare the ground for a relationship built on trust (cf. Tost et al., 2021), eventually leading to a ‘social license to operate’ (SLO) as an expression of good governance.

Figure 6.3. Source – pathway – receptor model in risk assessment.

A key conceptual approach in all risk assessment is the ‘source – pathway – receptor’ paradigm (Figure 6.3), or in other words:

What is the cause of the risk? – How can it cause harm? – Who or what can be affected?

Risk management can address any of the three elements, but the preference is for treating the source, then if the first is not feasible, the pathway. Removing receptors, for instance, preventing the access of the public to zones (potentially) at risk, typically is the last resort. However, (temporary) receptor removal is a typical risk management method in a technical context by e.g. limiting the amount of time an employee can spend in higher risk parts of a plant, fencing off certain areas, guard rails, etc. The discussions in the following section can all be conceptually seen in this way.

6.2.2.2 Exploration-related risks

Exploration activities have specific environmental and operational health & safety (OHS) risks associated with them, but at the same time allow to establish the baseline for environmental impact assessments (EIAs) and for planning the future

safe operation of combined extraction. Exploration activities may include the following:

- Remote / desktop studies prior to entering the field to undertake exploration.
- Planning for field operations with minimal impacts and environmental risks in view.
- Mapping and collection of exploration datasets without removing samples for analysis (including geological mapping, geophysical surveys, and any environmental or socio-economic baseline studies that can be undertaken at this stage).
- Collection of samples in the field for chemical analysis (including geological, mineralogical, and geochemical sampling).
- Invasive (explosive seismic) or non-invasive (hammer seismic, geoelectric, geomagnetic, geotelluric, etc.) geophysical surveys.
- Exploration drilling and sampling (via a variety of drilling techniques, incl. borehole geophysics).
- Drafting of the mineral and energy resource and reserve disclosure statement (in line with e.g. PERC (PERC-Standard, 2024), UNFC, 2021), and/or other applicable Codes and Standards) with respect to ESG requirements.
- Closure and remediation of the Exploration site(s).

Perhaps the most invasive operation during exploration is the drilling of boreholes. As boreholes are likely to be very deep, they will pass through various aquifers, which entails the risk of hydraulic short-circuiting and cross-contamination, if not carried out with the necessary care. Drilling sites also need to be made safe, so that any spilled drilling fluids, potentially contaminated waters, or drill-chippings can be contained and eventually removed for safe disposal, if needed. The preparation of the drilling-site itself may impact the local flora and fauna and the soil properties. Drilling operations are often noisy and may disturb local fauna as well as people nearby. The construction of access roads and the use of public roads for the transportation of materials and equipment will have further impacts to consider.

Similar considerations apply to reservoir seismic exploration, where also disturbance by blasting or vibro-seismic vehicles may be an issue. Particular care must be exercised in vulnerable and low-metabolism regions, such as the arctic, alpine, or semi-arid regions, where self-healing of damages to ecosystems will take a very long time.

Exploration will feed into an assessment of resources and reserves compliant with CRIRSCO-aligned standards, PERC for Europe, and/or UNFC. As will be discussed in more detail below, this kind of resource classification will also consider potential environmental and societal impacts as well as the governance context of any future exploitation project in form of so-called modifying factors. This means in practice, that the respective potential life-cycle risks for an extractive project should be outlined at this moment.

6.2.2.3 *Project development*

While the project development activities *per se* are not likely to entail any environmental or OSH impacts, their outcomes may well do. Planning for the

whole life cycle of the envisaged extractive operation is important in order to reduce its potential impacts in the ESG space. Such planning will encompass in the present the construction of the various extraction- and injection wells, the siting and construction of the industrial facilities, namely the power-plant and the plant for the extraction of the metal value including a storage area for reactants and products, management options for extractive and processing wastes, transport routes for reactants and products, etc.

The drilling of the various wells will give rise to a small amount of extractive waste, which will need to be managed according to the requirements of the Extractive Waste Directive (EWD, 2006). Any inert components of these wastes probably can be re-used on-site for construction purposes. Project development will include the permitting application procedures, as these will be iterative with more detailed planning. At this moment also the final EIA will be developed together with the mitigation plans for any risks and impacts potentially arising.

OHS risks during plant construction are akin to those of other drilling operations and construction sites and the respective safety at the workplace regulations will apply (cf. the Directives 89/391/EEC (CEU, 1989) and 92/91/EEC (CEU, 1992)). Interactions with (local) stakeholders will continue from the exploration phase, as stakeholder concerns may influence the design and mode of operation of the extractive operation.

One aspect during construction *in situ*-leaching facilities that may attract particular attention from the public are measures to increase the permeability and reactive surfaces down-hole, also known as 'fracking'. Such measures consist of pumping fluids at high pressure into the boreholes with a view to opening up fractures and other discontinuities. The fractures etc. are kept open by pumping sand or zirconium spheres into the voids thus created. This technique is/was regularly used by the hydrocarbon industry to increase yield. Public concerns arose due to the use of flow-improving surfactants and the seismic activity caused or triggered. There is a risk of seismic events due to the disturbance of the rock-stresses at depth by the 'fracking' process. Modelling of rock-stress changes may need to be foreseen to predict and control seismic activity.

It is always necessary to make preliminary plans for closure, decommissioning, and long-term management of any extractive waste facilities constructed in particular. Ideally, the mine should also be integrated into the socio-economic fabric of the region.

6.2.2.4 Deep mining

The selection of the mining method is governed by the geometry of e.g. the ore body, the structural setting and geomechanical properties of the host and surrounding rock, and the scale of operations. An underground extractive operation may potentially alter the properties, features and functions of an area below and above ground compared to the pre-extraction situation. Some of the alterations are permanent, whilst others are (partially) reversible. The PERSEPHONE underground extraction operations are generally characterised by the extraction and transport of relatively smaller volumes of material, the exposure of potentially harmful elements to environmental agents, the generation

of smaller volumes of extractive waste, and a much smaller environmental footprint compared to that of conventional extraction operations. Despite continuous and significant improvement in safety performance, underground extractive operations remain a highly hazardous working environment that continues to pose a risk to occupational safety and health. Extractive companies are required to conduct their operations so that they do not pose risks to public and worker health and safety, infrastructure, land, property and the environment for which PERSEPHONE will provide solutions.

The environmental and OSH risks associated with the development and operation of an underground extraction operation are complex. Based on EU and national legislation, as well as additional industry guidance, companies, academia and industry partners continue to develop improved means of analysing and managing environmental risks. In the area of OSH, EU Directives as well as relevant guidance such as the "Guidance on risk assessment at work" (COM, 1996) are available. Good practice underground extraction operations demonstrate that they fully understand the physical and social environment that they are operating in and have clearly identified and understood all potential risks posed by their operation through a robust risk assessment and management process.

It is not attempted to identify and prioritise all risks or provide comprehensive information on risk treatments and controls, as these are relative to the context of each operation.

Understanding and consideration of the context within which the underground extractive operation is undertaken is necessary to define the limits, or in risk management terms, the appetite and tolerance, within which environmental risks must be managed. Conversely, in the area of OSH, all risks for the safety and health of workers have to be prevented or minimised and workers have to be protected from them according to EU OSH legislation and guidance from EU-OSHA or similar national OSH organisations.

The context determines the scope of an operation's Environmental and OSH Management Systems. When implementing operational context and objective-setting processes, it is important that the external environment and stakeholders continue to be considered.

The context of underground mining operations includes the natural, built, social, business, and operational environment within which it is undertaken. This environment will influence operations to varying degrees, and in turn, the operation will potentially impact upon components of the environment. Key drivers of environmental and OSH risks associated with underground operations include the physical and chemical properties of the materials being extracted, groundwater features and conditions, mining methods used, the proximity of sensitive environments and communities, host-country laws and regulations and the organisational culture of companies.

Environmental context and sustainable objective setting for an underground operation are initially undertaken as part of the Project Feasibility Study (PFS) and Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA). However, the context of an operation is by its very nature, dynamic. Over time, the physical landscape is transformed, the geochemical characteristics of extracted materials will be

altered, the social, political and economic landscape may vary, improved monitoring and control processes and technology are developed, and environmental, human health and resource models are refined as more monitoring data gathered from the operational environment are introduced, all of which influence the context of an operation. On commencement, where significant change is planned or occurs, and throughout the life of an operation, it is good practice to periodically review the context of the operation to identify those changes that may influence environmental and OSH risks and how they are managed and monitored. This in turn may lead to updates on the UNFC classification (see below).

Prior to conducting a risk assessment, it is important to formulate the scope and objectives of the assessment. The selection of the appropriate risk identification tool is based on the scope of the risk assessment. For environmental risk assessment, Mishra & Rinne (2014) provide an example of a structured approach to the design of the scope and objectives for Geotechnical Risk Assessment (GRA) for underground mines.

In the area of OSH as concerns extractive operations, the Framework Directive 89/391/EEC (CEU, 1989) and Directives 92/91/EEC (CEU, 1992a) and 92/104/EEC (CEU, 1992b) and apply as well as other related OSH Directives. The main legal obligations of employers are stipulated in Articles 5 – 12 of Directive 89/391/EEC. In general, the employer has the duty to ensure the safety and health of workers in every aspect related to the work.

In the first instance, safe management routes for extractive residues will depend on the contents of certain elements or compounds, such as heavy metals, radionuclides, arsenic etc., for which no further use or recycling routes are foreseen. Some of these materials may be used on-site for further construction purposes. Compared to other types of extractive operations these quantities will be comparatively smaller with the new techniques proposed by PERSEPHONE. It should be noted that an extractive operation, regardless of technique used may generate other types of waste, not originating in the material extracted, but tools and machines as well as the processing routes used.

6.2.2.5 Processing

This term refers to any process that improves the economic value of the target commodity by separating the waste (gangue) materials from the target commodity, resulting in a higher-value product and an extractive waste stream (tailings). The scales and methods of processing are highly variable across the mining sector and are dependent upon the characteristics of the parent material and the requirements for marketable products. Processing methods and the infrastructure requirements to support processing are determined and designed during the project feasibility, planning and design phases. Whilst today's extractives sectors are governed by comprehensive EU and Member States legislation and international and national standards with respect to environmental, OSH performance, many of the negative societal and environmental impacts associated with processing operations can be avoided or minimised if they are operated according to leading practices.

Constructed and commissioned processing facilities are intended to provide for the (environmentally and operationally) safe, reliable and cost-effective extraction of the target commodities for the approved life of the mine. Key attributes of conventional processing operations often include:

- Continuous high demand and consumption of raw material inputs such as energy, water, and reagents/chemicals/fuels.
- Continuous and relatively high volumes of air/water emissions and waste material outputs.
- A continuous source of a complex range of environmental, safety and health hazards.
- Public health and environmental impacts have the potential to extend beyond the operational site boundaries and in some cases national boundaries within the EU and globally.

By bringing as much of these processes underground as possible some of the above issues can be addressed.

The high consumption of ancillary raw material, limited capacities of reliable utilities, such as electricity, gas and water, outside of cities, and supply and logistics constraints at more remote locations, may require mineral processing to be self-sufficient for the supply of certain resources. Thus, mines and processing operations may include self-generation of electricity or steam and the manufacture of critical reagents and chemicals, such as sulfuric acid or slaked lime. These process-supporting operations may be a significant source of environmental and OSH risk and be considered major hazard facilities in their own right.

6.2.2.6 Closure, decommissioning and after-care

Once the mine has reached the end of its useful life due to the exhaustion of target minerals, it will need to be closed in an orderly fashion. This may include a slow re-establishment of the original hydraulic regime if the extraction operation resulted in any such change.

Upon closure, structures above and below ground need to be decommissioned so that they do not constitute any long-term risks and cause impacts. Once the mine-head installations have been removed, shafts need to be capped to prevent foreign items from entering them and causing contamination or people or livestock falling into them. Installations and structures above ground will need to be dismantled if no further use for them is foreseen. Any contamination in the ground from spills etc. will need to be removed and the site remediated, if necessary. Unless there is contamination by heavy metals or radionuclides, it can be foreseen that most materials can be directed to recycling.

Any extractive waste facility constructed during the operation needs to be closed and made long-term stable, if not designed in this way already. Respective guidance can be found in MWEI-BREF (2018).

6.2.3 Guidance on the internalisation process

6.2.3.1 Overview

Based on the work outlined above, a scheme for the internalisation of ESG requirements has been developed, to be implemented through a checklist to accompany the development of the extraction sites. The checklist takes prospective operators through several steps that help them identify ESG risks along the life cycle of a facility. The operators are thus enabled to address these potential ESG risks before they become active risks. The checklist also helps to inform discussions with regulators and other (e.g. civil society) stakeholders.

This checklist consists of two parts, namely on a comprehensive project description that is based on the CRIRSCO reporting template (CRIRSCO, 2019; SAMESEG, 2017) and on the extensive risk catalogue that was developed in the context of drafting the Guidelines for Risk Assessment in the Extractive Industries (Eco-Efficiency, 2023). This risk catalogue focuses on the environmental and OHS risks and less on societal or governance issues.

6.2.3.2 Comprehensive project description

The SAMESEG guidance intends to support ‘competent persons’, i.e. professionals with relevant (risk) knowledge, rather than potential project developers. Thus, the SAMESEG guidance is written very much from the investors’ needs perspective and, therefore, needed to be reformulated to cover ESG issues from a more general environmental and social sustainability or strategic impact perspective (Table 6.1).

Table 6.1. ESG checklist, adapted from SAMESEG (2017).

GENERAL
1. Provide a description of organisational structure, systems, policies, procedures and management plans, and governance procedures in place to manage ESG issues.
Key plans, maps and diagrams
1. Provide a map which identifies the locality of sensitive receptors to be included on maps within the project area and at least the zone of influence of the site. All surface water features to be included on maps.
2. Identify and describe the location of any sensitive areas within and around the project area and within the zone of influence of the site.
Legal aspects
1. Outline the applicable ESG legal compliance requirements and any mandatory and/or voluntary standards or guidelines to which the project will (have to) subscribe.
2. Identify the ESG permits, authorisations and licences that will be required. Assess whether there is a reasonable basis to believe that all ESG permits, authorisations and licences can be obtained.
3. In case of an already existing mine, provide a description of any pending administrative enforcement action such as but not limited to directives or compliance notices instituted against the operation, including a notice received by the operator of an authority’s intention to issue a directive or compliance notice, by any authority concerned with the regulation of ESG issues whether or not such pre-compliance notice or compliance notice has been suspended pending corrective action.
4. Provide a description of any known future financial liabilities that arise by virtue of recognised claims, penalties, fines, damages and administrative enforcement action that will become due and payable in future.
Environmental parameters

1. Provide an appropriate analysis of the environmental context within which the project is located (or provide the contents of the mandatory EIA). Give an appropriate analysis of the material aspects and impacts that may need consideration including how existing activities may exacerbate or mitigate existing aspects and impacts.
2. Describe, assess and prioritise the risks associated with any obvious environmental factors that may require modifications to the planned extraction project. Focus on issues that are likely to remain significant despite the implementation of proven and economically viable mitigation measures.
External societal and political parameters
1. Provide an appropriate analysis of the external societal and political context within which the project is located.
2. Describe and prioritise current societal and political risks, and potential risks that take into account how activities may exacerbate or mitigate existing risks.
3. Describe any societal and political issues that may have a material effect on the planned project. Include issues that are likely to remain material despite the implementation of proposed mitigation measures.
Internal social parameters
1. Describe and assess the risks associated with any obvious internal social factors and/or specific contextual details that could have a material effect on the planned project.
Conformance and compliance audits
1. Provide a description of legal compliance audits undertaken, including a summary of material findings and management plans to address these findings.
2. Provide a description of ESG management system conformance audits undertaken, including a summary of material findings and management plans to address these findings.
ESG liability
1. Describe the closure, social obligations, rehabilitation plan, activities, remaining liability and compliance costs.
2. Provide a description of mechanisms in place to address unplanned closure.
3. Describe the bonding obligations in place to ensure that these liabilities can be funded on a qualitative and quantitative basis.
Risk analysis
1. Provide a description of the existence of a risk assessment process which has been undertaken to identify material ESG issues. Describe programmes in place to monitor identified material ESG issues.
2. Describe how the risk assessment process is integrated with the overall risk management framework.

6.2.3.3 Risk catalogues

The lists of potential risks below attempt to be fairly comprehensive. This does not mean that all these risks would be relevant for a given extraction operation at the same time. The list mainly serves a means to create awareness of potential risks and as a checklist during project planning. A considerable number of the risks listed are not specific to extractive operations but would be associated with the various life-cycle phases of any industrial operation, such as chemical processing plants for instance.

The risks are organised by life-cycle phase and environmental compartment or other type of receptor potentially affected. This way of organisation means, that certain types of risks, for instance air emissions, reappear in different categories. It would have been also possible to organise this list by type of risk and then list their possible causes. However, the chosen structure allows to attribute risks more clearly to root-causes in each life-cycle phase for which different control measures might be appropriate. Such root-causes should be addressed during the project planning phase.

In the specific context of the PERSEPHONE project, the risk catalogues (Table 6.2) can also be used to demonstrate to stakeholders, where the chosen technologies help to reduce mining-related risks at root. When using the PERSEPHONE-technologies in existing or in abandoned mines, many of the key planning decisions obviously have already been taken.

Table 6.2: Catalogue of risks to be considered during ESG and OSH assessments.

Exploration		
	Risk category	Impact
Exploration geologist in the field	Walking on the ground	Disturbance of plant cover and wildlife
	Stream sampling	Turbidity disturbing aquatic life
	Stranger (s) in the area	Inquietude and apprehension among locals
Airborne geophysics	Helicopters and drones	Hovering/low altitude flight disturb wildlife
		Inquietude and apprehension among locals
Ground-based geophysics	Vibro seismic trails	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations
	Explosive seismics	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles and explosions
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations and explosions
		Accidental damage to buildings (windows)
		Contamination from spilled drilling fluids
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
		Risk from storage and handling of explosives
		Wildfire risk from explosions
		OSH risks from operating heavy machinery
	Core drilling	Severe disturbance of plant cover and wild-life due to heavy vehicles and explosions
		Disturbance of locals by vibrations and explosions
		Contamination from spilled drilling fluids and chips
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment
Short-circuiting and cross-contamination between aquifers due to inadequate lining and sealing between aquifers upon completion		
Penetration of surface contamination into unsealed boreholes		
OSH risks from operating heavy machinery		
Transport of equipment and samples	Road vehicles	Road accidents, also involving locals
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids in the environment off-road and during maintenance in the field
		Loss of life due to accidents
	Helicopters	Crashes with loss of life
		Environmental contamination due to crashes
		Wild-fires due to crashes
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids when maintained in the field

Planning		
	Risk category	Impact
Strategic planning	Site selection	Location of surface facilities can cause more or less disturbances to the natural environment or human settlements
		Habitat fragmentation by surface installations and extractive waste management facilities
		Cumulative impacts from several mining and other industrial facilities

Construction of shafts and surface facilities		
	Risk category	Impact
Site preparation	Removal of vegetation cover	OSH risks associated with vegetation clearance
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids from logging and brush cutting equipment

		Disruption and displacement of wildlife
		Accidental killing of wildlife
		Noise disturbance of locals
	Operation of earth-moving plant	Disturbance of plant cover and wildlife
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids from plant
		OSH of equipment operators
		OSH of on-site staff
		Increased surface erosion and stream turbidity
		Dust generation and off-site dispersal
		Accidents due to operator error
	Off-site transport	Road accidents involving lorries
		Accidents during transport of heavy plant
		Lost loads
	Buildings construction	OSH of crane operation
OSH of scaffolding work		
OSH of stationary equipment (circular saws, mixers, rammers, ...)		
Dropping hazards (tools and materials form overhead)		
Dust and fibres from building materials (on-site and off-site)		
Shaft preparation	Drilling	Noise and vibration
		Dust generation
		Spilling of drilling fluids
		OSH of drilling equipment operation
	Water	Contamination of water-bearing strata
		Draw-down of groundwater levels
		Cross-contamination of aquifers
	Gas	Radon-release from open boreholes

Extraction and Processing		
	Risk category	Impact
Extraction	Operation	Accidental spills of processing fluids in plant
		Chemical spills during processing fluid preparation
		OSH of plant operation
		Kinetic energy including dropped objects and falls from height
		Failure of pressurised vessels and hot piping
	Water	Accidental discharges of contaminated fluids
		Failure of pipes and tanks
		Failure of decant water treatment systems
		Regional water stress due to extraction of process water
	Air	Olfactory nuisances off-site
Biological	Biohazards e.g. from bacteria used in advanced processing techniques	
Radiation	Naturally occurring radioactive minerals (NORM)	
Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations	
Products	Chemical	Hazardous impurities
		Hazardous processing agent residues
By-products	Radiation	NORM in products
	Chemical	Hazardous impurities
Wastes	Chemical	Hazardous processing agent residues
		NORM in by-products
	Radiation	NORM in wastes

Waste Management		
	Risk category	Impact
On-site materials movement	Operation	OSH risks due to earth-moving plant
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids from equipment
		Dust generation due to vehicle movement
		Spills due to failure of tailings pumping systems
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations

Extractive and production waste management facilities	Geotechnical	Dam stability
		Hydraulic heave at toe
		Slipping of dam
		Slumping slopes
		Internal erosion (suffusion, piping)
		Failure of liner
		Failure of cover (e.g. hydraulic heave)
	Water	Erosion (general)
		Failure of drainage and diversion systems
		Acid Rock Drainage (ARD) generation
		Failure of drainage and seepage water treatment systems
	Air	Surface water turbidity due to erosion
		Dust generation from uncovered facilities
Radiation	Radon releases	
Vegetation	Failure of re-vegetation	

Closure and Decommissioning		
	Risk category	Impact
Site abandonment	Operational	Collapse of built structures due to lack of maintenance
	Water	ARD in surface and groundwaters
		Turbidity in surface due to unmaintained covers
	Air	Dust generation due to unmaintained covers
		Methane release due to failing covers
	Radiation	Radon release due to failing covers
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
Public safety		Failure of access prevention (collapse of fences)
		Falls into uncovered wells
Decommissioning	Operational	Uncontrolled access to hazardous substances (reagents)
		OSH of dismantling and demolition activities
		OSH of plant and machinery operation
		OSH of site staff
		Exposure to hazardous substances in buildings
		Noise and vibration from demolition activities
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids to the environment
		Loss of hazardous materials from structures being dismantled
		Kinetic energy including dropped objects and falls from height
		Accidents during on-site transport of materials
	Water	Short-circuiting between aquifers due to changing hydraulic regime
		Leaching of alien substances during hydraulic re-equilibration
		Release of hazardous substances during demolition and dismantling
		Loss of oils and hydraulic fluids to groundwaters
	Air	Dust exposure of workers
		Off-site dust from demolition activities
		Release of hazardous minerals (asbestos, silica, ...)
		Dust generation from e.g. crushing of concrete
	Noise	Dust releases before covers and re-vegetation becomes effective
		Off-site noise and vibration due to demolition and dismantling activities
	Electrical	Shock due to damaged electrical installations
	Transport	Accidents during off-site removal of materials for recycling or re-use
		Release of hazardous substances during transport to off-site disposal
	Societal	Nuisance of demolition activities

Remediation		
	Risk category	Impact
Wells	Water	Residual lixiviants that cannot be removed by pump-and-treat
		Short-circuiting between aquifers
Extractive and production waste management facilities	Operational	Human intrusion (e.g. extraction of aggregates)
		Unsuitable redevelopment (e.g. foundations in covers)
	Geotechnical	Long-term stability of dams
		Hydraulic heave at dam toe
		Retrograde dam erosion due to overtopping
	Failure of capping due to uneven dewatering	

		Erosion of capping
		Long-term frost resistance of covers
		Long-term functioning of covers
		Loss of stability of covers due to bioturbation (burrowing animals, plant roots)
	Water	ARD formation
		Failure/silting up of surface water diversions
		Failure of toe drainage
		Seepage due to failure of liners
		Release of contaminants into the aqueous environment
	Air	Turbidity in surface waters due to erosion
		Radon leakage into buildings on-site or into the surrounding environment
Dust due to eroding covers		
Recultivation	Failure of re-vegetation efforts on waste facilities	
External risks	Natural hazards	Collapses due to earthquakes (slopes and dams)
		Changing climatic boundary conditions (e.g. amount and intensity of precipitation)

The waste-management, closure, decommissioning, and remediation steps are not within the scope of PERSEPHONE as such, but the techniques being developed in the project, will help to alleviate some of the issues often associated with these steps. For instance, more targeted extraction means less waste to manage on the surface and, hence, smaller and thus easier to manage facilities with less impact and eventually less effort during closure and a possible remediation phase. After having gone through both steps, the prospective operator should have a comprehensive overview over the potential ESG issues the operation may face.

6.2.3.4 Sustainability reporting

As noted above, extractive operations are now generally expected to not only provide financial and corporate responsibility reports, but to also report on the sustainability aspects. Various reporting standards have been developed over time and here the one by Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB, 2024) for 'Metals & Mining' (SASB-Standards, 2024) is outlined, which will be helpful as guidance (Table 6.3).

Table 6.3. Topics covered by the 'Metals & Mining' sustainability accounting standard by SASB (SASB-Standards, 2024).

TOPIC	METRIC	CATEGORY	UNIT
Air Quality	Air emissions of the following pollutants: (1) CO, (2) NO _x (excluding N ₂ O), (3) SO _x , (4) particulate matter (PM ₁₀), (5) mercury (Hg), (6) lead (Pb), and (7) volatile organic compounds (VOCs)	Quantitative	t
Waste & Hazardous Materials Management	Total weight of non-mineral waste generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of tailings produced	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of waste rock generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of hazardous waste generated	Quantitative	t
	Total weight of hazardous waste recycled	Quantitative	t
	Number of significant incidents associated with hazardous materials and waste management	Quantitative	Number
	Description of waste and hazardous materials management policies and procedures for active and inactive operations	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Biodiversity Impacts	Description of environmental management policies and practices for active sites	Discussion and Analysis	n/a

	Percentage of mine sites where acid rock drainage is: (1) predicted to occur, (2) actively mitigated, and (3) under treatment or remediation	Quantitative	%
	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near sites with protected conservation status or endangered species habitat	Quantitative	%
Security, Human Rights & Rights of Indigenous Peoples	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near areas of conflict	Quantitative	%
	Percentage of (1) proved and (2) probable reserves in or near indigenous land	Quantitative	%
	Discussion of engagement processes and due diligence practices with respect to human rights, indigenous rights, and operation in areas of conflict	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Community Relations	Discussion of process to manage risks and opportunities associated with community rights and interests	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	(1) Number and (2) duration of non-technical delays	Quantitative	No., Days
Labour Practices	Percentage of active workforce employed covered under collective bargaining agreements	Quantitative	%
	(1) Number and (2) duration of strikes and lockouts	Quantitative	No., Days
Workforce Health & Safety	(1) OHS all-incidence rate, (2) fatality rate, (3) near miss frequency rate (NMFR) and (4) average hours of health, safety, and emergency response training for (a) direct full-time employees and (b) contract employees	Quantitative	Rate
Business Ethics & Transparency	Description of the management system for the prevention of corruption and bribery throughout the value chain	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
Tailings Storage Facilities Management	Tailings storage facility inventory table: (1) facility name, (2) location, (3) ownership status, (4) operational status, (5) construction method, (6) maximum permitted storage capacity, (7) current amounts of tailings stored, (8) consequence classification, (9) date of most recent independent technical review, (10) material findings, (11) mitigation measures, (12) site-specific EPRP	Quantitative	Various
	Summary of tailings management systems and governance structure used to monitor and maintain the stability of tailings storage facilities	Discussion and Analysis	n/a
	Approach to development of Emergency Preparedness and Response Plans (EPRPs) for tailings storage facilities	Discussion and Analysis	n/a

It should be noted that that the SASB standards presented in Table 6.3 are designed to be applicable world-wide and some elements may not be relevant in a European context, while for instance OHS-related aspects are covered by the respective directives and regulations of the European Commission, e.g., Directives 89/391/EEC, 92/91/EEC, and 92/104/EEC, as well as Regulations (EC) Nos. 1272/2008 (CLP) and 1907/2006 (REACH).

6.2.3.5 Relationship to Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)

The environmental and sustainability aspects will be also informed by the EIA that is certainly required as part of the permitting procedure. These, together with the

site-specific risk catalogues will shape the narratives to address any SLO issues as part of addressing the societal and governance aspects. The weight to be given to each issue will depend on the outcomes of the stakeholder interaction processes. However, the key messages to stakeholder are likely that the overall environmental impacts and nuisances during the operational phase are likely to be small.

From an overall sustainability and hence environmental point of view the key message is also likely that the CO₂-footprint and the amount of embedded carbon will be small in comparison to other extraction techniques.

6.3 Proposal for a UNFC/UNRMS/CRIRSCO-compliant assessment

6.3.1 Overview

A variety of stakeholders have a vested interest in accurate data on the occurrence and availability of mineral resources. Governments need such information for strategic decision- and policy-making. Investors, who fund extraction need to base their decisions on reliable data on the likely viability of projects. However, not only data on the physical presence of mineral resources are of importance, but also information on their extractability and any circumstances that may pose an obstacle to their extraction. The dimension of time also plays a role, as in the early phases of a potential project the level of knowledge of the mineral occurrence is low and exploration activities aim to decrease the level of uncertainty for the data users and, hence, increase the level of knowledge and confidence. It is therefore essential that the industry communicates the risks associated with investment effectively and transparently in order to earn the level of trust necessary to underpin its activities.

It is clear, that the information needs of governments and industry/investors are somewhat different. On the other hand, as mineral resources extraction and use are a global business, an alignment of the way how resources are assessed and reported was desirable, both from a business as well as a strategic planning perspective.

6.3.2 Industry resource reporting – CRIRSCO-aligned codes

The Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards (CRIRSCO, 2024), which was formed in 1994 under the auspices of the then Council of Mining and Metallurgical Institutes (CMMI), is a grouping of representatives of organisations that are responsible for developing mineral reporting codes and guidelines in Australasia (JORC), Brazil (CBRR), Canada (CIM), Chile (National Committee), Colombia (CCRR), Europe (PERC), India (NACRI), Indonesia (KOMBERS _ KCMI), Kazakhstan (KAZRC), Mongolia (MPIGM), Russia (NAEN), South Africa (SAMREC), Turkey (UMREK) and the USA (SME). The combined value of mining companies listed on the stock exchanges of these countries accounts for more than 80% of the listed capital of the mining industry.

Figure 6.4. Mineral resources and reserves according to CRIRSCO.

The international initiative to standardise market-related reporting definitions for mineral resources and mineral reserves had its start at the 15th CMMI Congress at Sun City, South Africa in 1994. The mineral definitions working group (later called CRIRSCO) was formed after a meeting at that Congress with the primary objective of developing a set of international standard definitions for the reporting of mineral resources and mineral reserves. Figure 6.4 illustrates the classification of mineral resources and reserves according to the increasing level of confidence as exploration and exploitation progresses.

The similarity of the various national reporting codes and guidelines has enabled CRIRSCO to develop an International Minerals Reporting Code Template (CRIRSCO, 2019). This can act as a "core code and guidelines" for any country wishing to adopt its own CRIRSCO-style reporting standard, after including provisions for country-specific requirements such as those of a legal and investment regulatory nature. Following discussions over a number of years, CRIRSCO published Standard Definitions in October 2012. These fifteen definitions have been incorporated in International Reporting Template of CRIRSCO dated November 2013 and in the Codes and Standards of most of the CRIRSCO Members in their own updates.

Accordingly, The Pan European Reserves and Resources Reporting Committee (PERC-Standard, 2024) developed for Europe a Standard for Reporting of Exploration Results, Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves, which sets out the minimum standards, additional guidelines and recommendations for the Public Reporting of Exploration Results (including Exploration Targets), Mineral Resources and Mineral Reserves.

A key aspect that determines whether a mineral occurrence can become a viable extraction project are the so-called 'Modifying Factors' (CRIRSCO, 2012) that include, but are not restricted to, mining, processing, metallurgical, infrastructure, economic, marketing, legal, environmental, social and governmental factors. In other words, they are concerned with internalisation of ESG aspect discussed above.

6.3.3 United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC)

The United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC, 2021), in its core principles, encompasses a tool for the comprehensive management of all

socio-economical, technological and uncertainty aspects of energy and mineral projects. The project maturity and resource progression model of UNFC can de-risk projects from costly failures and thus protect the investments. UNFC fully integrates social and environmental considerations and technology readiness required.

UNFC aims to provide clear and consistent specifications, guidelines and best practices for all energy and mineral sectors, which are of particular importance for the management of expanding demand of bioenergy, geothermal energy, solar energy, wind energy and hydropower resources.

To help the application of UNFC uniformly worldwide, guidelines on requirements for competency of the personnel are included in the system. UNFC provides case studies and implementation examples, not only to improve the consistencies in the usage but also to enhance the system through innovative applications. Sustainable management of energy and raw material resources in a rapidly changing global economic landscape requires accurate mapping of supply and demand. The recoverable resources available on our planet need coherent and consistent definition and categorisation at global, regional, national and local levels.

UNFC is a principles-based system in which a resource project is classified on the basis of three fundamental criteria (UNECE, 2021):

- environmental-socio-economic viability (E),
- technical feasibility (F), and
- degree of confidence in the estimate (G),

using a numerical coding system. Combinations of these criteria create a three-dimensional system (Figure 6.5). Categories (e.g. E1, E2, E3) and, in some cases, Sub-categories (e.g. E1.1) are defined for each of the three criteria.

Figure 6.5. UNFC Categories and Example of Classes.

The first set of Categories (the **E Axis**) designates the degree of favourability of environmental-socio-economic and governance (ESG) conditions in establishing the viability of the project, including consideration of market prices and relevant legal, regulatory, social, environmental, and contractual conditions.

The second set (the **F Axis**) designates the maturity of technology, studies, and commitments necessary to implement the project. These projects range from early conceptual studies through to a fully developed project that is producing and reflects standard value-chain management principles.

The third set of categories (the **G Axis**) designates the degree of confidence in the estimate of the quantities of products from the project.

The Categories and Sub-categories are the building blocks of the system and are combined in the form of “Classes”. UNFC can be visualised in three dimensions, as shown in Figure 6.5 or represented in practical two-dimensional abbreviated versions.

For more details, the reader should consult the *Supplementary Specifications for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources to Minerals* (UNECE, 2021). Also of interest are the guidelines for the extraction of uranium (UNECE, 2017) in particular the section on extraction by *in situ*-leaching (ISL). ISL could be envisaged as method of recovery of metal value, integrating both, excavation and processing, into a single step.

It needs to be kept in mind, that the UNFC in the first instance was developed to assess (and manage) resources on a country level with a view to make policy- or strategic decisions and not to manage particular projects with respect to financial decisions. On the other hand, CRIRSCO-aligned assessments and classifications concern specific projects, and can be “translated” (and incorporated) into UNFC using a so-called ‘bridging document’ (UNECE, 2015) was developed early on (Figure 6.6) and is currently being revised.

CRIRSCO Template		UNFC-2009 “minimum” Categories			UNFC-2009 Class
Mineral Reserve	Proved	E1	F1	G1	Commercial Projects
	Probable			G2	
Mineral Resource	Measured	E2	F2	G1	Potentially Commercial Projects
	Indicated			G2	
	Inferred			G3	
Exploration Results		E3	F3	G4	Exploration Projects

Figure 6.6. Simplified Mapping of CRIRSCO Template to UNFC-2009 Classes and Categories (from UNECE, 2019).

The revised version of the Bridging Document (CRIRSCO & UNECE, 2024) explains the purposes of both, the CRIRSCO Template and the UNFC: “The CRIRSCO Template aligned reporting codes and standards focus on the detailed requirements for market-listed mineral companies to substantiate the conclusions of their activities transparently regarding the reporting of volumes of mineralised material on a mineral asset(s) owned by a minerals company, with the prime objective of supporting exchange regulation and avoiding market abuse. UNFC provides a logical framework for the comparison of the estimated mineral products that may be derived from an entire mineral project in terms of aggregated estimate quantities, the maturity and feasibility, the degree of technical environmental-socio-economic viability and the level of confidence in those assessments.”

The European Commission has been advocating the use of UNFC in resource-related projects *inter alia* to make classifications compatible with the Raw Materials Information System (RMIS, 2024) developed by the Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC). This caused some concern in the industry, who normally used CRIRSCO-aligned reporting standards and feared a double burden of having to report to governments also using UNFC. Under these circumstances, a certain competition between the systems was perceived, although ‘bridging’ documents had already been developed.

An expert roundtable was organised by INTRAW on 24 January 2023 in collaboration with the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) and the Pan-European Reserves and Resources Reporting Committee (PERC), and it brought together a small group of invited experts to discuss how to reinforce data confidence and transparency in assessments of mineral resources. The experts noted that the UNFC provides a broader high-level overview of potential opportunities, while CRIRSCO-aligned reporting provides a selective perspective of mineral endowments as only ‘viable’ projects are effectively reported. Participants agreed that the UNFC is well tailored for resource inventories, since it encompasses all (‘viable’ and ‘unviable’) deposits / projects.

6.3.4 The United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS)

The United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS) (UNECE, 2019) provides countries, companies, financial institutions and other stakeholders a tool for sustainable development of energy and mineral resource endowments with the framework of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG, 2024a). The UNRMS applies to energy resources including oil and gas, renewable energy, nuclear energy, minerals, injection projects for the geological storage of CO₂, groundwater, and anthropogenic resources, such as secondary resources recycled from residues and wastes.

Thus, the UNRMS is designed to be a:

- Global voluntary system for resource management to be used by governments, industry, investors, and civil society.
- Innovative integrated resource management framework for resources such as minerals, petroleum, renewable energy sources, nuclear resources, anthropogenic resources, geological storage and groundwater to support the

development of policies and regulations in the sustainable management and advancement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

- Comprehensive information framework and methodology to support resource progression applicable for programme, portfolio, project and asset-level management.
- Sustainability framework to aid the financing of resource sectors.
- System for local and indigenous communities for evaluating and assessing projects against stated environmental-social-economic objectives.
- Scheme for long-term considerations of commercial and policy aspects of projects.
- Design of conditions for the industry to harness the integrative dynamic capabilities.
- Support kit for projects to help align with applicable regulations.
- Instrument to support sustainability and financial reporting.

The emerging challenges in these sectors are the sustainable, environmental-friendly, carbon neutral and efficient development, production of energy and raw materials required for a growing population. Innovations in production, consumption and transportation are fundamentally challenging how energy and material sectors function today. As a unique tool for harmonising policy framework, government oversight, industry business process and efficient capital allocation, UNFC is designed for managing the natural resources required for the present and future needs of society and realising the objectives of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG, 2024b).

6.3.5 Decision-making in a UNFC evaluation

The Supplementary Specifications for the application of UNFC to Geothermal Energy Resources (UNECE, 2022a) propose a detailed decision-making tree for each of the 'axes' during the evaluation of resources (Figure 6.7 - 6.9). As the decisions depend on each 'product', i.e. each extracted commodity, it may need to be repeated for each of them (see EGRM, 2024). These decision trees serve as illustrative examples of a structured decision-making approach using UNFC.

For each of the three axes (E, F and G), a separate decision tree is provided. By following the arrows from decision box to decision box, the user will end up in a box giving the most suitable classification at the highest hierarchical level for the given axis.

- 'End boxes' have a green colour fill. In some cases, the end box is red, suggesting that there may be insufficient information to classify the Project.
- The arrows connecting the boxes are coloured: red represents the direction for decision NO; green represents the direction for decision YES; with a blue arrow, no decision has to be made (passing information only).
- For the E Axis, a loop is introduced because there is potentially a suite of issues pertaining to the 'license to operate' in the environmental, social, economic, legal, etc. domains, which need to be resolved. There will usually be multiple contingencies and the overall project E-classification should be that of the lowest ranking one.

Project activities as used in the F-axis classification definitions are related to the ‘technical’ evaluations that are performed and documented. These technical studies include:

- (a) Geological studies,
- (b) Geophysical studies,
- (c) Geochemical studies,
- (d) Geomechanical studies,
- (e) Subsurface modelling studies,
- (f) Surface equipment/infrastructure studies,
- (g) Siting/logistics.

The studies with the lowest maturity define the final score. While in principle the evaluation according to UNFC needs to be carried out for each target commodity separately, there will be many common elements along the decision trees (Figure 6.7 to 6.9).

E – axis decision tree

Figure 6.7. UNFC E-axis decision-making tree (UNECE, 2022a).

6.3.6 Application of UNFC to PERSEPHONE-type projects

6.3.6.1 *Setting the Scene*

The UNFC (and similarly CRIRSCO-aligned assessment) follow a set of procedures and the 'Qualified Expert' (or 'Competent Person' in CRIRSCO) is a key element in the associated Quality Assurance process. The task of the 'Qualified Expert' is to estimate the available resources following a campaign of exploration or after certain phases of exploitation and to draw scientifically and technically founded conclusions from this. These conclusions are made publicly available and are the basis for informed decision-making by different stakeholders, ensuring transparency and reliability in resource evaluations. However, there is typically a delay of several month to a year between, the collection of the assessment data and the final publication of the Competent Person's report. Particularly, in the case of operating mines, in this way the report may be considerably out of step with the reality in the mine. This increases the risk and uncertainty for investment decision makers. One of the objectives of PERSEPHONE as a whole is to generate data that better reflect the real-time situation when exploring or exploiting a resource.

The PERSEPHONE data collection is built around a constantly updated model of the mineral occurrence or mine. These updates are provided by at-the-face sensors continuously, which allows to periodically update the model in short intervals. This continuous updating in turn allows to update in near real-time the resources and reserves classifications as per Figure 6.5, as the level of confidence in the geological assessment (G-axis, cf. Figure 6.5) is increased. Additionally, as also mineralogical and geotechnical data in 3D-space are collected, the confidence in the assessment of the technical feasibility (F-axis) is increased.

Another section will explore how the system of 'Qualified Expert', which is at the core of the UNFC can be adapted to the much more rapid process offered by PERSEPHONE.

6.3.6.2 *Review of current UNFC-guidance with respect to PERSEPHONE*

As noted previously, the resource/reserve evaluation according to UNFC assumes implicitly a sequential process that terminates with a signed report by the 'Qualified Expert'. In contrast, the PERSEPHONE processes aim to provide a near real-time updating of the resource and reserve estimations (cf. Figure 6.4). The trust in the UNFC and the CRIRSCO-aligned processes hinges on the reliability and accountability of the 'Qualified Expert'. This important aspect has to be maintained to make the PERSEPHONE process acceptable to the financial world.

It can be assumed that deploying the PERSEPHONE techniques will not alter the classification along the E-axis beyond the original assessment (e.g. EIA) for new mines, in which the respective mining techniques would have been considered already. In the context of enlarging existing mines and re-opening abandoned mines, the situation can be different. The down-mine exploration and more targeted extraction will change the environmental impact of the mine and, hence, probably also the attitude of the public towards it. However, such change will probably only occur once and not periodically. For this reason, one can assume

that the E-axis classification remains stable for the duration of either the project as a whole or for at least large parts of the life cycle.

Likewise, it is probable that the F-axis classification will not change unless very different mineralogical and/or geotechnical conditions are encountered as mining progresses. Such changes are likely to occur on a timescale of several years, rather than months unless the geology in a mine is very variable.

To the contrary, the G-axis assessment could change much more frequently, as new exploration and production data become available. The discussion, therefore, focuses on the G-axis (cf. Table 6.4).

The *Supplementary Specifications for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources to Minerals* (UNECE, 2021) have been reviewed with respect to which extent they cover already the mining methods proposed by PERSEPHONE in Appendix 2.

6.3.6.3 *Quality Control and Quality Assurance*

Reliable and consistent data (estimates of quantities, classification, and aggregation) are required for robust decision making. It is therefore essential that an appropriate quality control processes are in place.

Both UNFC and CRIRSCO are relying on the professional qualifications of individuals that have been assured by relevant documentation and registration with a professional body.

Thus UNFC (UNECE, 2022b) specifies that “[t]he *Qualified Experts* must be accountable for the quality of their work and guidance is provided in the Section “Practical Guidance in Applying UNFC for Primary and Secondary Raw Materials in Europe,”. The regional or national bodies which receive the data and may choose to regulate the requirements should assure themselves that these processes are applicable and have been applied.

A review process can be extremely helpful in establishing and maintaining consistency, while identifying and resolving issues. This can readily be implemented within a preparer’s organization. Whilst more difficult to implement, it can also be extremely helpful to introduce reviews across organizations (e.g., at the national and regional level where data is received) and to bring in external reviewers, to share experience and achieve a greater consistency.” Any updates to the G-axis based on data collected in near real-time, therefore, must be signed off by a ‘Qualified Expert’.

6.3.6.4 *Implications of the Bridging Document (CRIRSCO & UNECE, 2024)*

For the further exploration at face in existing mines it is very likely that the E- and F-axes of UNFC will not be affected. The technologies under development in PERSEPHONE will only affect the G-axis classifications. On the other hand, when exploring closed mines with a view of re-opening, as new permits will be required, the whole spectrum of UNFC will be relevant. In order to attract new investment, reporting under both, CRIRSCO and UNFC may be needed, so that looking at their concordance is important.

Table 6.5. Specification of the UNFC G axis and corresponding CRIRSCO Template considerations (CRIRSCO & UNECE, 2024)

<i>UNFC G axis: Degree of Confidence (based on UNECE, 2021)</i>			<i>CRIRSCO considerations</i>
<i>Category</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Supporting explanation</i>	<i>Resource/Reserve confidence categories</i>
G1	Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a high level of confidence.		Corresponds with a Measured Resource or Proved Reserve category of confidence.
G2	Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a moderate level of confidence.	Product quantity estimates may be categorized discretely as G1, G2 and/or G3 (along with the appropriate E and F Categories), based on the degree of confidence in the estimates (high, moderate, and low confidence, respectively) based on direct evidence.	Corresponds with an Indicated Resource or Probable Reserve category of confidence.
G3	Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a low level of confidence.		Corresponds with an Inferred Resource category of confidence.
G4	Product quantity associated with a Prospective Project, estimated primarily on indirect evidence.	<p>A Prospective Project is one where the existence of a developable product is based primarily on indirect evidence and has not yet been confirmed. Further data acquisition and evaluation would be required for confirmation.</p> <p>Where a single estimate is provided, it should be the expected outcome but, where possible, a full range of uncertainty should be calculated for the prospective project.</p> <p>In addition, it is recommended that the chance of success (probability) that the prospective project will progress to a Viable Project is assessed and documented.</p>	<p>Corresponds with the CRIRSCO Exploration Target which is a statement or estimate of exploration potential for a mineral deposit where there has been insufficient exploration to estimate Mineral Resources.</p> <p>Exploration Targets must be expressed as a range of quantity and quality.</p>

6.3.6.5 Summary observations

Summarising the insights above, one may conclude, that the current UNFC guidelines are sufficiently flexible to accommodate the quasi real-time updates as furnished by the PERSEPHONE down-mine techniques. In order to utilise the potential of these techniques for supplying up-to-date information for investors and capital allocators, a schedule of more frequent reporting and the necessary administrative procedures have to be put into place, than the usual yearly reports. The basic procedures do not change, but only the frequency with which the reports are updated.

A set of decision-making trees like that of the Supplementary Specifications for the application of UNFC to Geothermal Energy Resources (UNECE, 2022a) would be helpful in particular for the G-axis assessments (c.f. Figure 6.9) and would need to include recursive loops for more frequent (more than yearly) review by the 'Qualified Expert'. Such a review could be restricted to the assessment, whether the data furnished by the PERSEPHONE techniques would warrant or require a change in the classification, assuming that all other variables remain the same.

7 Evaluation scenarios and benchmarking specifications

This section will aim to provide the technological roadmap for achieving the stated KPI (Key Performance Indicators) in the PERSEPHONE Specific Objectives. This will be done by providing an overview of the specific proposed technologies and research methodologies in the related PERSEPHONE tasks, and a following specification on how those technologies will be evaluated in the following areas:

- What are the test sites where evaluations will be performed or on which datasets?
- What testing, experimentation, or demonstration scenarios will be used to evaluate the proposed technologies?
- How do those evaluations relate to the project KPIs?
- Along the path to the project deliveries what are some benchmarks for the proposed novelties?

Rock Mass Preconditioning for reducing energy consumption of extractive processes

Evaluation scenario: Due to the low TRL of new preconditioning technologies developed under the PERSEPHONE project, the evaluation will be based on simulations and tests in laboratory conditions.

On the one hand, the evaluation will be based on the analysis of the extent and density of cracks generated by preconditioning. On the other hand, the resistance recorded during drilling will be analysed. By assumption, well-preconditioned rock should be easier to mine and it should be possible to achieve a similar result using less amount of explosives.

Way of technology benchmarking: Benchmark levels will depend on the evaluation method. In the case of evaluation based on numerical simulations, it is expected that:

- The length of cracks will increase by at least 5%.
- Cracks density will increase by at least 10%.

When assessing the difficulty of drilling, it is assumed that after preconditioning:

- The time of drilling a single hole will decrease by at least 10%.
- The amount of explosives needed for the excavation of a similar volume of rock will decrease by at least 5%.

Next Generation Deep Mineral Exploration Drilling Systems

Evaluation scenario: Due to the low TRL of technology and the preliminary state of its development it is assumed that evaluation scenarios will be rather qualitative than quantitative. The evaluation workflow is as follows:

- *CAD Design of manipulator and tools* - It is planned to use Computer-aided design (CAD) software to create detailed models of the manipulator and tools. Then based on simulation the most effective solution will be chosen.

- *Simulation in Gazebo - Virtual prototyping:* Implement the CAD models into Gazebo simulation environment to simulate drilling scenarios and validate systems performance. Again, the most efficient solution will be chosen based on simulation results.
- *Prototyping of drill tools to optimise design, functionality, and performance parameters* - Prototypes will be developed based on results from physical testing.
- *System integration of drill tools and robotic arms* - Mechanical integration, integrate drill tools and robotic arms mounted on robots to form a cohesive drilling system.
- *Ultimately validation of proposed approach will be performed in mock-up in laboratory environment.*

Way of technology benchmarking: The effectiveness of drilling will be evaluated using more than one mobile robot performing a drilling task. It is expected that within the PERSEPHONE project developed approach will allow to:

- Conduct successful validation of production face drilling of >15 meters. Validation will be performed for position accuracy and useability.
- Perform a comparative validation of extension drilling feed by multiple robotic systems.
- Successful implementation and validation of LIBS and MWD rock characterization is successfully validated in long hole drilling.
- Collection of drilling samples.
- Validation of an autonomous drill planning and precise drill arm manoeuvring with ≤ 250 mm accuracy.
- Successfully perform Multiple-holes drilling by the single drill rig in the lab mock-up.

Hole deviation monitoring system for long hole drilling as a blasting quality indicator

Evaluation scenario: Evaluation of proposed approach will be a continuous process including testing, validation and continuous system recalibration and development.

The proposed technology will be evaluated in the lab environment and in the Epiroc test mine. Evaluation will be:

- Qualitative - based on direct measurement of drilling accuracy,
- Quantitative – based on the determination of the possibility of risk reduction and control of planned outcome.

Way of technology benchmarking: A hole deviation monitoring system is expected to enable higher accuracy and control of the drilling process (with a real location of the drill hole of 0.6%). Which also enables increased control of the blasting outcome and fragmentation. The exact benchmarking parameters are as follows:

- Quality control of long hole drilling, +/- 0.6 % (+/- 0.3 m for a 50 m hole).
- Measuring speed 0.5 – 1.5 m/s (depending on mine conditions).

- Increased safety, less risk of hanging stopes.
- Increased control of planned outcome.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - LIBS slurry analyser

Evaluation scenario: The analytical performance of this technology will be best evaluated in a lab environment. When creating similar conditions as in a mining environment, various samples can be fed to the sensor and measured in as reproducible conditions as possible. After measurement, these samples can be thoroughly analysed by established lab techniques to determine their ‘true’ composition.

With a large enough dataset, a calibration model can be built which can be compared against established analytical results. This will finally produce qualitative numbers such as accuracy, detection limits and repeatability of the sensor. This method for calibration and evaluation is the standard procedure for most analytical techniques.

Other, more practical and qualitative evaluations will need to be performed in the mining environment. Preferably in the Epiroc test mine

Way of technology benchmarking: Referring to SO2 KPI 3: *LIBS and MWD rock characterization is successfully validated in long hole drilling*. The main benchmark for this technology will be to successfully validate the concept and proof the working principle preferably in a representative environment.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - LIBS mine-face scanning

Evaluation scenario: Evaluation of the technique is best done in a combination of lab and underground environment. Analytical parameters (accuracy, resolution) are difficult to determine in a mine and are therefore best studied in the lab. For this purpose a mock-up “mine face” can be constructed with materials of known composition.

After that the sensor can be evaluated underground. Either at the test site in Greece or the test mine of Epiroc. These evaluations should focus on proper functioning of the system. How autonomous is it? Does it survive real, underground conditions?

Way of technology benchmarking: The main benchmarks would be to validate if the sensor data can be actively used to update the digital twin. This would be in line with KPI3 of SO4. Does it reach the desired accuracy level such that it is useful for the digital twin? If this is possible within an underground environment without infrastructure it would also connect well with KPI2 of SO5.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - MWD and in-situ hardness test

Evaluation scenario: A reliable and real time rock characteristics obtained from MWD is critical in defining the geological features and ground condition. Based on the existing methods and tools, MWD data used for real time rock characterization in-situ rock hardness tool attached to the drill rig will be used for calibration of MWD results.

It is expected that quantitative evaluation will be performed in the field conditions. Lab tests might be used for the further validation of the field-based result.

Way of technology benchmarking: Measurements with the new MWD module will be carried out supported by parallel rock hardness measurements with a well-calibrated, in-situ rock hardness evaluation tool installed on a drilling rig. Additionally, rock samples will be tested in laboratory conditions.

The reliability of the newly developed solution will be determined based on the correlation coefficient achieved between the validated technology available on the market and the new MWD solution. A correlation level $r_{xy} > 0.8$ will indicate the reliability of the novel solution prototype.

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Multi-spectral down hole imager

Evaluation scenario: For deep hard to reach deposits, it is intended to focus on metallic ore vein type deposits (ex: sulphide-veins) where precise and automated mineralogy segmentations of the acquired image is the main output. The evaluation of the technology will be based by direct comparison acquisition made on relevant samples. Ground-truth data will be acquired using laboratory XRD, Raman and LIBS to produce reference segmented image with accurate mineralogy classification. A subset of this reference data will be used to train a multispectral image classification model and another subset of this reference data will be used to test the accuracy of the model (ex: % correctly classified pixels). The efficiency of the acquisition will also be evaluated in terms of resolution and speed (ex: mm/min - pixels/mm).

The target borehole diameter will be of PQ size (122mm diameter). The imaging device will scan the borehole inner surface and produce a multispectral image (range of 350 to 2500nm) in the shape of a cylinder or “virtual core” that will be segmented in mineral phase by a ML model pretrained on reference data. The technology will be evaluated in lab conditions (1-2m physical PQ borehole with simulated ore veins (from relevant real samples) reconstituted for repeatable testing.

Way of technology benchmarking: The system should have a spectral range of at least 350-2500 nm and be able to acquire image in a borehole of a typical PQ diameter. Accuracy in identifying the metallic mineral phases at least 90% in a lab setup. It should provide sub real-time feedback with an imaging time of less than 15 min/meter, which is the virtual core production rate.

These objectives are in line with the KPI 4 of SO2, and KPI 4 of S04

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Multi-spectral rock face imager

Evaluation scenario:

In the use case of the deep mine re-exploration, we propose to acquire and process rock face imagery to produce useful data for grade estimation in a relevant mining environment. The evaluation of the technology will be based by direct comparison with rock samples taken from the imaged surface. Ground-truth data will be acquired using laboratory XRF, XRD, wet chemistry analysis, and LIBS to produce reference segmented images with accurate mineralogy/geochemistry classification.

A subset of this reference data will be used to train a multispectral image classification model and another subset of this reference data will be used to test the accuracy of the model (ex: % correctly classified pixels in the case of a mineralogical classification, concentration accuracy in a case of a ore grade estimation.)

The efficiency of the acquisition will also be evaluated in terms of achieved resolution and speed. The technology will be evaluated in lab condition (reconstituted scene in small scale and on the field, acquisition/processing in underground mine environment.

Way of technology benchmarking:

The system should have a spectral range of at least 350-850 nm and be able to acquire multispectral image sequences in an automated way. The acquisition process should take less than 5min (including DUV exposure and processing). The main benchmarks would be to validate if the sensor data can be actively used to update the digital twin of the mining environment considered for use case 2.

These objectives are in line with KPI 4 of SO2, and KPI 5 of S04, *KPI 3 of S05 (if we have access to the magnesite mine, otherwise we can demonstrate it in an abandoned mine in Belgium)*

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Downhole electro(magnetic) measurement – ERT and IP

Evaluation scenario: The technology will be evaluated in a lab environment reproducing similar condition to the project's test site (KGHM mine). Samples from the test mines, and analogues, will be used for the laboratory test. On site testing (TRL-5) is envisioned to validate the lab results but only when developments have progressed sufficiently enough. We will use the data for real-time rock characterization and mapping.

The results will be evaluated qualitatively (depth of interpretation and map quality) and quantitatively (rock-measured electrical properties). Such type of techniques is needed to better identify geological features during the exploration and production phase.

Way of technology benchmarking:

High-resolution ERT-IP measurements should be demonstrated in lab set-up in conditions and on samples corresponding to use case #1.

ERT-IP measurement should:

- reach a decimetric (minimum) to pluri-centimetric (maximum) resolution.
- investigation depth will depend on the specific rock /mineral composition but should reach at least 10 cm.
- Each ERT-IP profile (one line) should be processed in less than 1 hour.
- The ERT-IP profile should successfully classify ore/waste boundaries within the sample with at least 15cm accuracy on known samples (synthetic prepared samples) and locate structural discontinuities with also 15cm accuracy.

These objectives are in line with the KPI 4 of SO2, and KPI 4 of S04

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Face-scanning electro(magnetic) measurement ERT-IP

Evaluation scenario: The technology will be evaluated in a lab environment reproducing similar condition to the project's test site (KGHM mine). Samples from the test mines, and analogues, will be used for the laboratory test. On site testing (TRL-5) is envisioned to validate the lab results but only when developments have progressed sufficiently enough. We will use the data for real-time rock characterization and mapping.

The results will be evaluated qualitatively (depth of interpretation and map quality) and quantitatively (rock measured electrical properties). Such type of techniques is needed to better identify geological features during the exploration and production phase.

Way of technology benchmarking:

High-resolution ERT-IP measurements should be demonstrated in lab set-up in conditions and on samples corresponding to use case #1.

ERT-IP measurement should:

- reach a decimetric (minimum) to pluri-centimetric (maximum) resolution, on a section of 25 cm to 1m.
- investigation depth will depend on the specific rock /minerals composition but should reach at least 5cm.
- Each ERT-IP profile (one line) should be processed in less than 30min.
- The ERT-IP profile should successfully classify ore/waste boundaries within the sample with at least 15cm accuracy on known samples (synthetic prepared samples) and locate structural discontinuities with also 15cm accuracy.

These objectives are in line with the KPI 4 of S02, and KPI 4 of S04

Real-time rock characterization and detection of rock mechanical and geophysical properties supported by advanced on-line analytics systems for planning and characterization of near-mine exploratory drilling - Acoustics

Evaluation scenario: The technology will be evaluated in a lab setup and on a rock face but not in a mining environment since the TRL is still low (TRL-2 to 3). Still these tests will be relevant for the project's test site (KHGM mine). Samples from the test mine will be used, as well as analogues from the partners core collections (historic deep exploration drillings in relevant environments). A test on a real rock face will be performed on a surface outcrop, with well-known structural characteristics.

Testing of the newly developed acoustic instrument will include:

- High-resolution measurements on a selection of drill cores. Characterization of the impact of fracture zones on acoustic speed.
- Field measurement on a selection of rock faces presenting joints/fault planes with or without alteration minerals.
- Creation of a "catalogue" of acoustics properties of relevant lithologies, including acoustic speeds range and anisotropic features.

Way of technology benchmarking: High-resolution acoustic measurements should be demonstrated in lab setup on relevant samples corresponding to use case #1. Minimum specification:

- 5 types of relevant rocks are acoustically characterized with the developed tools.
- 80% accuracy in differentiating between unfractured and fractured rocks in the laboratory test sets.
- Measured acoustic speeds absolute values (aggregated data) within 75% of the ground-truth data on core samples (acoustic logging reference measurements).

These objectives are in line with the KPI 4 of S02, and KPI 4 of S04.

Computer-aided planning of excavation in exceptional deposit conditions

Evaluation scenario for use case 1: A well-developed numerical model should enable making forecasts with appropriate accuracy. The criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of the new approach will be the comparison of data resulting

from simulations with data from in-situ measurements. The assessment may be based, for example, on measuring the convergence of workings or comparing stress distribution zones resulting from seismic measurements and those calculated using FEM. It is assumed that the use of data-driven estimation should ensure a better fit of the model to the observations than simulations based on lab tests.

Evaluation of the results of numerical modelling can be carried out in two ways.

- In a quantitative way, when specific values, e.g. displacements obtained as a result of calculations, are compared with in-situ measurements (Figure 7.1-left).
- In a qualitative way, when there are no direct measurements of stresses or displacements. Then you can compare, for example, places of seismic activity with places of stress concentration (Figure 7.1-right).

Figure 7.1. Examples of model validation in quantitative (left) and qualitative way (right)

Due to the lack of equipment, all data regarding rock strength, displacements and possible stresses must be collected using autonomous machines. Therefore, both the construction and validation of the model depend on the capabilities and accuracy of autonomous devices. Nevertheless, assuming that it is possible to obtain data for building and validating the model, ways of evaluating the results of the proposed approach can be determined. This time, as in the case of exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits, the assessment can be made both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Way of technology benchmarking for use case 1: It is assumed that data-driven numerical modelling should ensure a better match of simulation results to observations made in situ, compared to models based on data from laboratory tests. Given the complexity of the problem, it is impossible to determine the difference in % accuracy achieved with both approaches. However, the minimum fit of the model to the actual data can be determined. It is assumed that the model after validation should achieve a correlation $r_{xy} > 0.5$ compared to measurements performed in situ (in the case of stress and displacement measurements). In the case of qualitative analyses, it is assumed that stress zones should be more similar in location and shape to zones of e.g. seismic activity than in the case of simulations based on laboratory tests.

Evaluation scenario for use case 2: Due to the lack of equipment, all data regarding rock strength, displacements and possible stresses must be collected using autonomous machines. Therefore, both the construction and validation of the model depend on the capabilities and accuracy of autonomous devices. Nevertheless, assuming that it is possible to obtain data for building and validating the model, ways of evaluating the results of the proposed approach can be determined. This time, as in the case of exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits, the assessment can be made both quantitatively and qualitatively.

Way of technology benchmarking for use case 2: The benchmark of the proposed solution will be based on determining the size of the match between simulation data and observations conducted in situ. It is assumed that the results of data-driven simulations should be characterized by a better match to the values recorded in-situ, both in quantitative and qualitative terms. In the case of access to underground measurements, it is assumed that the correlation between observations and simulations should be $r_{xy} > 0.5$.

Autonomous Path Planning and Multi-Machine Coordination

Evaluation scenario: Methods efficacy will be evaluated against existing SoTA methods in high-fidelity simulation environment. Evaluation scenario will be repeated 10 times with same initial conditions for machines and 2 different sets of goal positions.

4 simulated mining machines designed in PERSEPHONE will be placed at the entrance to the mining simulation environment and will receive navigational goals.

The evaluation will be quantitative and compared against the ground truth data in terms of:

- Tunnel length coverage.
- The number of conflicts resolved.

Way of technology benchmarking:

- Validation of collaborative autonomous navigation capability in an environment of 2 m × 2 m pathways that are representative of abandoned mines with ground robots, in a mock-up mission scenario with at least 4 vehicles that target all the challenges of collaboration and risk identification related to deep subterranean environments.
- Validation in high fidelity simulation environment incorporating the full integration of sensor payloads and robotic autonomy to the full-scale mining vehicle concept developed in PERSEPHONE towards mock-up mission scenario for autonomous operations in tunnels of at least 5km long.

High-accuracy navigation and alignment for precise autonomous drilling & excavation operations

Evaluation scenario: Methods efficacy will be evaluated against existing SoTA methods in high-fidelity simulation environment. Evaluation scenario will be

repeated 10 times with same initial conditions for machines and 2 different sets of goal positions.

4 simulated mining machines designed in PERSEPHONE will be placed at the entrance to the mining simulation environment and will receive navigational goals.

The evaluation will be quantitative and compared against the ground truth data in terms of:

- Tunnel length coverage.
- Number of conflicts resolved.

Way of technology benchmarking:

- Validation of collaborative autonomous navigation capability in an environment of 2 m × 2 m pathways that are representative of abandoned mines with ground robots, in a mock-up mission scenario with at least 4 vehicles that target all the challenges of collaboration and risk identification related to deep subterranean environments.
- Validation in high fidelity simulation environment incorporating the full integration of sensor payloads and robotic autonomy to the full-scale mining vehicle concept developed in PERSEPHONE towards mock-up mission scenario for autonomous operations in tunnels of at least 5km long.

On-line Sensor-based Traversability and Risk Assessment

Evaluation scenario: Methods efficacy will be evaluated against existing SoTA methods in high-fidelity simulation environment. Evaluation scenario will be repeated 10 times with same initial conditions for machines and 2 different sets of goal positions.

4 simulated mining machines designed in PERSEPHONE will be placed at the entrance to the mining simulation environment and will receive navigational goals.

The evaluation will be quantitative and compared against the ground truth data in terms of:

- Tunnel length coverage.
- The number of conflicts resolved.

Way of technology benchmarking:

- Validation of collaborative autonomous navigation capability in an environment of 2 m × 2 m pathways that are representative of abandoned mines with ground robots, in a mock-up mission scenario with at least 4 vehicles that target all the challenges of collaboration and risk identification related to deep subterranean environments.
- Validation in high fidelity simulation environment incorporating the full integration of sensor payloads and robotic autonomy to the full-scale mining vehicle concept developed in PERSEPHONE towards mock-up

mission scenario for autonomous operations in tunnels of at least 5km long.

Multi-machine real-time and infrastructure free mapping and localization

Evaluation scenario: Methods efficacy will be evaluated against existing SoTA methods in high-fidelity simulation environment. Evaluation scenario will be repeated 10 times with same initial conditions for machines and 2 different sets of goal positions.

4 simulated mining machines designed in PERSEPHONE will be placed at the entrance to the mining simulation environment and will receive navigational goals.

Mesh network will be evaluated in the lab environment.

The evaluation will be quantitative and compared against the ground truth data in terms of:

- Tunnel length coverage.
- Number of conflicts resolved.

Way of technology benchmarking:

- Validation of collaborative autonomous navigation capability in an environment of 2 m × 2 m pathways that are representative of abandoned mines with ground robots, in a mock-up mission scenario with at least 4 vehicles that target all the challenges of collaboration and risk identification related to deep subterranean environments.
- Validation in high fidelity simulation environment incorporating the full integration of sensor payloads and robotic autonomy to the full-scale mining vehicle concept developed in PERSEPHONE towards mock-up mission scenario for autonomous operations in tunnels of at least 5km long.
- Validation of the mesh network connectivity with data exchange (up to 15Mbit/sec for WiFi and 1Kbit/sec for LoRa), and range test in the lab environment using main network quality metrics as RSSI and bitrate.

Autonomous Drill Planning and Execution from Onboard Sensing of the Rock Face Characteristics

Evaluation scenario: Methods efficacy will be evaluated against existing SoTA methods in high-fidelity simulation environment. Evaluation scenario will be repeated 10 times with same initial conditions for machine and same drill plan for 2 different mine faces.

Simulated mining machine designed in PERSEPHONE will be placed at the face of the mining simulation environment and will be commanded to perform an autonomous alignment and positioning according to the face drilling plan.

The evaluation will be quantitative and compared against the ground truth data.

Way of technology benchmarking:

- The precise alignment and navigation autonomy framework for face drilling will allow to locate machines with up to 30 cm error in XYZ.
- The drilling autonomy framework will validate the capability of autonomous drill planning and precise drilling with 5cm accuracy.
- High Fidelity simulations of the full integration of sensor payloads and robotic autonomy on the mining vehicle towards an as-realistic-as-possible full-mission scenario for autonomous alignment of a mining machine with a drill face in a simulated operation environment is demonstrated.
- 100% conflict/collision-free operation.

8 Data requirements for geomodel development

The advent of geomodelling in the mining industry marks a pivotal shift towards sustainable and efficient resource extraction. Geomodels, intricate digital representations of geological settings, serve not only as tools for exploration and mine planning but also as means to predict and manage environmental impacts. The development of these models, however, is contingent upon the availability, accuracy, and comprehensiveness of geological data. This section outlines the critical role of data in geomodel development, focusing on the objectives and expectations within the framework of the PERSEPHONE project, a collaborative effort involving two partner mines.

The success of geomodels hinges on the foundational layer of high-quality, comprehensive data. By setting clear objectives for data collection and utilization, the PERSEPHONE project aims to advance the capabilities of geomodelling, thereby enhancing the sustainability, safety, and efficiency of mining operations. This collaborative effort is expected to yield significant improvements in how geological data is harnessed for environmental planning and operational decision-making in the mining industry.

8.1 Evaluation of geomodelling techniques in relation to digital twin standards

A digital twin embodies a detailed virtual representation of a physical, manufactured entity, emphasizing a gap when considering the naturally occurring geological systems (Nagovitsyn & Stepacheva, 2021). This delineation necessitates a thorough examination of the capabilities and methodologies behind geological sampling and modelling, contrasting these with engineered models to ascertain their potential for digital twinning.

The inherent characteristics of geological formations—described as Discontinuous, Inhomogeneous, Anisotropic, and Non-elastic (DIANE)—present specific hurdles in the accurate simulation and modelling efforts, diverging significantly from the more predictable properties of engineered materials (Hodgkinson & Elmoultie, 2020). Critical mining operations tasks, such as the assessment of slope stability or the optimization of drilling and blasting practices, depend heavily on a precise understanding of these geological discontinuities through data sources like drilling logs, remote sensing technologies, and geochemical surveying.

Building a geomodel entail navigating data that spans a spectrum of resolutions, format, each demanding a degree of interpretation and processing. An example of common input data is listed in Table 8.1. This introduces a layer of uncertainty and inconsistency, especially when interpreting interval data, trends, and generating three-dimensional models. While emerging techniques in data science, including machine learning and self-organizing maps (SOM), offer pathways to enhance the interpretative quality of geological data and merge disparate data types, they have yet to fully conquer the inherent uncertainties to form a comprehensive digital twin of geological reality.

Table 8.1. Typical geological data and potential to support a digital geological twin.

Typical Input Data and Methods	Value	Improvement Potential	Potential to Support a Digital Geological Twin
Non-geophysical drill hole data	Establishes spatially known points	Enhances with increased density and core recovery	Currently impractical for desired high resolutions
Down-hole logging data	Provides detailed geological insights	Limited by drill hole density; reliant on interpolation	Restricted data collection and incorporation
Geological maps (surface/outcrops)	Offers direct in-field information	Potential improvement with better surface-to-subsurface connectivity	High surface definition potential: subsurface definitions may lack
Geophysics—regional and cross-hole	Broad-scale geological information	Improved with more surveys; limited by interpretation requirements	Volumetric sampling limitations
Lithological and geochemistry data	Point-specific lithological insights	Improves with more data points and detailed analysis	Sparse prior to full rock mass excavation
Stratigraphic modelling outputs	Merges direct and indirect geological data	Enhanced with increased data integrity and density	Direct information remains sparse until the excavation
Structural modelling outputs	Informs on rock mass structures	Improves with more data and detailed geophysical analysis	Precise for large structures; mine-scale detail impractical until excavation
Hydrogeological data	Direct and indirect water-related insights	Improved with more frequent water level observations	Challenging at mine scale during or post-mining

The challenges in refining geological models stem from both the cognitive reliance on expert judgment, addressing the so-called epistemic uncertainties, and the technological difficulties presented by the geological complexity. Current computational methods, despite their advancement, still grapple with limitations regarding the dynamic, multidimensional nature of geological processes.

Efforts to mitigate stochastic uncertainties through advanced geostatistical techniques are making headway. Nonetheless, their capability to accurately forecast low probability but impactful geological events remain inadequate for the predictive accuracy required by a digital twin. Innovations aiming at real-time model refinement, utilizing sensory data for continual updates, seek to elevate geological models' precision, especially in addressing underground stability and other geotechnical concerns.

Thus, while geological models remain foundational to the strategic and operational planning of mines, their current form and the nature of their foundational data limit their capacity to fulfil the real-time, predictive criteria of digital twins. This highlights an ongoing need for innovation in both technology

and modelling methodologies to close the gap between the existing state of geological modelling and the idealised standards of digital twin technology.

The digital twin environment, as defined by Hodgkinson and Elmouttie (2020), is described as a "multi-domain physics application space dedicated to the functioning of digital twins," which could include, for instance, the processing systems or other engineering aspects of mining. Such an environment necessitates the integration of geological data or a complete geological model of the area surrounding the mining digital twin. This integration is crucial for forecasting the future behaviour and performance of the system. However, unlike the digital representation of an engineered system, which can be precisely known, measured, and duplicated in a digital format, a geomodel represents only an interpretation of the underlying geology. It's important to note that incorporating geological data into a process-oriented digital twin does not equate to creating a geological digital twin itself.

8.2 Challenges and Limitations

The intricacies of geomodelling in the mining industry encompass a broad spectrum of challenges and limitations, directly influencing the efficacy and reliability of geomodels.

a) Data Quality and Availability

A fundamental issue within geomodelling is the quality, completeness, and consistency of geological data. These aspects are crucial for the development of reliable models, yet they often fall short due to insufficient data gathering and processing methodologies. The impact of data quality on model reliability cannot be overstated, as inaccuracies or gaps in data can lead to significant misinterpretations of the geological setting.

b) Integration of Diverse Data Types

Another pressing challenge is the integration of heterogeneous data types, including spatial, temporal, and qualitative data, sourced from a variety of origins. The ability to synthesize these disparate data streams into a unified and coherent model is often hampered by inconsistencies and the complex nature of geological information, complicating the geo-modelling process further.

c) Software Limitations

The limitations presented by geo-modelling software also pose considerable challenges. These limitations encompass scalability issues, a lack of flexibility, and restricted interoperability with other tools and systems. Such constraints can stifle the development and refinement of geomodels, impeding their ability to accurately represent subsurface conditions.

d) Skills Gap

The geo-modelling field also grapples with a notable skills gap, characterized by a shortage of professional adept in leveraging advanced geo-modelling tools and interpreting intricate geological data. This gap underscores the need for enhanced training and education within the industry to equip practitioners with the necessary skills to address the complex demands of geo-modelling.

e) Regulatory and Environmental Considerations

Lastly, the regulatory and environmental landscape presents its own set of challenges. Geo-modelling practices must navigate this landscape effectively, ensuring that models not only comply with regulatory requirements but also thoroughly consider environmental and social impacts. This necessitates a balanced approach to model development, one that aligns with both industry standards and broader societal expectations.

8.3 PERSEPHONE Project Data

8.3.1 Data Inventory

For the PERSEPHONE project, geomodels will be constructed using existing data from partner mines, which will be enhanced with new data from project-specific technologies. The accompanying table (Table 8.2) lists the standard data sets used for geomodel development in mining. Datasets marked as 'Essential' are the minimum required from project partners for accurate geomodelling and are integral to meeting both the project's objectives and UNFC standards.

Table 8.2. List of standard data sets used for geomodel development

Dataset	Data	Format	Requires spatial coordinates	UNFC Requirement	Digital Twin Development	Description
Geological Database	Drill hole data	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Records from drilling operations detailing subsurface geology
	Sample data	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Analyses of physical samples taken from surface or rock face
	Lithology/ Rock Type	Table	Yes	Yes	Essential	Classification of rocks based on their physical and chemical composition
	Alteration	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Classification of the alteration in the rocks
	Mineralogy	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Study of minerals within the geological samples
	Assay (Composition)	Table	Yes	Essential	Essential	Chemical composition of selected target elements
	Structure	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Geological features such as faults and folds
	Geotechnical /rockmass	Table	Yes	Yes	Yes	Mechanical properties and behaviour of the rock mass
Geological model	Lithology	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Essential	3D representation of different rock types
	Alteration	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Yes	3D representation of different alteration types
	Structure	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Essential	3D visualization of geological structures
	Grade	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Essential	Essential	Distribution of ore grade within the rock mass
	Geotechnical	Surface/Wireframe	Integrated	Yes	Yes	3D model of geotechnical properties
Resource model	Grade/Ore body	Shells/Block	Integrated	Essential	Essential	3D volumes representing the concentration and distribution of ore
	Estimation parameters	Table	Integrated	Essential	Yes	Data used to estimate the quantity and quality of the resource
Geophysical Data	Surface seismic/ Magnetic/ IP data	3D visualizations/ Maps	Yes	Yes	Yes	Geophysical measurements done in surface
	Downhole geophysics	Table/sections	Yes	Yes	Yes	Geophysical measurements done post-drilling
Infrastructure	Topography (LIDAR)	3D models/ Point clouds	Yes	No for deep UG mine)	No for deep UG mine)	Topographic data for detailed surface mapping
	Mine workings	3D/Map	Yes	Yes	Essential	Layout and design of the mine's physical structure

Environmental and Social Data	Environmental Impact Assessments	Reports/ Maps	For monitoring	Essential	Yes	Studies on the potential environmental impacts of mining operations
	Social Impact Assessments	Reports/ Maps	For monitoring	Essential	Yes	Studies on the potential social impacts, including community engagement
	Hydrological Data	Maps/ Models	Yes	Yes	Yes	Data on water flow and distribution within the mine area
	Environmental Monitoring	Table/ Database	Yes	Yes	Yes	Real-time data on environmental conditions impacting mining operations
Mine Planning	Mine schedule	Gantt Charts/ Tables		Yes	Yes	Detailed plan for mining operations over time
	Future works	Project management tools		Yes	Yes	Projections for future expansions and development activities
	Logistics Data	Supply Chain Management System		Yes	Yes	Information on the transportation and logistics of materials and resources
Geometallurgical Data	Metallurgical characteristics	Table/ Graphs/ Models	Yes, if not composited	Essential	Yes	Information on the variability in comminution and metallurgical response of the ore across the deposit
	Recovery rates	Table/ Graphs	Yes, if not composited	Essential	Yes	Expected recovery percentages based on processing methods
	Liberation characteristics	Table/ Graphs/ Models	Yes, if not composited	Yes	Yes	Expected liberation of the ore
	Comminution/ Separation parameters	Table/ Graphs		Yes	Yes	Comminution and separation units' parameters utilised for separating the ore and waste
Mine Operational Data	Production data	Table/ Real-time stream		Yes	Yes	Data related to the quantity and rate of ore extraction
	Ore flow diagrams	Diagrams/ Models		Yes	Yes	Detailed diagrams showing the flow of material through the various stages of mining
	Equipment performance	Table/ Logs		Yes	Yes	Records and analyses of mining equipment efficiency and maintenance
	Storage	Database/ Inventory system		Yes	Yes	Information on the storage capacity and inventory management
Processing Data	Process flow diagrams	Diagrams/ Models		Yes	Yes	Detailed diagrams showing the flow of material through the

						various stages of the processing plant and equipment units (including parameters)
	Tailings characteristics	Table/ Reports		Yes	Yes	Characteristics of tailings, including potential recoveries and environmental considerations
	Plant performance data	Table/ Real-time stream		Yes	Yes	Real-time data on processing plant operations, such as throughput and recovery

8.3.2 Data Accessibility and Quality Assessment

After establishing a thorough data inventory, the subsequent focus is on ensuring the accessibility and quality of the data. This involves a rigorous assessment process where the existing datasets undergo evaluation for their accuracy, completeness, and consistency. Data accessibility refers to the ease with which data can be retrieved and utilised effectively in the geomodelling process. It's vital that project partners have systems in place that allow for the seamless sharing and integration of data.

8.3.3 Data Generation Plans

The future data generation strategy for geomodelling will leverage advanced sensing and measurement techniques to enhance the accuracy and resolution of the geomodels. We plan to integrate a suite of technology, each contributing unique data on rock properties and composition as listed in Table 8.3.

Table 8.3. Description of the technologies to be developed in the PERSEPHONE project, their measured properties, related geo-model properties, limitations, and possible sampling strategies

Technology/sensor	Description	Measured property	Related geo-model property	Limitations	Sampling strategy
Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS)	Utilises a high-powered laser to vaporize a small part of the sample and analyses the emitted light spectrum to identify elemental composition.	Composition	Direct: Grade Indirect: Mineralogy/ Lithology/ Alteration	Calibration with standards is required; laser safety precautions needed; accuracy may be affected by sample homogeneity.	Face scanning, analysis of drill chips/ slurries
Multi-spectral camera	Captures image data at specific frequencies across the electromagnetic spectrum to infer the composition.	Composition (spectral range 350-2500 nm)	Direct: Potential for grade estimation Indirect: Mineralogy/ Lithology/ Alteration	Dependent on lighting conditions; requires direct exposure to the target surface for accurate readings.	Downhole logging or from the mine face during mapping or surveying

Electro (magnetic) measurement	Employs electrical and magnetic fields to determine the subsurface geological structure and rock properties.	Rock mechanical properties (resistivity, conductivity, induced polarization)	Indirect: Mineralogy (for sulfides)	Depth penetration may be limited; influenced by adjacent strata and requires interpretation.	Downhole logging or direct from the face
Acoustics	Utilises sound waves to analyse rock properties, including density and elastic constants.	Rock mechanical properties (acoustic velocity, attenuation)	Indirect: Structure	Requires coupling with the rock; affected by noise and rock heterogeneity.	Downhole logging or from the mine face during mapping or surveying
MWD Real-time rock characterization	Measures while drilling, using the response of drilling machinery to infer rock properties.	Drilling parameters (pressures, speed, etc.)	Indirect: Structure (Relative hardness and fractures)	Indirect method: correlation with actual rock properties needed; influenced by drill bit wear and drilling conditions.	Downhole during drilling operations
On-rig in Situ hardness measurement tool	Directly measures the hardness of the rock face or drill cuttings using a specialised tool mounted on the rig.	Absolute Hardness	Calibration for MWD	Measurement may not represent conditions below the surface; requires contact with the rock; influenced by surface conditions.	At the face, typically post-drilling and pre-blasting

8.3.4 Integration with Existing Data

The essence of dynamic geomodelling within the PERSEPHONE project lies in the ability of existing models to incorporate and adapt to new data. For this to be effective, the models must be inherently flexible, allowing for the integration of new data, particularly those concerning specific measured properties and related geomodel properties indicated in Table 8.3, it is critical to establish a direct correlation between these elements.

Furthermore, to ensure the validity and reliability of the data derived from these advanced technologies, it will be corroborated against ground truth data obtained from lab-based analytical methods (in case of composition).

9 Summary and conclusions

The increased demand for raw materials in the EU is driving a narrative that the minerals industry should perform much better in terms of health and safety, environmental responsibility, community benefits and stakeholder inclusiveness. Mining owners and operators should be much more aware of the influence that societal, environmental, and economic conditions have on them but also the impact they have on the health of nature, the EU dependence on other continents, and the sustainability of ecosystems after mining.

The aim of this deliverable was to provide detailed information on the technologies that the PERSEPHONE project will develop to respond to the demand described above and provide impetus for similar action further along the mineral value chain; to be the catalyst to challenge the frontier of humanless mining and to reach the state where mining only provide benefit to mankind and not be considered the industry that destroys the fragile home of mankind.

Based on aspirations of the PERSEPHONE project the following benefits will be derived from this project:

- Research in next generation technologies for achieving an energy efficient and sustainable development of next generation extraction systems in deep deposits and in abandoned/suspended mines.
- The development of technologies for online rock characterization and producing computer-aided extraction plans for deep/abandoned mines by developing next generation drilling systems.
- The development of next generation intelligent autonomy for deep mining exploration/production drilling and excavation machines that can operate in unknown extreme subterranean environments without on-site human assistance or installed infrastructure; and do this for multiple machines.
- The development of online solutions for continuous monitoring of mined material characteristics that leads to resource-efficient planning and execution of extraction plans.
- Building Digital Twins for the construction of data-driven and dynamic geo-modelling synthesis.

Within PERSEPHONE there are opportunities to further research and develop autonomous technologies for exploration and extraction in deep mines, abandoned and suspended mining projects. As interdisciplinary innovation, experimentation, and examination of legacy data are fundamental to facilitate the transition towards deep underground mining.

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12 Appendix 1 - Identification Of End-User Requirements, Evaluation Scenarios And Benchmarking Specifications For Technologies Developed Within PERSEPHONE Project

Grant agreement no.	101138451
Project acronym	PERSEPHONE
Title	IDENTIFICATION OF END-USER REQUIREMENTS, EVALUATION SCENARIOS AND BENCHMARKING SPECIFICATIONS FOR TECHNOLOGIES DEVELOPED WITHIN PERSEPHONE PROJECT
Document Type	Questionnaire
Related WP	WP1 - Specification and requirements for enabling sustainable deep mining
Related Activities	T1.2, T1.3., T1.5
Related Deliverable	Requirements, specifications and benchmarking tools for proposed technologies
Author/s	Björn Lindqvist (LTU), George Bourmas (GM), Johnny van den Berg (MRP), Krzysztof Fuławka (CUP).
Keywords	Technology requirements, Deep mining, Abandoned mines, Technology specification, Technology benchmarking,
Abstract	Adapting technologies to end-user requirements requires collecting detailed information regarding expectations, limitations and assumptions regarding the tested/developed technologies. This questionnaire will collect requirements specified by end-users of technologies developed in the PERSEPHONE project. Evaluation scenarios and benchmarking specifications for each technology will also be specified.

History of Changes

Version	Date	Reason of change
1.0	12 April 2024	First version of survey (sent to related PP)

Introduction

WP1 is focused on heavy research activities required to establish the definitions, specifications and conceptualization of operation and development in adopting smart, sustainable and autonomous deep-mining exploration and extraction practices of the future. This WP will contribute to the improvement of information exchange among the project partners from different research fields to create common goals and development plans while ensuring the operational demands of end users.

The new paradigm of exploring critical minerals in deep-mines or abandoned / suspended mines exceeds the traditional way of ore exploration mining, sensing, geology studying, mapping, mining operation, and thus WP1 aims to serve as a guide, ensuring aligned and synchronized developments in contrary to the fragmented and isolated planning.

To build awareness, trust and acceptance it is important that all end users and technological stakeholders in PERSEPHONE project will be involved in formulate this vision.

WP1 extract measurable benchmarking specifications, as the mechanisms to contextualise the overall impact of PERSEPHONE project.

Taking into account the above, it is necessary to collect a number of information from developers of individual technologies. In order to systematize the way of collecting information, a unified questionnaire was prepared, which aims to provide appropriate substantive input to T1.2, T1.3 and T1.5.

No of task
Please describe which will be described
List of technologies being developed (in this task)
If within one task more than one technology/software/method will be developed please list them here.

Detailed description of each technology/software/method

Description of technology X
Please describe briefly technology here. Please try to fill in the following information. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What device/technology/method is this? • What will be the development/research methodology? (theoretical methods, existing things to build on top of etc.) • What is this technology used for? • How will this technology be improved within the scope of the project?

- What contribution does this technology make to the current SoTA?
- What is the TRL of this technology?
- Can the technology be used in the exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits?
- Does the implementation of the technology for exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposits require additional/special infrastructure and devices?
- Can the technology be used in the exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines?
- Does the implementation of the technology to exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines require additional/special infrastructure and devices?

End-user requirements for implementation of technology in use case 1 (exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposit)

Identification of the end user for technology X
Who will be the end-user of technology?
End-user requirements
What requirements may be raised by end-users/mining operators in relation to developed technology?

Evaluation scenarios and benchmarking specifications for use case 1 (exploration and extraction of deep and hard-to-reach deposit)

Evaluation scenarios for technology X
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determine how you are going to evaluate the new technology/method/software efficiency. • What are the scenarios for this evaluation? Are you going to evaluate your technology in lab condition/operational condition/ based on simulation? • Will evaluation be qualitative? • Justify why evaluation based on parameters proposed by you is important and reliable.
Benchmarking specifications for technology X
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benchmarks refer to the criteria by which technology will be judged during an evaluation. Please determine benchmark for considered technology

**End-user requirements for implementation of technology in use case 2
(Exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines)**

Identification of the end user for technology X
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> According to section 3 – but refers to abandoned and suspended mines. Requirements in this case may be slightly different due to lack of proper infrastructure and accessibility.
End-user requirements
As above end-user requirements should be slightly different due to the abovementioned conditions.

**Evaluation scenarios and benchmarking specifications for use case 2
(Exploration and reactivation of abandoned and suspended mines)**

Evaluation scenarios for technology X
In the case of evaluation scenarios, it is possible that they will be similar for use case 1 and use case 2. Still, needs to be carefully analysed for each of technology/method/software.
Benchmarking specifications for technology X
As above benchmarking specifications may be similar for use case 1 and use case 2. Still, needs to be carefully analysed for each of technology/method/software.

13 Appendix 2 – Evaluation of the UNFC Supplement for ‘Minerals’ with respect to its applicability to PERSEPHONE-type technologies

In the following, the *Supplementary Specifications for the Application of the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources to Minerals* (UNECE, 2021) are reviewed with respect to which extent they cover the mining methods proposed by PERSEPHONE.

Table A.2.1. ‘G-axis Categories’ from the UNFC Supplement on Minerals.

G-Axis Categories (UNFC (2019) text in italics)		
<i>Category</i>	<i>Definition</i>	<i>Supporting explanation for minerals</i>
G1	<i>Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a high level of confidence.</i>	<i>Product quantity estimates may be categorised discretely as G1, G2 and/or G3 (along with the appropriate E and F Categories), based on the degree of confidence in the estimates (high, moderate and low confidence, respectively) based on direct evidence. Alternatively, product quantity estimates may be categorized as a range of uncertainty as reflected by either (i) three specific deterministic scenarios (low, best and high cases) or (ii) a probabilistic analysis from which three outcomes (P90, P50 and P10) are selected. In both methodologies (the “scenario” and “probabilistic” approaches), estimates are then classified on the G Axis as G1, G1+G2 and G1+G2+G3 respectively. In all cases, the product quantity estimates are those associated with a project.</i>
G2	<i>Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a moderate level of confidence.</i>	<i>Product quantity estimates may be categorised discretely as G1, G2 and/or G3 (along with the appropriate E and F Categories), based on the degree of confidence in the estimates (high, moderate and low confidence, respectively) based on direct evidence. Alternatively, product quantity estimates may be categorized as a range of uncertainty as reflected by either (i) three specific deterministic scenarios (low, best and high cases) or (ii) a probabilistic analysis from which three outcomes (P90, P50 and P10) are selected. In both methodologies (the “scenario” and “probabilistic” approaches), estimates are then classified on the G Axis as G1, G1+G2 and G1+G2+G3 respectively. In all cases, the product quantity estimates are those associated with a project.</i>
G3	<i>Product quantity associated with a project that can be estimated with a low level of confidence.</i>	<p><i>The G-axis Categories are intended to reflect all significant uncertainties (e.g. source uncertainty, geologic uncertainty, facility efficiency uncertainty, etc.) impacting the estimate forecast for the project. Uncertainties include variability, intermittency and the efficiency of the development and operation (where relevant). Typically, the various uncertainties will combine to provide a full range of outcomes. In such cases, categorization should reflect three scenarios or outcomes that are equivalent to G1, G1+G2 and G1+G2+G3.</i></p> <p>Additional Comments:</p> <p>The G axis in minerals and mining conditions primarily reflect geologic uncertainty impacting the estimate forecast for the project. Uncertainties include availability and resolution of direct data such as drill hole density in relation to the mineralisation and or deposit type.</p> <p>In addition, indirect data such as geophysical data might be included, which should be measured against redundancy of methods (e.g. geophysical measurements calibrated against drill core evaluation, drill hole logs. Calibrated methods provide higher certainty than uncalibrated methods.)</p> <p>The accuracy of measurements controls the level of the category (lab assay, rock mechanics, mineralogical phase assessment).</p>
G4	<i>Product quantity associated with a Prospective Project, estimated or postulated primarily on indirect evidence.</i>	<p><i>A Prospective Project is one where the existence of a developable product is based primarily on indirect evidence and has not yet been confirmed. Further data acquisition and evaluation would be required for confirmation.</i></p> <p><i>Where a single estimate is provided, it should be the expected outcome but, where possible, a full range of uncertainty should be calculated for the prospective project. Based on the lack of direct evidence, an estimation of qualities and quantities is not suitable and/or potentially misleading in mineral exploration.</i></p> <p><i>In addition, it is recommended that the chance of success (probability) that the prospective project will progress to a Viable Project is assessed and documented.</i></p>

Section A.6 concerns the mining methods and according to the definition proposed, it is likely that the PERSEPHONE techniques still fall into the category

of conventional underground mining, though due to the robots being used, exploration and extraction could take place below the water table without the usual dewatering of the mine.

Section B. Definitions of Categories and Sub-categories

The meaning of the axes E, F, and G have been explained in Figure 6.5. While the classification along all axes can change over time, changes along the G-axis are more likely to occur on a shorter timescale as exploration and/or exploitation progress. The level of confidence in the assessment will improve with more exploration or exploitation, which does not necessarily mean that quantities increase.

Section C. Minerals project evaluation

As item *“32. Minerals projects may adopt various methodologies in the various stages of the mineral life cycle including in the estimation of quantities as appropriate to the project. The basis for any estimations shall be appropriately referenced in the evaluation. This includes not only third-party data but also methodologies or procedures that have been used by the evaluating entity to generate in-house data.”* Indicates, various data sources can used and have to be adequately described. So, down-mine real-time data acquisition systems would be described.

As the knowledge about the workability of the rocks and the mineralogy of both, the ore and the host-rock increase, to some degree the assessments along the F-axis will improve (items 36 to 38). Most importantly, the degree of confidence in what can be extracted from the mine (item 39) will increase continuously, as new data are fed into the geological model.

Section D.1. Classification of projects based on the level of maturity

The classification according to the level of project maturity is very unlikely to change quickly and on the basis of the continuous data gathering. Such decisions would rather be made periodically, based on carefully weighing the evidence. However, exploring the space around and existing mine will provide information on the continuing viability or otherwise.

Section 4. Distinction between potentially produced quantities and undeveloped quantities

The at the mine-face assessments could have short-term impact on the classification per items:

47. Quantities of products associated with projects are categorized as F1 to F3 as potentially developable using existing technology or technology currently under development or operation. There may be remaining quantities with no development project. The product quantity associated with these are categorized as F4. These are quantities which, if produced, could be bought, sold or used.

and

48. In minerals projects these products may be currently unused by-products such as specific minerals or metals or mine waste (host rock) which could be used as aggregate material.

The respective estimations would be continuously updated and can also be used in the short-term planning of the mine operation, taking into consideration current market conditions.

Chapter E Project Reporting

2. Effective date

50. Reported estimates of mineral product quantities are as at the Effective Date of the evaluation. The Effective Date shall be clearly stated in conjunction with the estimate. The evaluation should take into account all data and information available to the evaluator prior to the Effective Date.

For the purpose of near real-time reporting as data are generated by the PERSEPHONE techniques, periodic 'effective dates' will need to be agreed upon, at which moment the Competent Expert will compile and submit an updated report.

3. Minerals product

52. Estimates should be classified separately for each minerals product that will be sold, transferred, used, unused or consumed in operations. Where estimates for different products have been aggregated for classification, and separate estimates are not provided, the aggregated estimates shall be accompanied by a statement clarifying which products have been aggregated and the conversion factor(s) used to render them equivalent for the purposes of aggregation.

53. Product types could include metallic minerals, non-metallic minerals and/or industrial minerals, ...

The down-mine sensor techniques developed under PERSEPHONE will allow a quasi-continuous updating of the mineralogical composition at the mine face. If significant changes in the mineralogy are detected, it has to be checked, whether this has an influence on the treatability of the ore and if necessary, the F-axis needs to be updated as well.

9. Avoidance of double counting

66. Reporting of estimates shall be exclusive for each class or sub-class. When different products are reported care should be taken to avoid double counting.

When an ore contains different target metals, care has to be taken not to double account the total quantity of ore.